

RESISTANCE AND SURVIVAL : AN ECOFEMINIST READING OF MAHASWETA DEVI'S CHOTTI MUNDA AND HIS ARROW

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Abstract:

Ecofeminism which is introduced in the 1970s deals with the connection between the subjugated status of women, nature and other oppressed classes. As a movement ecofeminism rejecting previously held dominant ideologies of patriarchal as well as colonial domination holds the belief that the oppression of women and the domination over the other inferior sections of the society by men carry the link to the degradation of environment. Locating resistance and survival of the subaltern in her novel *Chotti Munda and His Arrow* Mahasweta Devi draws out the unspoken and unwritten history of the subaltern, the history of their survival that is wrapped by the importance of the elite class. Searching history through her visiting to the tribal villages she writes the tragedy of their survival, their connection to nature, their culture of archery and their resistance against their exploiters. What I intend to highlight here is the survival and solidarity of the subaltern from an ecofeminist viewpoint in postcolonial context where history, nature, culture and identity being dominated by the elite class seek the way out from these dilemmas through their innate connection to their culture of archery. Thus challenging dominant strategies of the elite class, Mahasweta Devi empowers the subaltern to resist by their strategies of survival in postcolonial context.

Keywords: *Chotti Munda and His Arrow, Ecofeminism, Mahasweta Devi, Postcolonial, Subaltern, Survival, Resistance.*

Chotti Munda, as per Gayatri Chakravoty Spivak, repeatedly dramatizes subaltern solidarity : Munda, Oraon, and the Hindu outcastes must work together. Today such a solidarity has a name : dalit. The seduction of an identitarianism in the name of the dalit can learn a lesson here. With a degree of regret, Chotti accepts that cultural identity must be--to take an altogether inappropriate metaphor that is easy for the reader to understand--museumized (*Chotti Munda* 290).

While Spivak's "Can the subaltern speak?" strongly declares the muteness of the

subaltern Mahasweta Devi's *Chotti Munda and His Arrow* holds the voices of the subalterns, the language of their culture of archery. Mahasweta Devi, along with the records of the colonial and postcolonial history, draws out the voices of the Mundas who are the victims of the criminalization of politics, merciless torment and oppression. She says, "What Chotti Munda or my other stories and books depict is a continuing struggle" (*Chotti Munda* ix). While saving the tribal culture and traditions from being disappeared, Mahasweta Devi emphasizes a series of dilemmas, responsible to affect the subaltern world and enough to give voice to

the subalterns. On one hand, the novel depicts the tyrannical supremacy of the landowners, moneylenders and the contractors who benefit from the support of the government and clutch the Mundas and the untouchables through everlasting bondage, on the other hand, it represents the inequality, poverty, deprivation and humiliation of the tribal communities. What this article intends to focus is to analyse Mahasweta Devi's *Chotti Munda and His Arrow* from the view point of Ecofeminism. As a theory it is still at a budding stage and needs more examination for its wide recognition. The term ecofeminism is coined by the French writer Françoise d'Eaubonne in her book *Le féminisme ou la Mort* in 1974. It deals with a link between feminism and ecology. It approaches a connection between the subjugated status of women, nature and other oppressed classes. She shows how male dominated society and its masculine power are responsible for the oppression of women and exploitation of nature. On one hand, ecofeminism works as a theory and on the other hand, it works as both movement and philosophy. As a theory it connects all kinds of social domination along with the domination over women and exploitation of nature.

For Ynestra King, "Ecofeminism's challenge of social domination extends beyond sex to social domination of all kinds, because the domination of sex, race, and class and the domination of nature are mutually reinforcing. (quoted in *Ecofeminism: Women, Culture, Nature* 21).

While as a movement ecofeminism rejects previously held dominant ideologies like patriarchal and colonial domination to establish sustainable society, as a philosophy it erases all forms of social injustice by erasing the dualistic notions (man/woman, nature /culture etc.) to liberate all the subordinated classes. In *Chotti Munda and His Arrow* Mahasweta Devi showing her concern on the tribal life, their survival and their protest against the

exploitation made by the landowners and the moneylenders proves her liability as a writer to draw out the unwritten history of the subaltern so that it can not be vanished. As ecofeminism reveals women-nature connection, in this novel ecofeminist perspective becomes clear through Mahasweta Devi's urge of writing about the tribals, about their history, about their survival, their bondage with nature and their native culture of archery. Various kinds of movements are the origins of ecofeminism. "The women and life on earth : ecofeminism in the eighties" conference held at Amherst (1980) was the first ecofeminist conference to encourage the ecofeminist organizations and activities. Karen J. Warren says: "the living conditions of women, people of color, the poor, and children ... are an ecofeminist issue" (*Ecofeminism: Women, Culture, Nature* 12). In *Chotti Munda and His Arrow* the living condition of tribal women, caste discrimination, poverty problem among the Mundas and the uncertain future of the tribal children are also an ecofeminist issue.

From the beginning of the novel it is very clear that the Mundas are very insecure in their land where they have no right to touch and see the precious goods and by chance if the precious goods come into their hands they are driven out from that area as Purti Munda remembers "how White men and Biharis jumped at the sight of coal and mica, how instantly they disfigured adivasi areas with slums of tile-roofed dwellings. Who knows what such people will do if they see gold? These hills, these forests, this river will once again be spoiled" (*Chotti Munda and His Arrow* 2). Mahasweta Devi states about the Mundas' consciousness of the ecological system that makes them to fight for planting *sal* and removing *sagun*. They know that *sal* has commercial value but *sagun* is ecologically worthy. Karen J. Warren states:

both deforestation and reforestation through the introduction of a monoculture species tree (e.g. eucalyptus) intended for commercial production are feminist issues because the

loss of indigenous forests and multiple species of trees has drastically affected rural Indian woman's ability to maintain a subsistence household (Karren Warren 127).

At the age of fourteen Chotti is sent to Parmi's father-in-law's house where he sees that the entire village is occupied by the other Bihari sects and castes "poor upper caste, rich upper-caste etc." (*Chotti Munda* 5). He also sees how the entire family goes to do bonded labour and he is prohibited to go to Dhani Munda. "I still say, when t' bow's in his hands, Munda societies and families are in danger" (*Chotti Munda* 5). The non-tribal impostors, being integrated as moneylenders, freelancers and agents provides credit service to the Mundas and the other low caste untouchables. This facility apparently brings relief among the Mundas but in reality it is very manipulative. The exploiters being assisted by the British acts not only exploit the tribal communities and untouchables but also they help the British to dislocate these people from their land. Actually the British needs to displace these people with the arrival of industries and making new projects. Thus they are underprivileged by the colonialism which snatching their traditional mode of survival bring them under the trap of revenue and landownership "...a strategy to situate the writing of a conquered people's history by conquerors at the very heart of the question of one nation's oppression by another" (*Dominance without Hegemony* xiii). The privilege, enjoyed by the elite class gives birth to the supremacy of modern capitalism, possessed a relation to the old feudal system. Ranajit Guha states:

...that subordination cannot be understood except as one of the constitutive terms in a binary relationship of which the other is dominance, for 'subaltern groups' are always subject to the activity of ruling groups, even when they rebel and rise up. (*Subaltern Studies* vii).

Mahasweta Devi shows here that it is not Lord Birsa's Ulgulan but Chotti Munda's spellbound arrow which signifies Chotti's opposing power against the moneylenders. As Joseph Pieper states:

Culture depends for its very existence on leisure, and leisure, in its turn, is not possible unless it has a durable and living link with the cultus, with divine worship... Culture... is the quintessence of all the natural goods of the world and of those gifts and qualities which, while belonging to man, lie beyond the immediate sphere of his needs and wants. (quoted in Karen J. Warren 160)

Chotti Munda's association with Dhani Munda brings another kind of story in Chotti's life that makes him a heroic figure in his village. Chotti is well aware of the facts of the tribal survival: "How the earth was made, how that earth was burnt in the fire of Shengelda, how a man and a woman survived, how a new earth was created..." (*Chotti Munda and His Arrow* 7). But the new epic which he comes to know from Dhani Munda about the Munda life happens twenty years ago. Mahasweta Devi shows here the inner sufferings of Dhani Munda who is compelled to be silent for the lives of the Mundas who will be tortured if he shows rage. The police tells Dhani not to go anywhere either his job will be lost. He tells Dhani further: "Yes I will not tease t' Munda people But e'en t' Gormen don't want new torture and t' Munda roughed up" (*Chotti Munda* 6). Chotti Munda comes to know about the new torture that is related to bonded labour while at the time of harvest the entire family members of Parmi's father-in-law's house went to give bonded labour. Dhani cannot tolerate this kind of bondage for the Munda communities.

Where d'ye go? Dhani roared.
Bond labour!
Yes grandpa.

To gie bond labour? Dontcha Know? That bond labour is one among all th' ills he fought against?(*Chotti Munda* 6).

Dhani disgracefully says that the Munda communities here are the broken-backed and live on the kindness of Diku-Hindus. "As if in the unbearable pain of not being able to speak ,Dhani spoke, They know I'm t' Haramgod of archery. They think if I lift an arrer I'll call t' great revolt ---Ulgulan--- again" (*Chotti Munda* 8). Thus Dhani has been presented as a great rebel of stubborn spirit, an epithet of ground-breaking fortitude. His madness and tremendous hurriedness inside his heart lead him to many revolts:

Dhani was always crazy , at the time of the Santal Hul Dhani was a lad of twenty. The Kherwar revolt, the Mulkoil revolt of the Sardars, and then Birsa's revolt. Armed struggle is also an addiction. He went to all the revolts in the hope that Mundas would establish villages in forest and arable land and farm rightfully and in peace..." (*Chotti Munda* 11).

Mahasweta Devi says : "Archery was very much in their blood"(xi). She thinks Birsa Munda's resistance is continued through Chotti Munda's magic arrow that is handed over to him by Dhani Munda. This arrow becomes the weapon of their survival.Chotti not only takes the learning of archery from Dhani Munda but his soul is also ignited by Dhani's teachings. Dhani abuses Chotti that his interest only lies in winning Chotti fair and there is no progress or no struggle to change the Munda's life or "no piercin' of moneylender, polis, an' soldier with' arrests in t' heat of that fire, but there's t' chotti fair. Gormen babysits t' Munda tribe that way" (*Chotti Munda* 10). Parmi's father-in-law says that the Lalas or traders give them to plough the land as there produces no good crop. If they come to know anyway about the pepper they will take away. So they can do nothing in spite of their knowledge of growing pepper in this land. It is enough for them that

rice grows here. Mundas and the Oraons possess no land. "All t' land is Diku Land--- Hindu Land...."(*Chotti Munda* 11). Partha Chatterjee says, "The tension between a peasant community and an external exploitative force also becomes clear in the case of the operation of outside traders or moneylenders, particularly when they are racially or culturally distinct from peasantry" (*Subaltern Studies* 19). In the novel the representation of displacement, disproportion, casteism, famine, dispossession and humiliation is abounding. Here the wealthy and dominant landowners like Lala Bajinath and his son Tirathnath both lash out and humiliate the tribals by taking bonded labour from them. Lala Bajinath and the Daroga together forcefully push Bisra Munda towards death. He is compelled to hang himself as without any kind of fault he is bitterly beaten by the Daroga. Tirathnath thinks that to take the bonded labour from the Mundas and the untouchables is his natural duty. In time of drought when the Mundas and the untouchables go to Tirathnath to get some food, he orders his manager to give them the last year's maize which is full of bugs. But while they are able to understand the deception of Tirathnath ,Chotti gathering all the Mundas with bows and arrows loots the granaries of Tirathnath. The daroga does not do any kind of report regarding famine so that Tirathnath can take bonded labour from them. Janis Birkeland opines: "In Western Patriarchal culture masculine constructs and values have been internalized in our minds, embodied in our institutions, and played out in power-based social relations both in our daily lives and upon the world stage" (Greta Gaard 17). Another Munda named Dukhiya from kurmi village informs Chotti that he is a bond-slave of Nakata king's manager who not only tied him up with perpetual bondage but also his woman betrays him and marries to an another man. Dukhiya becomes unable to tolerate the abuses from the Manager and cutting him down hangs himself. As Frantz Fanon in his *The Wretched of the Earth* draws out the psychological trauma of the

colonized people, Mahasweta Devi also demonstrates the psychological sufferings from drudgery and plight of the Mundas under the bonded labours of the landlords. In *The Post-colonial studies Reader* Jan Mohamed states: "Genuine and thorough comprehension of Otherness is possible only if the self can somehow negate or at least severely bracket the values, assumptions, and ideology of his culture." (Abdul R. Jan Mohamed 18). Mahasweta Devi narrates:

It's as if Dukhia is drunk, drunk, as if he's free at last from the bond-slavery of his soul's thousand sorrows. His legs tremble a bit, he gives an innocent glance that holds a worldwide astonishment, and he says, Ye said he wouldn't badmouth no more. But then he comes to take his cut from t' market. I'm sittin' here with red pepper ---come to take his cut why does he move me hand with t' tip of his shoe? (*Chotti Munda* 54).

Dukhiya tells that nothing is deposited in his book in turn of the bonded labour which is started from his father's father and their entire generation is bounded by that. He says that they are to do various kinds of bonded labour. When the manager goes to the king's court, they take his palquin. The entire day is spoiled and neither food nor drink is given to them. Ania Loomba says:

The colonial contact is not just reflected in the language or imaginary of literary texts, it is not just backdrop or context against which human dramas are enacted, but a central aspect of what these texts have to say about identity, relationships and culture. (*Colonialism/Postcolonialism* 73)

In a similar way another Munda named Puran is exploited and oppressed by Tasilder Singh who smashes his house by placing elephant into it. Tasildar Singh after coming back from the king's hunt, a poisonous arrow pierces his back and he dies. Later it becomes clear that he is killed by Puran whose only purpose of learning archery is to stand against injustice. Janis Birkeland in her

essay "Ecofeminism: Linking theory and Practice" states that ecofeminism presents a proper understanding into the connection between the mistreatment of personal and political power which lie behind oppression of human beings and exploitation of environment. Mahasweta Devi along with subaltern humans also contributes picture of the subaltern nature in this novel. She demonstrates the tribal's sense of responsibility for nature. Offering Dhani Munda's ecological talent Mahasweta Devi shows how it leads towards a harmonious relationship between human beings and non-human nature. Taking Chotti into the forest Dhani called the jungle Our Mother and tells "Let me learn ye t' jungle. With jungle learning' ye won' die starvin' What isn't there in the jungle?" (*Chotti Munda* 11). The Mundas, being the original inhabitants always maintain the ancient pattern of settling. When a particular village or settlement becomes overpopulated, heads of the society find out another uninhabited place and assess its aptness in terms of soil, water and wind flows. If it appears favourable they drive a pole (Khunt) into the ground. The adjacent virgin forest will also be cleared to set up a village. Thus the Mundas' pattern of setting up a village becomes very healthy and pollution free as it is completely free from over population. Purti Munda's inside reconciliation with nature becomes clear while he opines if the white man and the Biharis come to be settled here "These hills, these forests, this river will once again be spoiled" (*Chotti Munda* 2). Again Dhani Munda's deep association with nature makes him oblige to shout on behalf of nature, on behalf of the forest. T'forest cried. Told him, Birsa, Diku-Master-White man ---together they've made me unclean, naked, undressed, clean me up. The adivasis' ecological knowledge and their skill are exploited by the landowning class. Thus the Mundas cannot cultivate pepper despite of its economic value as the landowners will snatch it away if they come to know.

Chaia Heller in her article “For the Love of Nature” says:

The ability to really know nature requires a continual process of critical self-consciousness. We are social creatures looking at the world through social eyes. In order to see nature, we must be increasingly conscious of our social desires and anxieties, our reluctance to relinquish power within society. If we are not conscious of our own greed, then we will see nature as a greedy force from which we must continually steal in order to survive....A metaphor that emerges within the language of a tribal people cannot be accurately translated into the language of an oppressive people. (*Ecofeminism: Women, Animals, Nature* 231)

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TRANSGENDER AUTOBIOGRAPHIES: ADVANCES IN HUMAN RIGHTS AND SOCIAL CHANGE

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Abstract:

'Third Gender' as stated by the law, *Hijras* as the tradition bearers, and as the umbrella term Transgender, covers all these expressions under its domain. The term 'third gender' came to practice after the verdict of Supreme Court of India on 15th April, 2014 and recognized the transgender as 'third gender.' Apart from the law and order it enabled for the protection of transgender, and projected the need to establish human rights in the society for transgender. There is a need to protect and promote the rights of transgender and this cannot be achieved by documenting it in the form of a law, in isolation. Literature also plays a vital role in establishing and asserting human rights in society as it reveals manifold forms of lives and helps in a deep understanding of the social system. It not only portrays the imitation of human action but also serves as a corrective mirror and brings in a positive change as it gets circulated and reaches the larger readers. The objective of this paper is to present that apart from law and rules, literature is also an important tool to sensitize and establish human rights in society. This paper will study and analyze some of the literary texts i.e., autobiographies written by transgender from India from a human rights perspective.

Keywords: *Autobiography, Human Rights, Transgender, Laws*

Transgender studies is a subfield of LGBT studies (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender/Transsexual) and it provides an interdisciplinary approach to gender studies, gay and lesbian studies, women studies and sexology by dealing with the intersections of sex and gender intertwined with the culture, lives and political movements. Transgender studies further deals with the social and political ramifications related to the community which includes transgender history, liberation, literature, ethnography, anthropology, psychology and health related issues. Transgender studies is an established area in the West with the efforts of theorists like Judith Butler, Simone De Beauvoir and Magnus Hirschfield and academicians such as Paisley Currah and Susan Stryker who initiated the first non-medical academic journal *Transgender Studies Quarterly* in 2014 devoted to transgender issues. In India, the *hijras* are a visible community and directly or indirectly we have read and heard the mythologies, beliefs and ideas related to the *hijras* and *hijra* community. They are an important part of India's cultural beliefs as the harbinger of blessings on the newlyweds and newborn children. Their visibility in the society is in contrast to their absence from the academia in India. This doesn't imply that their indifference makes them the subject of investigation but there is a need for a space of discourse which has been narrow. Their discourse should not be confined to the domain of gender studies as

there is much more that is needed and can be unraveled from within.

Third Gender

‘Third Gender’ as *hijras* are usually referred in India, to denote transgender was introduced in 1975 by M. Kay Martin and Barbara Voorhies, who employed it to draw attention to the ethnographic evidence that gender categories in some cultures could not be adequately explained with a two-gender framework. This revelation had profound implications for feminist and gender theorists as well as for social movements and political activists in the United States, as it allowed them to think outside a dichotomous gender system. ‘Third gender’ began to be applied to behaviors that transcended or challenged male-female codes or norms. It was also applied to societies that seemed to provide institutionalized intermediate gender concepts and practices. In India, the term ‘third gender’ came to practice after the verdict of Supreme Court of India on April, 15, 2014 and recognized the transgender as ‘third gender.’ ‘*Tritya Prakriti*’ is another expression in Sanskrit that was used to define ‘third gender’ in pre-colonial India. The term was taken from Hindu texts (*Puranas*) and mythologies which defined *tritya prakriti* as third gender which would encompass any gender outside the dichotomous framework.

Will Roscoe in the book *Changing ones: Third and Fourth Gender* (1998) introspects about the changing gender roles in North America, “Third gender generally refers to male berdaches and female berdaches, while fourth gender always refer to female berdaches”. The term ‘berdache’ is an anthropological term used in North America as a whole to define multiple gender significations. The term is not synonymous to Indian *hijra* or transgender as a whole. The term was replaced with ‘two-spirit’ and it has sacred, spiritual and ceremonial role connotations and has nothing to do with identities and their sexual orientation. It can

be concluded that there are cultural connotations and beliefs related to a certain identity that cannot be justified or measured by a given parameter. The Indian *hijra* and the North American *berdache* includes people with distinct and a few similar identities and orientations but it doesn’t necessarily put them under same roof. The two terms are not synonymous but are alike.

TG Rights and Laws in India

Human rights are integral to all the genders, male, female and the third gender. All the rights are assigned by the Indian Constitution. With the legalization of transgender as ‘third gender’ there are laws and rights enacted in favour of them. Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code dating back to 1860 was introduced during the British rule in India which criminalizes sexual activities ‘against the order of nature’ arguably the homosexual sexual activities. It was decriminalized by High Court of Delhi on July 2009 but the judgment was overturned by the Supreme Court of India on 11 December 2013. On Feb 6, 2016, it was decided by the Chief Justice of India T.S. Thakur that it will be reviewed afresh by a five-member constitutional branch. A. Revathi, a trans-woman and activist, retrospects in *A Life in Transactivism*: “society thinks that vaginal or penetrative sex is the only kind of sex that is ‘natural.’ Transgender persons are not even regarded as people. We are seen as sexual deviants who are meant to satisfy only the perverse pleasures of male clients” (59). Though there is a legal recognition of the gender identity of the transgender, the paradox faced by them is the criminalization by section 377 of the Indian Penal Code. It violates their right to life, autonomy, dignity guaranteed under Article 21, right to equality under Article 14 and their right to expression and freedom under Article 19 as the petition states. Further the Transgender protection of Rights Bill, 2016 has been enacted by the parliament which seeks to:

- define a transgender person;
- prohibit discrimination against transgender person;
- confer right upon transgender person to be recognized as such, and a right to self-perceived gender identity;
- issue of certificate of identity to transgender persons;
- provide that no establishment shall discriminate against transgender person
- in matters relating to employment, recruitment, promotion and other related issues;
- provide for grievance redressal mechanism in each establishment;
- establishment of a National Council for Transgender;
- punishment for contraventions of the provisions of the Bill (1-10).

Apart from the laws that are enacted for the welfare of transgenders, the other issues that can be addressed or included for their upliftment in the society as Dhishna P, an Indian critic in her study suggests in “Implications of Gender Studies: Male, Female and the Third Genders” (2016):

The process of understanding gender identity is a more complex task as the notions of gender are unlimited with the body, the psyche, desires and passion of individuals. Normativity in sexual identity remains a cultural construct. When one talks about gender rights all these aspects need to be taken into consideration simultaneously. This could reason for the marginalized genders to gain more relevance in the present (10).

The above nuances related to transgender were entitled in the bill for their amelioration but the question arises; is it actually benefitting them to get a secure and a respectable position in the society? More than everything there is a need to establish and spread awareness regarding transgender rights as they suffer persistent inequalities in the aspects of life at the hands of the society.

They are subjected to trans-phobic attacks which results in non-acceptance in the society. Trans-phobia refers to expressions of fear and hatred of trans-people. There is need to understand the affect of myriad forms of oppressions that they face. Viviane Namaste in *Sex Change, Social Change* (2005) argues:

Transsexual lives are ordered, governed, and controlled in and through the criminalization of prostitution.” Moreover, both she and Mirha-Soleil Ross claim that trans-women suffer not only due to the poverty, homelessness, illness, and discrimination attendant on their lower socioeconomic backgrounds, but also as sex workers, in which work the majority experience violence that goes unnoticed (27).

Oppression on *hijras* as sex-workers is also rampant and *hijra* autobiographies give evidence to such conduct. Revathi in her autobiography *The Truth about Me* (2010) recalls her experience while she was walking on the streets for sex work. Having figured out by the man that she is a transgender she was beaten and kicked by the man. She retrospects:

Khoja! Fucker! Shouting, he pulled me by my hair, threw me down and kicked me. He beat me again, and then rushed to his car and took out a knife. I hit at his hand and the knife dropped. I tried to run, but he pulled at my sari. He kept pulling until he had stripped me of it, and I was down to my petticoat and blouse (215).

Law and order form the rules but law and literature together can bring in the much needed parity and acceptance. A. Revathi in her book *A Life in Trans Activism* (2016) clearly portrays the change that literature can bring. She mentions, “The overwhelming public response for my books is the source of great satisfaction for me. I feel that the reason I took to writing has been validated” (xiii).

Literature and Transgender

Literature also plays a vital role in establishing and asserting human rights in society as it reveals manifold forms of lives and helps in a deep understanding of the social system. As defined in *Encyclopedia Britannica*;

Literature is a body of written works. The name has traditionally been applied to those imaginative works of poetry and prose distinguished by the intentions of their authors and the perceived aesthetic excellence of their execution. The art of literature is not reducible to the words on the page; they are there solely because of the craft of writing. As an art, literature might be described as the organization of words to give pleasure. Yet through words literature elevates and transforms experience beyond “mere” pleasure. Literature also functions more broadly in society as a means of both criticizing and affirming cultural values.

It not only portrays the imitation of human action but also serves as a corrective mirror and brings in a positive change as it gets circulated and reaches the larger readers. In this context, the autobiographies that have been chosen for this study are Vidya’s *I am Vidya* (2007), A. Revathi’s *The Truth about Me* (2010). These two autobiographies portray the experiences (physical and mental) in various stages of their lives especially during transition from a cisgender to a transgender and then further acceptance and inclusion to the society. This paper will highlight the various incidents where they put in their courage to stand up for themselves in the face of stiff opposition and go forward in their quest for self-completion. The focus is on the experiences and atrocities as faced by transgenders at the hand of society as revealed in the autobiography and the need for transgender human rights. Literature can play as a tool in order to sensitize and spread awareness in the society.

Autobiography as a Genre of Literary Studies in Research

Autobiography is a literary genre known for its use by women to write about their hidden lives. Mary Evans introspects, “The feminist ‘project’ of using autobiography to uncover the hidden lives of women is just one example of the use to which genre can be put” (37). With the advent of time, autobiography as a genre is also used by transgender to express their deeper self. It is new literary genre in picture. Though there are various genres of literary composition used by the writers to depict transgender in their works, but autobiography as a research method and as a genre used by transgender “demonstrates the way in which individuals are perceived and judged both within a culture and by those with more distance from it” (37). The major genres in literature are poetry, prose, drama, autobiography and biography. The main feature that settles autobiography as genre is that of offering insight into the extent to which a particular individual can be understood and evaluated. It becomes less about the person and more about the relationship between the individual and the society. But it is important to distinguish the motives responsible for different kinds of autobiography. “Autobiography can be-and often is-about an individual, but as well as being either by or about an individual, it can also be a collective subject” (38). Simone De Beauvoir’s *Memoirs of a Dutiful Daughter* is an example of autobiography written about escape from a certain social milieu. It can be concluded in the words of Mary Evans that: “When individuals write autobiographies, they often locate themselves as people who have had a battle against a particular culture” (38). So, autobiographical method of research holds a very significant place in research and autobiography makes it possible for marginalized genders to reach a larger domain. It can be inferred that autobiography is a tool for marginalized genders to write about their hidden lives. Other genres can’t do a similar justice with the marginalized

subjects as the essence to express one's individual self in relation with the culture and society will be lost.

'Third Gender', the lawful signification given by Supreme Court of India to *hijras* (eunuchs) in order to protect their rights and interests, but the question arises; Is it actually helping them to evolve or stumble on a decent place in the society or the social system? Their status in the society is self explanatory to this question. "They continued to beat me, and I continued to scream. When the train stopped at Pimpri, someone shouted, 'Push the creature out!'" (I am Vidya, 102). It succinctly portrays the atrocities that a transgender face in their day to day lives. This brings into the much needed factor to be incorporated in the social system in order to protect the rights of transgender i.e. human rights. Human Rights are moral principles and they are inherent to all human beings regardless of their nation, location, religion, caste, creed, ethnicity, sex or sexuality. They are universal laws and they are egalitarian in the sense of being same to each and every one. The basic idea of human rights movements emanated after the Second World War and the atrocities of the Holocaust culminating in the adoption of Universal Declaration of Human Rights in Paris by United Nations Assembly in 1948. The case of transgender or the *hijra* community is totally opposite in this regard as in India, though they are given the status of 'third gender', still transgenders are looked down with ridicule and disrespect. As mentioned in the Writ petition (Civil) No.400 of 2012 versus Writ petition (Civil) 604 of 2013 regarding transgender community in India;

Our society often ridicules and abuses the Transgender community and in public places like railway stations, bus stands, workplaces, theatres, hospitals, they are sidelined and treated as untouchables forgetting the fact that the moral failure lies in the society's unwillingness to contain or embrace different

gender identities and expressions, a mindset which we have to change (2).

With the coming of gender fluid identities and identities that are tailored by sex assignment surgeries, it is expected of cisgenders to embody and encapsulate these changes in the society. Further as mentioned in the Writ Petition, where they have referred the German philosopher Immanuel Kant, who was of the view that "at the basis of all conceptions of justice, no matter which culture or religion has inspired them, lies the golden rule that you should treat others as you would want everybody to treat everybody else, including yourself" (107). Further the reference to John Rawl's notion of Justice as 'fairness' is combined with the notions of Distributive Justice, to which Noble Laureate Prof. Amartya Sen subscribed;

We get jurisprudential basis for doing justice to Vulnerable Groups which include TGs. Once it is accepted that the TGs are also a part of Vulnerable Groups and marginalized sections of the society, we are only bringing them within the fold of aforesaid rights recognized in respect of other classes falling in the marginalized group. This is the minimum riposte in an attempt to assuage the insult and injury suffered by them so far as to pave way for fast tracking the realization of their human rights (109).

Vidya in her autobiography *I am Vidya* describes the importance of literature to fight depression and overcome fear. She writes, "Literature and solitude were my companions" (41). Vidya through her autobiography tries to communicate her turmoil of being a woman in a man's body followed by her fear of 'coming out' as female. "I had no problem with people recognizing my femininity but hated it when they made fun of me on that account" (56). In the process, she tried to hide her femininity due to the non-acceptance of a transgender in the society. It is not about the acceptance or non-acceptance of a

transgender in the social system, but the way society treats them. She mentions:

I was a girl. Unfortunately, the world saw me as a boy. Inwardly I wanted to be girl, but I made every effort possible to hide my femininity from outside world. I took particular trouble to remain inconspicuous at college, my unpleasant memories of my bitter experience at school still afresh in my mind. I tried to lead a false life of strenuous attempts like a man and speak like one. (40).

Despite her efforts to hide her femininity she couldn't hide it and was made fun of, ridiculed and considered repository of shame by her classmates in the school. Vidya retrospects:

Crude puns were invented by my classmates to scribble my name along with them on blackboard- for instance adding suffix 'ali', a colloquialism for eunuchs, to regular Tamil words to describe me. (32).

Being a transgender, A. Revathi in her autobiography *The Truth About Me* brings up the duties that are expected of a male child in the family. She gives instances of her friend who wanted to undergo transition but couldn't. "My friend did not want to go to Delhi with me. He was an only son and so he decided to live at home, hiding his feminine feelings, expressing them only on the hill-top" (36). Due to the approach of the society and family he was holding back his desires and chose to continue his life as a male. She also adds the lack of support from her family and the ill treatment by her brother because of her decision to be transgender and had undergone Sex- reassignment surgery. "My brothers came home when my father was not there and threatened me, 'you pottai motherfucker! Be glad that we've let you in sari! Think you can hang around with those number nines, with your cock chopped off, and still demand your share of property'" (168). This was the intense struggle Revathi had to undergo to be accepted by the family. Revathi fought for her house with his father

as she built it. She feels that it is a step in assertion of rights of the *hijras* to have the right to own property. It is significant step to reclaim the lost spaces.

Vidya's autobiography gives instances about the violence being inflicted on her and on transgenders as a whole and there is no one to raise a voice against it or provide protection. How can one be a mute spectator to such violence and injustice? Being *hijras*, *pottais* or *trirunangais* doesn't mean they would live their life devoid of the basic human rights. Vidya mentions:

Now four or five people surrounded me again. One of them held my arms and intertwined them between the stairs of the ladder to upper berth. Another pulled my hair. A third thug belted me with the buckle end hitting my face. His wild swing of belt found my cheekbone and I started bleeding (102).

If someone beats me, pinches me, scolds me, I hurt. I long for respect. I want to live a life of dignity. I want to go to work as many women do. But who gives people like me love? Or respect? Who offers us clothes to hide our shame? When I am hungry who feeds me? Did I come with a mission at birth, wanting to be a pottai? I did not imagine that I would talk endlessly on several roads, begging, doing sex work (*I am Vidya* 220).

In "Living Smile Vidya's Traumatic Experiences- an Overview" by S. Ramya writes: "The title of all the 15 chapters (*Appa, A time for farewell, Accept me!, Chatla, I want to live with pride*) by itself explains the trauma she underwent throughout her life" (34). Vidya shares her experiences while staying in hostel during the college days. She adds; "I had to share a room with my mates in Madurai. Fear and worry dominated my thoughts, even thought they were all boys. In my heart, I knew I was not a male and that made me nervous. My nights were hell, filled with the fear of detection and ridicule by the students

gathered there” (41). The fear in the mind of transgender is rampant because the societal stereotypical mindset to treat them in an ill manner. M. Mondal in the study “Gender Geometry: A Study of Revathi’s Autobiography” mentions, “even though transgender identities have legal approval, and is currently enjoying much attention in the academic domain— “Trans identities were one of the most written about subjects of the late twentieth century” (Whittle xi) but the ground reality narrates a saga of social discrimination and psychic torture” (126).

A. Revathi’s autobiography *The Truth About Me* begins with a Preface that tells the clear motive of writing the autobiography;

As a hijra I get pushed to the fringes of society. Yet I have dared to share my innermost life with you--- about being a hijra and also doing sex work [...] My aim is to introduce to the readers the lives of hijras, their distinct culture, and their dreams and desires [...] I hope now that by publishing my life story, larger changes can be achieved. I hope this book of mine will make people see that hijras are capable of more than just begging and sex work. I do not seek sympathy from society or the government. I seek to show that we hijras do have the rights to live in this society. (v-vi)

Conclusion

To conclude, there is a need to translate human rights into transgender rights. This can be achieved with the help of literature as it is also an important tool to sensitize and promote transgender rights in the society. The social system needs to take off their stigma and work towards accepting them as individuals as part of the society. To achieve this end, transgender rights need to be implemented in the society. Law and Literature together can pave the way for this social change. A Revathi’s poetical lines in *A Life in Trans Activism* that sums their expectations from cisgenders, “We will continue to struggle, we ask not for your

pity, only your understanding” (68) suggests this unending struggle of transgenders to establish their gender identity.

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Brief Summary on Women's Rights & Duties

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(Regd: 12ICHRD2)

Abstract:

Human society and social behaviour has undergone many changes over the centuries. The structure and function of societies as well as roles and duties of their members changed according to the situation. In India, the position of women has always been a rather ambivalent one in our culture. On the one side, she has been raised to the status of divinity and on the other side; she has been exploited by men in every walk of life. All through the ages, women have contributed immensely to the enrichment of culture and progress of civilisation without getting due recognition for their contribution. The importance role played by women in globalisation i.e. electronics, information technology, food processing, agro-industry and textiles has been crucial to the development of these sectors. In view of the critical role of women in the agriculture fields. The programmes for training women in soil conservation, social forestry, dairy development and other occupational allied to agriculture like horticulture, livestock including small animal husbandry, poultry and fisheries. In view the another importance role by women in decision making. Women's equality is power sharing and active participation in decision making, including decision making in political process at all levels with be ensured for the achievement of the goals of empowerment.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Duties, Rights & Women*

Rights and Duties are two wheels on which the chariot of life moves forward smoothly. Life can become smooth if rights and Duties go hand in hand and became complementary to each other. Rights are what we want others to do for us whereas the duties are those acts which we should perform for others. The term 'Rights' means? Rights are rules of interaction between people. They place constraints and obligations upon the actions of the state and individuals or groups. For example, if one has a right to life, this means that others do not have the liberty to kill him or her. Rights are defined as claims of an individual that are essential for the development of his or her own self and that are recognised by society or state. But the rights have real meaning only if individuals perform duties. A duty is something that someone is expected or required to do. Parents for example have a

duty to take care of their child: you have duties towards your parents. A teacher has a duty to educate students.

Relationship between Rights and Duties:

Rights and Duties are two phrases as co-exist with each other. In other words the rights and duties are two sides of the same coin, to regulate the values and behavioural patterns of an individual. On one side, rights are important in developing the human personality and behaviour. The duties on the other hand, direct the individuals' importance of their contribution for the promotion of social good. In a way duty targets at the realization of rights guaranteed by various law and regulations both nationally and internationally (*Sastry, N.S.T, 2011*).

Women Rights and Human Rights:

Human rights are those minimum rights which are compulsorily obtainable by every individual as he/she is a member of human family. The constitution of India also guarantees the equality of rights of men and women. However, in the sphere of women's human rights in India, there exists a wide gulf between theory and practice. Indian society is a male dominated society where men are always assumed to be superior to society. The women in India very often have to face discrimination, injustice and dishonour. Though women in India have been given more rights as compared to men, even then the condition of women in India is miserable. The constitution not only grants equality to women but also adopt measures of positive power of women human rights in India. Like Rights to equality, Rights to education, Rights to live with dignity, Rights to liberty, Rights to politics, Rights to property, Rights to equal opportunity for employment, Rights to livelihood, Rights to get equal wages for equal work, Rights to protection from gender discrimination, Rights to protection from inhuman treatment, Rights to protection of health, Rights to social protection in the eventuality of retirement, old age and sickness, Rights to free choice of profession and Rights to privacy in terms of personal life, family, residence, correspondence.

Women's safeguard:

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental rights and Fundamental duties. The Constitution not only grants equality to women but also empowers the state to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women for safeguard, like Article 14, 15, 15(3), 16, 39(a), 39(c), 39(d) and Article 42 of the Constitution are of specific importance in this regard (*CEDAW, 1993*).

Women's share in society:

Women are poorly represented in the ranks of power, policy, land ownership and decision making. Women are not just behind in the political and managerial equality. This is in spite of the fact that women are found in large numbers in low-level positions of public administration, political parties and trade unions. Once the men reach adulthood, their roles do not change much except through seniority, but women's role changes from decade to decade in shifting patterns of production and reproduction. Female roles are seen as reproductive and domestic in supports of the male breadwinners of the family and this practice has conditioned women to accept a subservient role.

Women and Agriculture:

In view of the critical role of women in the agriculture and allied sectors, as producers, concentrated efforts will be made to ensure that benefits of training, extension and various programmes will reach them in proportion to their numbers. The programmes for training women in soil conservation, social forestry, dairy development and other occupations allied to agriculture like horticulture, livestock including small animal husbandry, poultry and fisheries will be expanded to benefit women workers in the agriculture sector (*Ojha, N.N, 2008*). Women are the backbone of agricultural workforce in the country. All the world women are the engine of agricultural workforce; but worldwide her hard work has mostly been remained unpaid (*DARE/ICAR Annual Report, 2003-4*). Women play a vital role in advancing agricultural development and food security (*FAO, 2011*). They participate in many aspects of rural life – in paid employment, trade and marketing, as well as many unpaid activities, such as tending animals, collecting water and wood for fuel, and caring for family members. Women also manage household consumption and food preparation (*Doss, Cheryl, Caren Grown, & Carmen Diana Deere, 2008*) Agriculture is the back

bone of many developing countries. Women account for more than half of the work force by participating in different activities, either directly or indirectly. The gender division of labour varies from one society and culture to another, and within each culture external circumstances influence the level of activity (Nigist, 2004). Agriculture is an engine of economic growth and provides the basis for most livelihoods in developing countries (World Bank, 2007). Women are the unavoidable part of any development programmes whether it is for developed or developing country (Raksha, J. C, 2016). Women play a central role in the agriculture economy (Raksha, J. C, 2016). Women constitute half of the agricultural labour force in low-income countries (FAO, 2011). Women's role is of multi-dimensional in nature agricultural fields need sowing, transplanting, weeding, irrigation, fertilizer application, plant protection, harvesting, winnowing, storing etc. In domestic field; her responsibility encompasses Cooks, Child rearing, water collection, fuel wood gathering, household maintenance etc and last allied activity fields- cattle management, fodder collection, milking.

Women's Health:

Special attention will be given to the needs of women in the provision of safe drinking water, toilet facilities and sanitation. A holistic approach women's health which includes both nutrition and health service will be adopted and special attention will be given to the needs of women. The reduction of infant mortality and maternal mortality, which are sensitive indicators of human development, is a priority concern. Women should have access to comprehensive, affordable and quality health care. Women's health problem as highly visible in rural area by endemic, infectious, and communicable diseases such as Malaria, TB, Jaundice, Chickenpox, snake bite and water borne diseases as well as hypertension and cardiovascular diseases. In view of the high risk of malnutrition and disease that women face at all the critical stage such as infancy,

childhood, adolescent and reproductive phases. We focussed attention would be paid to meeting the nutritional needs of women at all stage of the life cycle (Ojha.N.N, 2008).

Women and Economy:

Women's contribution in any economy is inevitable. Their roles vary region to region, work to work, country to country and within region also. The important role played by women in economy, electronics, information technology, food processing, agro-industry and textiles has been crucial to the development of these sectors. Women's perspectives will be included in designing and implementing micro-economic and social policies by institutionalizing their participation in such processes. Their contribution to socio-economic development as producers and workers will be recognised in the formal and informal sector.

Women Entrepreneurship in India:

With the changing socio-cultural environment and increasing educational opportunities, women became aware of their potential to develop entrepreneurial skills. In rural areas, female participation in employment outside the home is in fact viewed as slightly inappropriate, subtly wrong and definitely dangerous to chastity and womanly virtue (Dube & Palriwala, 1990). Indian society has witnessed some highly successful women entrepreneurs, such as Shehnaz Hussain (a world-renowned Indian herbal beautician who owns a chain of beauty parlors), Ekta Kapoor (a celebrated Indian film and television productions) and Kiran Mazumdar (a leading Indian businesswoman and founder of the biotechnology firm Biocon). However, the majority of female entrepreneurs, especially in the middle and lower middle classes as well as in rural areas, still find it difficult to simultaneously meet their entrepreneurial and familial demands so as to attain a proper work-life balance (Mathew & Panchanatham, 2009a). According to Nelasco (2008), even though the leadership

potential of women is very high, this potential is hidden by social, economic and political constraints. Today we find Indian women engaged in different types of traditional (e.g., garment-making, beauty care, fashion design) as well as non-traditional (e.g., founding financial institutions, educational institutions, entertainment companies) entrepreneurial activities. In other addition to their challenging entrepreneurial work, many of these women must also perform several roles in their families (see figure below). These roles include being a spouse, caretaker and parent; managing daily household chores; and providing services to the community and society. Women also must take care of their own health and other personal activities, which are often neglected because of role overload as well as time limitations.

Although motherhood is a social construct whose meaning changes over time, in most contemporary societies motherhood is conceptualized as a gendered division of labor that assigns women primary responsibility for child rearing (Glenn, 1994; Finkler, 1994). A woman's mission in life is to engage fully in domesticity to sustain the family (Tiano & Ladino, 1999; Vaughn, 1979). Women's identity is often defined in reference to their spouses, children, and family, forsaking their personal selves. A patriarchal ideology that frowns upon working outside the familial sphere reinforces female subordination to men and dedication to domestic affairs (Segura, 1991). Gender roles are in transition in Mexico. As a recent family planning survey (CONAPO, 1998) indicates, while over a third of men and women believe that personal plans for women should put household and family first, only a small proportion believe that household tasks and childrearing are exclusively female duties. Women's primary duties must be those of the home and the family, those of wife and mother; but that the full performance of these duties may be helped and not hindered if she also possesses a sense of duty to the public and the power and desire to perform this

duty. In those western states it is a real pleasure to meet women, thoroughly womanly women, who do every duty that any women can do and who also are not only in fact but in theory on a level of full equality with men. There should be equality of rights and duties but not identity of function; and with the men, as with the women, the primary duties are those related to the home and the family. The first duty of the average citizen is to be a good father or mother, husband or wife.

Conclusion:

Secularism, in philosophy, is the belief that one's own live can be best lived, and the universe best understood, with little or no reference to a god or gods or other supernatural concepts. Now-a-days, terms like 'right to education', 'right to information' and 'right to protest peacefully' are being used quite frequently. According to *Smt. Indira Gandhi* former prime minister of India "people tend to forget their duties but remember their Rights". Many a time, you also feel that you have certain rights. Rights and duties go together, my right is others duty, and my rights is my duty also. Right should be used for social good duty toward the state. Right without duties are mere power. Duty is an obligation to do or not to do something for the sake of other. Simultaneously, you may have been told by someone, may be your teacher, that you have certain duties towards other individuals, society, nation or the humanity. But do you think that every human being enjoys the rights or everyone performs the duties. But everyone will agree that there are certain rights that must be enjoyed by individuals. Particularly, in a democratic country like ours country, there are rights that must be guaranteed to every citizen. Similarly there are certain duties that must be performed by democratic citizens. Which is why, the Constitution of India guarantees some rights to its citizens. They are known as Fundamental Rights. Besides, the Indian Constitution also enlists certain core duties that every citizen is expected to perform.

These are known as Fundamental Duties. So, give respect to your mother, establish high-level corporate leadership for gender equality and promote education, training and professional development for women.

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RESEARCH ESSAY ON HUMAN RIGHTS & DUTIES

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Abstract:

The important of Rights are as much as important as duty. The paper is a simple essay discusses on the Rights of human and duties as well .Fight for human rights not only for us but for the whole of humanity. It's our duty to build better future citizens who would not only help in the development of the society, country but the whole world. That is possible when students are taught poems of Keki and Walt in schools and Universities so that they can learn about their rights and duties towards the nation as well as the whole world and thus help in making this world a better place to live in.

Keywords: *Duties, Human, Rights, Violence*

After a lot of troubles we have attained our independence .We should try to preserve that freedom. We have to fight for our freedom or else we would loose it. Earlier man was busy in wars and fighting with each other for no reasons. One race wanted to dominate the other races. They wanted to be superior to the others. They wanted to exploit the others and therefore they followed the way of cruelty and violence. They went for wars made others slaves and killed each other. There was rivers of blood flowing .It was due to greed for power , domination and trying to show themselves supreme. Than after two world wars there was enough of loss to humanity. People suffered a lot and therefore United Nation came into being for maintaining peace and giving rights to human beings where their voices could be heard and if they felt that there rights are being violated or they are not getting justice they could be heard at United Nations and it takes care of the people from isolated and underdeveloped countries where their voices can be heard and they won't be neglected .Constitution has been laid in such a manner that everyone gets equal rights. They all become privileged .Rights are even for the

downtrodden and vulnerable part of society like children and women as the rights of the people who can't speak can always be taken away and can be violated . They are exploited and abused therefore they should be empowered and uplifted they should be given equal rights. Human rights are meant for all so that everyone lives with joy and they get equal rights, equal opportunities like education, employment, religion, movement, right against harassment and abuse etc. As all human being have their own worth, they have value; they can help in the development of the country. They can serve the society too. Government does so much for the people than it is the duty of the country to follow the set norms rules and regulation laid down by the country etc and help in it' s development and upliftment .Give back to the society what it has received. Human rights education teaches us the practice of various values to be adhered .At the same time the knowledge of it is transferred from individuals accountable for their acts either at personal level or at societal level. The knowledge of human rights would also lead us to establish an orderly , peaceful and friendly society both

Research Essay on Human Rights & Duties

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at the national sphere and at an International sphere .

DUTIES:

Obligation mostly arises from ethical and moral duties which are very essential in life .Duties arise out of responsibilities which are legal and binding .Positive duties means to do good for the society. Perfect duties means that we should be perfect , sincere and honest whatever we are doing at every moment. While discharging the duty .Duty is a value that dictates individual to perform their moral and legal responsibilities at all times for the promotion of good to society and to individuals .Rights and duties can't be separated from each other .Adhering to duties is nothing but becoming dutiful and doing welfare of the society and state. It is the duty of every person to vote, to obey laws ,to work as far as his capacities permit for the benefit of the society.

RIGHTS

Every person has the right to be recognized as an individual having equal rights like others, obligations towards the society and having the rights to civil rights . Everyone in this society needs to be social and feel part of the society to promote exercise and protect his legitimate interest of political , economic ,religious ,social ,cultural professional , labour union and other nature. Every person has the right to work under proper condition and to follow his work of interest or do the job one is interested in under suitable conditions and should be therefore provided conducive environment.

HUMAN & RIGHTS

In this world everyone has right to live with freedom, with equality, without any discrimination on the basis of caste ,creed, religion, region or color .Along with the freedom people have responsibility towards country. They have to serve country and contribute to the society. Many facilities

government provide to the people so therefore it's peoples responsibility to contribute something in return back to the society what they have received. Everyone has right to live with dignity, respect and is independent to move anywhere in the country, adopt any religion, freedom to education, profession or do any job according to their interest and caliber. Everyone should be treated equally, all religions should be respected and their ideologies too. Our country is one of the biggest democracies in this world and there is Unity in Diversity and therefore it is our duty to preserve the peace and harmony and try improving it more so that we can leave a better country for upcoming future citizens and be an ideal for this whole world.

HUMAN RIGHTS AND DUTIES

It is something that a person must or should do as an obligation. It is a term that conveys a sense of commitment to someone or something .Every human being has the right to life, liberty and security of his people and family. All persons are equal before the law and have the same rights and duties without any distinction as gender, language, creed or other factor. Every person has the right to freely profess a religion, faith and manifest and practice it both in private and in public. Every person have the right to freedom of investigation ,opinion and expression dissemination ideas by any medium whatsoever .Everyone have the right to protection of law against abusive attach upon his honor his reputation and his private family life. Every person have the right to establish a family the basic element of society .All woman during pregnancy and nursing period and all the children have the right to special protection ,care and aid. Every person have the right to an education should be based on principles of liberty , morality and human solidarity .Every person have the right to participate in the cultural life of the community enjoy that arts and to participate in the benefits that result from intellectual progress ,especially scientific discoveries.

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OBJECTIVE-HUMAN RIGHTS AND DUTIES

- Remove hunger and poverty from society.
- Primary education for all.
- Eradicate gender Discrimination
- Women should be empowered.
- Child mortality to be reduced
- Improve health: Combat HIV/AIDS malaria and other diseases.
- Help in saving Environment-Sustainable development .
- Global partnership for development.

UNITY IN DIVERSITY: AIM

People of different socio-economical, politico-cultural perspective have to look like a single family.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT-DUTY OF CITIZENS

Man should do the welfare of the whole of society in such a manner which helps in the sustainable development. The development of the country and the world should be done in such a manner so that no one is harmed. Taking the environment into consideration - the trees, pollution, global warming and keeping a check on all those elements that are harmful for the humanity. Make judicious use of resources because the nature has sufficient to meet every ones needs but not every ones greed as said by Mahatma Gandhi.

PEACE AND HARMONY

Peace and harmony is most important thing conducting all auspicious festival and ritual in the best possible manner so that no one's peace is disturbed .A country which is terror free .Where there are no riots taking place. Where every ones has securities and that they can move in public places safely even at night where no one's independence is debarred. Where everyone can speak their mind. Where there is love ,kindness, care

,compassion ,universal brotherhood .For that everyone has to work hard to bring a revolution not only in this country but also in this whole world and one has to take responsibility of themselves but also try taking care of others whether they are neighbors , animals etc. One has to really work hard to eradicate poverty, fight against any kind of violence and injustice whether towards downtrodden, women, and children. Any kind of child abuse or women abuse should be stopped .If any ones sees or hears about any kind of violence taking place in the society or surroundings they should go to stop it or at least inform the police or take some action.

GREAT LEADERS -FOUGHT FOR OTHERS RIGHTS

There were many people who had fought for others rights like Mahatma Gandhi, Swami Vivekananda, and Rabindranath Tagore etc. They fought for the downtrodden and vulnerable part of society in non-violent manner. They fought for women's rights. Women started coming out of their houses. Swami Vivekananda said that when a man is educated than an individual is educated and when a woman is educated the whole family is educated. Rabindranath Tagore had opened the Viswa Bharti so that people from around the world can avail opportunity of education boys and girls both without any discrimination on the basis of caste ,creed or religion so it was a great Endeavour on their behalf and Mahatma Gandhi has proved his worth so many a times whether on Leo Tolstoy farm that all have the right to be educated and fight for their and others rights and thus serve humanity. Nelson Mandela also fought for the rights of others and Abraham Linclon laid his life and sacrificed his life for Americans .

CONTROL OVER GREED

There should be comradeship we should not only fight for own rights but for the rights of others too. We should not only enjoy our own rights but give rights to others too. We

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should be at peace that would only come when we have inner peace. We are satisfied with our inner self. We have no greed for lust, power and we have control over our anger. History is the proof that these elements have always created havoc on human life created disaster etc and lead to war and as a consequence we never attained anything out of that. It was only loss to humanity.

SPECIAL CHILDREN-PART OF SOCIETY

Even the special children should know about their rights so that they can participate in all events they can serve country in their own manner as everyone on this earth has potential to move the mountains. They should be made to realize their fullest potentials as they don't know what they can do. Human welfare should be every ones motto, goal and aim.

UNITED NATION-PRESERVING PEACE

United Nation is built so that it can preserve peace in this world and thus like this justice is there if someone feels that there rights are being violated they have every right to go to the high court or the supreme court where there rights are heard and it should be every ones duty on their part to give others their right and not debar anyone of their right that situation should not arise that people have to go the court and fight for the justice.

STUDENTS SHOULD BE EDUCATED

Students should be taught about human rights and duties .They should be taught how to follow the rules set by the government. How they can be useful to the society .They know about their rights because they would learn about their rights they can fight for their rights and then they can even participate and volunteer in different activities which would definitely help in the

development of the country as well as the whole world.

AUDIO VISUAL AIDS

Children should be taught about human rights and duties through audio-visual aids, projectors, T.V, tape-recorder, C.D, D.V.D, excursion, role –play, drama, debate, elocution, movies, songs etc. They should be asked to read more about human rights and duties. Their feelings for serving the nation should be aroused.

Students should be taught about the great ideals and about their great deeds how they sacrificed their life for the nation. They should be asked to spend time with the old age people in the old age home along with the orphans in the orphanage. They should be asked to serve them.

MORAL EDUCATION-TEACHING MORAL DUTIES

They should be taught moral values through value education at least once in a week or everyday so that students can learn more about values which is the need of the hour as when they learn about moral values would be aroused than only they can develop and serve the country as well as citizens. They should be asked to clean up the surroundings. They should be asked to help even at home .Help their mother while cooking, siblings while studying, helping in cleaning utensils , broom the floor ,buying things from the market as in this manner they would know their worth. They would be able to give back to the society what they have received. They would be able to become better citizens of the country. They would learn to become dutiful and responsible citizens .They should be asked to respect other culture, religion, language, others views, ideas ,learn how to be tolerable too because an eye for an eye will make the whole world blind so therefore they should be taught to shun the habit of taking revenge .

TEACHING THROUGH KEKI AND WALT'S POEMS

It's very important that they are taught about Keki. N. Daruwalla and Walt Whitman so that they can help in improving the society by studying the real present scenario as described by Keki. N. Daruwalla and the brotherhood message, democratic world as depicted by Walt Whitman.

As the poetries of Keki .N.Daruwalla depicts the corruption , exploitation, partition taking place and its consequences ,buying and selling of people. He is only telling about the scenes which he saw taking place like riots and how it arose in front of his eyes. What were the causes and its effects but he doesn't try to bring any solution to it or try to improve the situation. He doesn't want to change the people because you can't change anyone but you can only change yourself .He makes us aware that how things are existing in society like old traditional rituals which is fake.

WALT WHITMAN – DEMOCRATIC WORLD

Walt Whitman on the other hand talks about brotherhood, democratic world, this world and human beings have one religion that is of humanity. We should not go for war and shed each others blood when we all are brothers and are part of the same God. We have come from one origin that is God. Why to discriminate on the basis of caste, colour and religion. Why selling of black people by white people is taking place ?Why they is so much difference on the basis of status taking place? Why corruption is taking place in society ,people are being exploited and prostitution is taking place in society ?He says that after an individual is dead his soul would always remain alive. After a person is buried they would transform into grass. Thus he is sending a message to improve the society. He is not only talking about the living people but also dead people life after death. He says that all are going to have one end so why not live as one in this world.

Solutions to Keki's problem can be found in Walt Whitman's poems. Through kindness, care, compassion ,universal brotherhood many problems can be understood and solved to a very great extent. Love truth and non-violence were the weapons of Mahatma Gandhi who fought for the whole nations rights. Therefore when you fights for any ones or your own rights you have to see and take into consideration that no one elses rights are violated or no one is hurt. When you have the right to speak doesn't mean that you speak in a manner so that other sentiments are hurt etc. Therefore students should also be taught about every religion and their books because all religions talk about welfare of humanity and welfare of all.

WALT'S MESSAGE-UNIVERSAL BROTHERHOOD

He says that there should be universal brotherhood ,love, care and sharing. He says that why one is thirsty of another person's blood. He says that all are one in this world there is no difference between a leaf and a human being. As a man dies than they are born again as a leaf. There is no death of a soul but only bodies they change. Like people change clothes after death like that after death they only change bodies but soul stays alive in this universe. Nothing goes away from this universe. He says that all are buried in the same soil whether a king or a layman after death than there is no difference between anyone .So, why there is so much of differentiation before death if there would have been same peace before death then this world would have become a HEAVEN or better place to live in. Therefore this thing message of peace should be given to the students in primary schools only. These poems of Walt Whitman should be included in value education or English literature of school going students from primary level till University level as through this only they would learn to be disciplined follow rules and regulations etc. They would be able to respect elders. They would be able to obey them. They would not fight on small issues. They would learn not to violate

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others rights not to differentiate on the basis of caste, creed or religion or on the basis of economic status and no human trafficking would take place. No selling of human beings, no prostitution ,no exploitation many evils would be wiped off all would become one in this world.

KEKI'S POEMS

Keki through his poems tries to express what he sees and observes .He sees the riots taking place ,corruption, exploitation taking place he expresses selling and buying of people. Hardships faced by the people during India Pakistan's partition .How people died during the partition and havoc it created .He talks about that in some place there is dearth and scarcity of water and mosquitoes are biting but still people are staying at such places for job to earn money. Farmers they marry and they leave their wives to feed themselves and their children all on their own therefore they indulge in prostitution. Man is cruel and enjoys giving pain to others as they are worst than animals .What develops in them this animal instinct Whereas Walt says that war should stop, peace should only prevail animals are more peaceful than human beings as they don't run after power and they can also learn a great deal from the animals too. Whereas Keki says that human beings are greedy, cruel, dominating since past many ages and centuries .For ex: Asoka, Mughals, Alexander etc. Wars have taken place and greed for domination, power etc have taken place and would always remain the same always. If one wants changes in the society they the can be made because even an individual can make a difference. Teachers by teaching students through value education, poems, stories, dramas ,role – play, skets, operahs ,movies, audio-visual aids ,field excursions, visit to historical sites should spread and inculcate the values amongst students. Teach about human rights and duties. Make students responsible citizens who are dutiful and who know their rights. Even culture teaches a lot. Children learn more by seeing and observing what others are following and doing they learn

more through actions. Through literature one can come to know about the life style, thoughts ,feelings ,emotions of human beings etc . Way of dressing , food, culture too at particular point of time .So therefore through poems also message of human rights, duties, fraternity, universal brotherhood, peace, love and non-violence can be spread . Literature depicts the culture of the society. When poems are taught like of Keki and Walt we can say that solution to Keki's problems can be found in Walt Whitman's poems. Keki talks about harsh reality of life he don't want to change anything or whereas Walt says that stop this war ,selling of people ,exploitation(corruption and prostitution) ,differentiation on the basis of caste, creed, region, colour, economic status or religion.

MESSAGE OF LOVE , PEACE AND NON-VIOLENCE

Asoka had spread the message of peace by drilling the message deeply on the pillars. It was dug deep in the rock so that generations could read his message of spreading the message of love, peace ,truth and non-violence. He wanted to tell by drilling the message of peace deeply on the rock that how deeply he was hurt about it the Kalinga war which took place .He said that he was hurt so deeply he wanted to come close to common people but couldn't repent now as it was too late millions had already died and there was a river of blood flowing between him and the common people. He can't cross this river of blood and it's too difficult but he can come close to common masses only by serving humanity .For that Asoka had send his messengers to different islands for spreading his message of peace and non-violence and followed BUDDHA'S PATH, the middle path and now he is known to the world .So therefore we should learn from the mistakes of great people that one should learn about values and conquer themselves first.

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TEACHER'S DUTY

Teacher's should shoulder this great responsibility to help students become peaceful and non-violent. As we can see them they are open to mass media to a very extent. Even in society they are watching violence while watching television, video game etc. They are seeing violence at home which is cause of concern which has a negative impact on students and violence as well as abuse which needs to be eradicated from the society which can be done by the teachers only by teaching students about values and non-violence.

CONCLUSION

Students should be taught about peace they should be taught about values ,respect and value others ,other religion ,their fooding, culture etc. Through dramas, cultural program dances of various cultures children should be able to spread the message of peace ,unity and human values through dramas also they should be able to teach the moral values ,human rights and duties ,stop all kinds of war spread message of humanity .Students should be taught to donate blood ,voluntarily participate in First Aid and Red Cross during war. They should be asked to write essays ,participate in role play ,debate, elocution, dramas etc and thus help in making people aware about their rights and duties and also how to preserve peace and humanity which is the need of the hour.

Students should be taught about human rights and about Walt and Keki's poems so that they can be acquainted about harsh realities of life struggles of human beings, difficulties faced by them, learn about history and cultures, what were the consequences of human beings ,foolish acts likes wars and to learn a lesson from them and not to repeat the same ,develop love for humanity ,be emphatic develop aesthetic sense and learn ethics too. Learn to love and respect human beings and give everyone their rights and accomplish all the duties. Develop the feeling of equality , unity of this

whole world and that no one is inferior or isolated. Everyone gets equal opportunity to do job of their interest ,equal salary, there should be no discrimination on the basis of caste ,creed, region, religion, colour ,economic status, and gender whether for job, salary or education. All human beings have the same rights and duties as both are equally are important we should respect our rights and put into practice our duties. All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights students should be taught this as they are the future citizens and the development of the country as well as the world depends upon them. They can definitely help in preserving peace and humanity not only for this generation but even for the generations to come by using resources judiciously and respecting all creations created by God in this Universe thus transforming this world into a heaven.

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The European Union and China's Human Rights Perspective: It's Impact on Tibet Issue

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Abstract:

One of the most difficult and delicate areas in the EU-China relations is the question of human rights because of their differentiated and contested concepts of human rights and normative values. As we all know, the Chinese government does not believe in the universal value of human rights because of its authoritarian set. The People's Republic of China is deprived of necessary fundamental rights including freedom of expression, association, assembly, and religion. Exercise of any such activity perceived as a threat to their party (World Report 2015: China, Human Rights Watch). It is very evident in the case of Tibet as well that a series of self-immolations happened in Tibet since 2009 protesting against Chinese government's repressive and militarised rule in Tibet. On the other hand, European Union (EU) a noble peace laureate and normative actor in the international relations has been promoting human rights around the world as a universal value. Human rights, democracy and rule of law are core values of the EU. The EU has been very vigorous in case of massive human rights violation in Tibet as well. EU has expressed their support and concern for human rights situation in Tibet on many different occasions, by using various mechanism and instruments to improve human rights condition. Unfortunately gross violations of human rights remain a continuing fixture of the situation in Tibet, in spite of the EU's effort. However China argues that owing to their differences in historical background, social system, and cultural tradition, China can only start from its reality and explore a road with its characteristics. As a result, EU's pressure on China has substantially declined. Firstly because of Chinese obstinate behaviour towards international human rights norms and secondly, with the rising economic power of China, it is clearer that human rights issues get compromised over economic interest. In a way, Tibet issue is losing its voice and support. Therefore, the paper is intended to look into the ineffectiveness and the irony of EU in promoting HR in Tibet in the light of Chinese government's failure to comply with international standard HR norms.

Keywords: *Europe, China, International Relation, Human Rights.*

The relations between the European Union (EU) and Peoples' Republic of China (PRC) have been characterised by phases of agreement and cooperation as well as disagreement and tension. Both the EU and China gained important positions in international relations over the last decades, especially in economic terms (Algieri, 2002). Their economic growth is seen as both attractive and forward looking in the international system.

The year 2015 marks the 40th anniversary of the EU-China established diplomatic relations in May 1975. Their relationship based on Trade and Economic Cooperation Agreement 1985 has matured and transformed from Comprehensive Partnership to a Comprehensive Strategic Partnership in October 2003 (Li, 2009). Currently, China is one of the most important strategic partners of the EU among the Asian states. In 2004, China became the EU's second largest European trading partner behind the United States, in both exports and imports (Algieri, 2002), while the EU is China's largest trading partner, ahead of U.S and Japan. It was an unexpected yet significant relationship which Shambaugh describes as "one of the most important yet least appreciated development in the world affairs in recent years" (Shambaugh, 2004, p. 243).

One of the most difficult and delicate areas in the EU-China relations has been the question of human rights because of their differentiated and contested concepts of human rights and normative values. The Chinese government does not believe in the universal definition of human rights which is equal and inalienable to all the human beings. China argues that 'right' to individual is not inherent rather bestowed by the state (Goldman, 2002). The citizens of China is deprived of fundamental rights, such as freedom of expression, association, assembly, and political rights. Exercise of any such activity by its citizens is often perceived as a threat to the stability of their

party (World Report 2015: Human Rights Watch). The Tibetans are also denied the same fundamental rights. Therefore, over 100 Tibetans resorted to self-immolation since 2009. They do not have other legitimate options to protest against the PRC's continued repressive and militarised rule in Tibet. On the other hand, the EU a noble peace laureate and normative actor in the international relations arena has been promoting human rights around the world as a universal value. Human rights, democracy, and the rule of law are some of the core values of the EU. The EU has been vigorously bringing up the issues of massive human rights violation in Tibet with China. Further, the EU expressed their concern for human rights situation in Tibet on several occasions at different platforms. Unfortunately, the EU's attempts to make situations better in Tibet did not yield desirable results because gross violations of human rights remain a continuing fixture of the situation in Tibet. To defend their position and counter criticisms of human rights violations by the world community, the PRC persistently uses the theory of cultural relativism. They use this theory to state that all the rights articulated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights are not consistent with (or cannot be fully incorporated into) the Asian culture (Le, 2012). The EU's pressure on China to comply with the human rights norms fail to bring about necessary changes in the behaviors of the PRC's leadership, specifically towards the human rights of their citizens and that of the Tibetan people.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to examine the ineffectiveness of the EU's human rights policies particularly in making the Chinese authorities comply with the universal human rights rules in their country.

To cooperate into the proposed arguments, it will explore different views of EU and China on the issue of human rights and its implications on Tibet issue. It would also discuss the current situation of human rights

in China taking the case study of Tibet and EU's position on Chinese human rights violation. It would further analyse the shift in the ways in which the EU formulates human rights policy towards China and how it has changed over time. Lastly, it intends to understand to what extent economic and strategic interests have undermined the EU's promotion of human rights in its dealing with China. It will further question the effectiveness of EU in promoting human rights in China.

Human Rights Situation in China

After the 1989 Tiananmen Square protest, the PRC's human right abuse reached the forefront of international concern (Le, 2012), China faced unprecedented international pressure but responded by challenging certain aspects of the human rights system. Major issues of concern like repression of freedom of speech, freedom of religion, freedom from discrimination, freedom from torture, and other political rights continue to be a matter of concern (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights 2009; Human Rights Council Resolution 5/1: People's Republic of China). Those major concerns continue to exist because they have never been meaningfully addressed. The PRC in an attempt to clutch at straws has been using the theory of cultural relativism to defend their positions on human rights conditions in their country.

Human rights as a discourse did not exist in China before the 1970s.¹ The dominant political discourse back then was the discourse on class struggle² (Chen 2005: 162). Post Mao's era,

¹other terms like citizen rights, people's rights were used frequently though

²China believes class struggle is needed because there are some anti-socialist elements in society. So long as class enemies still exist, they should be suppressed and no rights should be extended to class enemies.

Chinese government has played a proactive role in the process of human rights discourse transformation. Since 1978, a discourse on human rights has slightly changed, as class struggle was no longer the main focus. The Party's policy shifted their focused on economic construction and reforming economic policies with a view to encourage foreign direct investment in their country. But there is less improvement in the political rights of the masses because Chinese foreign policy on human rights and most other subjects is overwhelming realist (Ming; Forsythe 2001: 1098), and thus devoted to a narrow national party interest.

With the coming of President Xi Jinping to power, it was assumed the decade-long repressive political policy of his predecessors would come to an end. Unfortunately his government chose to tighten control over key pillars of civil society and continues to curb fundamental rights (Human Rights Watch, World Report 2015: 155). According to Radio Free Asia 2015 Report, Chinese Right Group said, "China's human rights situation is currently the worst that has been seen in a quarter-century". Civil Rights and Livelihood Watch Founder Liu Feiyue told RFA that "the stability maintenance regime is getting stricter and stricter; you could say it's getting more and more brutal, more and more inhumane" (RFA 2015.³ In case of Tibet as well, human rights situation has worsened. The discontent of Chinese rule over Tibet is shown in the form of series of self-immolations and protest at mining operations.

EU and Human Rights

The institution of human rights assumes prestigious position in the international arena. This position is because of the evolution of human rights as one of the central arms in the machinery of the United

³Reported by Xin Lin for RFA's Mandarin Service, Translated and Written in English by LuisettaMudie.

Nations (UN; Heyns&Viljoen, 2001). The EU believes that the “promotion and protection of human rights around the world is a legitimate concern of the international community” (UN Guidelines for Minorities, p. 1).

The EU is committed to the promotion of normative values and human rights in China in an active, sustained and constructive way.⁴ Democracy and human rights are typically placed at the core of its both foreign and internal politics (Kozma 2009: 603). There are two important factors for contemplating such issues as a strategic importance. First, EU is known as a normative power in international relations and human rights have become a value of honour for EU. It provided an idea of the creation of China as a safe place for EU's future investment which has been the topmost priority in the EU's agenda towards China. Successful democratisation and opening up of the Chinese market to the world has been another most important objective of EU (Sajdak 2013, p. 24).

EU's Position on Human Rights in Tibet

Human rights advocates argue that the political situation in Tibet makes is different from the rest of China. The implementation of Chinese authoritarian policies in Tibet has led to a cultural and physical genocide in contrast to the administration of its policies in the rest of China (Adams 1998). The Human Rights Watch, World Report 2014 has provided human rights report in Tibet which read as follows:

“The Chinese government systematically suppresses political, cultural, religious and socio-economic rights in Tibet in the name of combating what it sees as the separatist sentiment. Arbitrary arrest and imprisonment remain common, and torture and ill-treatment in detention is endemic. A politicised judiciary precludes fair trials

⁴Eeas.europa.com

overly tasked with suppressing separatism”. (p. 328)

“Police systematically suppress any unauthorised gathering. On July 6, 2014, police opened fire in Nyitso, Dawu prefecture on a crowd that had gathered in the countryside to celebrate the Dalai Lama's birthday. Several people were injured. The government censored news of the event” (Human Rights Watch, World Report 2014, p. 328).

EU accepts that China has one of the worst human rights records of any major country in the world. Certainly, the degree of protection for individual human rights is significantly lower than one is entitled to. In response to the China's violation of human rights in Tibet and its repressive rule in Tibet, the EU has established different institutions, provided guidelines on human rights, initiated human rights dialogue, and laid down human rights policies towards China. The EU's major condemnation of China's human rights situation occurred following the Tiananmen Square massacre in 1989 by imposing arms embargo sanction on China. In 1995, EU has initiated ‘the EU-China Dialogue on Human Rights’⁵ which provided a new channel of communication between them regarding all issues of concern (ECOM 2001). The European Parliament⁶ has expressed support for Tibet on several occasions by using various tools and instruments at its disposal such as written or oral questions and statements, the annual report on human rights, hearings on China and/or Tibet by the Sub-committee on Human Rights or by the Foreign Affairs

⁵ The EU-China human rights dialogue held twice a year and it discusses all the necessary issues such as civil, political freedoms, ethnic minorities' rights, death penalty and fair-trial, etc

⁶ European Parliament is an important actor on human rights.

Committee, meetings of the [Tibet Intergrup](#).⁷The European Parliament reiterated its call on the Council to appoint an EU Special Representative for Tibet and felt the need for the rights of China's minority communities to be put on the agenda for future rounds of EU-China human rights dialogue (European Parliament 2011). The EU delegation urged China to address the root causes of unrest and foster dialogue with and between the different ethnic groups, especially in Tibet and Xinjiang (CTA 2015; UNHRC Session).

After formalising human rights dialogue with China, EU prioritised Chinese ratification of the "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)" along with the "Covenant of 1996 on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)" and the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" as a part of solution for their relationship (Sautenet, 2007). The Chinese ratification of the ICCPR was considered as an important issue to be discussed in the EU-China dialogue (Murgo, 2007). The Chinese government has been declining to ratify the covenant despite continuous pressure on them (Lee, 2007: 449). There is less probability to improve political rights even if China agrees to ratify ICCPR. The irony is that in spite of ratification of the Convention Against Torture over 16 years ago, "amendments in legislation, and growing public awareness of the issue, torture remains a major problem for China" (Lee, 2007, p. 451). Torture and execution of its people still continue to take place behind the bar. China requires improving their value and behaviour substantially in terms of both the law and practice.

Effectiveness of EU's human rights policy towards China

Despite the EU's strategy of 'constructive engagement' based on cooperation and

⁷<http://www.tibetpolicy.eu/european-parliament-resolutions-2000-2012>

dialogue over human rights issues in China, the latter's human rights record has worsened over time (Panebianco, 2006). In response to such concerns, the European Commission's 2001 China Strategy outlined more concrete actions that could strengthen the human rights dialogue, stating that dialogue was "an acceptable option only if progress achieved on the ground" and therefore it needed to be more 'result-oriented' (European Commission, 2001: 11). The steps to strengthen dialogues and make it more result-oriented were outlined in the European Commission papers published in 2003 and 2006 (European Commission, 2006: 4). No alternative policies on human rights were suggested despite an adverse report on China's human rights. In fact, mention of the term human rights declined from fifty in the 2003 European Commission Paper to just nine in 2006 (Mattlin, 2005).

The EU-China dialogue on human rights situation in China has been occurring between low-level diplomats of the two parties. The outcomes of such dialogues have never resulted in serious action plans to improve human rights situation in Tibet. Therefore, the dialogues between the two parties just remained dialogues and did not make any difference at all in the lives of its citizens.

The leadership of the PRC never fails to challenge any criticisms levelled against them. The EU's effort to improve human rights situations in Tibet is considered as an intrusion in its domestic affairs and opposed as an unfavourable act. It also alleges that the EU's stance on Tibet is more as a Western ploy to irritate China and seek some diplomatic leverage, particularly to gain economic concessions from China. Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesman Qin Gang retorted to some such human rights criticism by saying that "Tibetan issues and human rights are purely China's domestic affairs, and China would not allow any outside interference" (Qin, Gang 2008). The EU's diplomatic relationship with the Dalai Lama

resulted in cancellation of a few high-level meetings and refusal to attend “dialogues on environmental issues and human rights” (Li, 2009). For example, China cancelled EU-China summit when former President Sarkozy met with the Dalai Lama. In the subsequent months, China started demanding France to support China's position on the Tibet matter. Chinese responded to French failure to protect the Olympic torch in 2008 by boycotting the France's supermarket Carrefour. Towards the end of 2008, Chinese common people were not happy with the Europeans attitude towards them. Therefore, many boycotted tourism to France. Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao deliberately did not visit France during his official tour to EU in 2009 (Li, 2009). Chinese students also boycotted the London Metropolitan University because it offered an honorary degree to the Dalai Lama. Similarly, Prime Minister Cameron's meeting with the Dalai Lama in May 2012 and the British's human rights report on China, resulted in the cancellation of British-Chinese dialogue. Further, the prime minister's planned trip to Beijing during the same year was banned (VOA, Asia: 2014). Such brazen acts of the Chinese leadership forced many European governments to avoid direct contact with the Dalai Lama and raise Tibet issue. Some other member states faced Chinese demands for apologies for holding earlier meetings, and some of them took U-turn.

An exponential growth of the Chinese economy made them a prominent player in the arena of international relations because many countries developed mutually beneficial business relationships with them. As a result, the international community, including the EU became softer and less critical of the bad behaviours of Chinese. The EU's pressure on the Chinese to comply with the universal human rights regulations has diluted so much that the pressure today is not any closer to the one Chinese received when inhuman acts that they perpetrated on peaceful demonstrators in Tiananmen Square. One of the major reasons why the

EU's current pressure on the Chinese leadership pales in comparison to the pressures of yesteryears as alluded to earlier was the EU's economic interest that has been intricately linked with the Chinese economy. In the current EU-China economic relationship, the Chinese appears to have the upper hand. Therefore, the EU adopts overly cautious approach in bringing up the human rights issues with Chinese leadership. Based on their current strength, the Chinese leaders expects their EU counterparts to be respectful of their positions on Tibet, Xinjiang, and Taiwan by remaining silence on those sensitive issues.

The EU member states are divided among themselves and compete for their own national interest. For instance, France and some other member states began to push the EU to stop tabling resolutions to condemn “China's human rights record at the annual meeting of the UN Commission on Human Rights”. It was solely motivated by their increased commercial interest in China (Casarini, 2006; Balducci, 2010). Meanwhile, Nordic countries such as Denmark and the Netherlands were under significant pressure from their public to link foreign policy to human rights. They can afford to do so because they had no important economic links to China. Nordic countries were against France leading the group in this regard because they wanted to continue tabling the critical resolutions (Balducci, 2010). This resulted in a division between EU member-states, culminating in the 1997 UNHCR meeting when a critical resolution towards China co-sponsored by Denmark, UK and the Netherland was voted against by France and four other member-states (Casarini, 2006). After this discussion, it was agreed that no more critical resolutions would be tabled at following UNHCR meetings (Baker, 2002). Thereafter, EU members have failed to promote human rights because their positions have been weakened by the economic interests of their respective countries. As a result, China

appreciates the way the EU's treats the human rights issues.

The only effective measure adopted by the EU to condemn Chinese human rights violations was the arms embargo; that was imposed on China after the incidents of Tiananmen in 1989 (Kinzelbach&Katrin, 2014; Richardson, 2014). However, the condemnatory measures has moved from public to more diplomatic and closed door meetings (Human Rights Forum 2010). The EU member states considered lifting the arms embargo in 2004 when the Chinese pressure grew (Huang, 2011). However, Chinese failed to remove arms embargo because of the US interference in the debate of lifting off the arms embargo and divergence in the EU's decision-making.

The European Council on Foreign Relations published an assessment report on April 17, 2009, on the status of the EU-China relations, and the Council has expressed that "EU should no longer exercise any restraint on China's human rights and citizenship issues" Additionally, the report stated that "EU should combine issues such as protecting freedom of religion and promoting so-called political reconciliation with the Chinese central government to reinforce, and not weaken the EU's stance on the so-called issue of human rights in China". It was stated further that "European leaders and its parliament should issue a statement refusing to accept Beijing's "imposition of restrictions" on their meetings with some political and religious figures, including the Dalai Lama" (Zugui 2009). However, the Union's human rights diplomacy has, in general, remained limited to issuing condemnatory declarations. Declaratory diplomacy on the humanright is not futile as the Union's repeated denunciations of violations have helped to make clear that human rights abuses are no longer acceptable to the international community. Violators of human rights face symbolic and repeated condemnation, force them to pay a modest political cost and undermine their legitimacy

(Donnelly 1998). However, EU's full potential on human rights issues is far from being realised.

Conclusion

From this study, it became evident that the EU's human right policy towards China is ineffective particularly in the case of Tibet. This year is the 40th anniversary of the EU and China relationship. Their relationship assumes greater significance in the backdrop of ongoing economic crisis. For example, EU sought Chinese help to bail out Greece from the Eurozone crisis. China's growing economic clout over the EU is making the EU more subservient. Premier Li Keqiang, in Europe on a day when financial markets took fright that Greece might leave the euro, said China and the world wanted to see Athens remain in the currency area and that China would continue to buy euro zone debt (BRUSSELS, June 29, 2015).⁸ Moreover, China in response to their domestic economy challenges, President Xi Jinping initiated the "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) on March 2015, to increase their focus on "improving diplomacy with neighbouring states and more strategic use of economic as part of China's overall diplomatic toolkit" (Kennedy& Parker, 2015).⁹ The EU's participation in the OBOR project, would definitely benefit from Chinese investment to update and reinforce Europe own infrastructure (Yan, 2015).

Thereby, human rights became an object of national foreign policy. The EU has a contradicting human rights policy towards China. They talk about promoting human

⁸ <http://www.reuters.com/article/2015/06/29/eu-china-idUSL5N0ZF2N020150629>>

⁹ Kennedy, Scott and Parker, D.A (2015), "Building China's One Belt, One Road", Center for Strategic and International Studies, Online, Accessed on 3rd Oct 2015, [URL]: <http://csis.org/publication/building-chinas-one-belt-one-road>

rights, but at the same time consider lifting the arms embargo sanctioned on China. The EU's economic interests weaken their position on human rights vis-à-vis violation of human rights in China. The gulf between the European Union's human rights rhetoric and reality evidently has not yet been bridged. As a result, Economic competition and conflicting national interest continue to restrict Europe's foreign policy on a human rights issue to mere declarations rather than actions. China believes Tibet as one of their core interest. Therefore, they do not accept and tolerate any intervention, be it in the name of human

As a result of overly cautious approach of the EU, it is likely that some sensitive issues for the rights, from outside forces. In such case, EU becomes helpless and makes them to believe that Chinese human rights situation will improve with its economic development. Hence, in this globalised world, EU's human rights approach towards China has been subordinated to the economic and trade interest. Principally, EU's foreign policy was set out to maintain its own norms and values in engaging with global actors in international politics but economic interest is taking over their norms. Chinese authorities, including human rights and Tibet, will be further marginalized. Further, pressure is likely to grow for the EU authorities to refrain from interfering in China's issues. The PRC might apply economic pressure on the EU respect Chinese human rights policies and lift the arms embargo.

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HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS AGAINST LGBT PEOPLE IN INDIA: NEED FOR INTROSPECTION

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Abstract:

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights promises a world in which everyone is born free and equal in dignity and rights. Yet, it is a shallow promise for many hailing from LGBT (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender) community who are confronted with hatred, violence and intolerance on daily basis. Society terms anything which is different as 'not normal'. Hence, condemning a person for being who they are is completely unjustified and so is society's power to exercise unnecessary control over an individual's gender or sexuality. The United Nations have documented widespread physical, sexual and psychological violence against LGBT people including murder, assault, kidnapping, rape, sexual violence as well as torture and ill-treatment. Deeply-embedded homophobic and transphobic attitudes combined with lack of legal protection against discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity, expose many LGBT people to glaring violations of their human rights. The invisibility and silence which surrounds the existence of sexual minorities lives produces its own order of oppression, making them feel that they are the only ones 'cursed' with such desires in the world. Adding to their woes is Section 377 of the Indian penal Code which criminalises Homosexuality. Due to the law, societal values and mainstream culture being unfavourable towards sexual minorities, very few can afford to be open about their 'illicit' sexual orientations. LGBT people don't need sympathy but understanding, acceptance and dignity just as all other human beings. A space for LGBT people is needed to look at these specific issues not from a hetero-normative perspective or with pre-conceived binary notions. Media being the "watchdog" of society is responsible for highlighting human rights violations, and bringing them to the notice of the National Human Rights Council. This research paper examines the human rights violations suffered by LGBT people in India. The paper lists several areas of concern that need to be addressed energetically and calls for synergy of efforts between government, media and the society. This paper urged the media to play a more active and significant role in promoting human rights culture across all spheres of society.

Keywords: *Discrimination, Human Rights, LGBT, Media, Section 377*

Human Rights are in fact, basic necessities in the form of certain claims of an individual recognized by the society and the state, without which one cannot live as human being. Every individual has, therefore, certain rights which are inherent in all individuals irrespective of their caste, creed, colour, religion, sex, language, ideology and nationality. These rights are also referred to as basic rights, birth rights, fundamental rights, natural rights or inherent rights. Such rights originate with the birth of individual and are essential for human happiness and progress. They are necessary for the material and moral upliftment of the human race.

Robertson defined Human Rights as,

“those basic rights to which every man, woman and child living on this earth is entitled by virtue of his being born as a human being”. In his opinion, these rights lay down the standards of general application for all human beings in all times and in all circumstances, thus setting the norms for advancement of the human society. Thus human rights can generally be defined as those rights which are inherent in our nature without which we cannot live as human beings.

The world conference on Human Rights held in 1993 in Vienna stated in the declaration that all Human Rights derive from the dignity and worth inherent in the human person, and that the human person is the central subject of human rights and fundamental freedom. D.D. Basu defined Human Rights as those minimum rights which every individual must have against the state or other public authority by virtue of his being a member of human family, irrespective of any other consideration.

The situation of **human rights in India** is a complicated one, as a result of the country's large size and tremendous diversity, its status as a developing country and a sovereign,

secular, democratic republic, and its history as a former colonial territory.

Research Objectives

1. To study the human rights violations suffered by LGBT people in India.
2. To study the issues and problems faced by the LGBT people in India.
3. To examine the role of media, government and civil society in safeguarding and promoting human rights of LGBT people in India.

Research Methodology

The research paper is written on the basis of case study done on the various issues related to LGBT community. For this purpose the coverage of issues related to LGBT community have been studied. To some extent their reasons have also been tried to find out. The research paper is written on the basis of both primary and secondary data. The primary data is collected through interviewing LGBT people in order to understand their issues and concerns. The secondary data is collected from various articles, journals, publications, books and online sources.

Concept of LGBT

LGBT stands for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender. It intends to signify a diversity of sexuality and gender identity and also used to refer to anyone who is non-heterosexual or non cisgender. To recognize this inclusion, letter Q has been added for those who identify as queer or are questioning their sexual as LGBTQ, recorded since 1996. Before the sexual revolution of the 1960s, there was no common non-derogatory vocabulary for non heterosexuality the closest such term, “third gender”, traces back to the 1860s but never gained wide acceptance in the United States. The first widely used term, homosexual, was thought to carry negative connotations and

tended to be replaced by homophile in the 1950s and 1960s, and subsequently gay in the 1970s. As lesbians forged more public identities, the phrase “gay and lesbian” became more common. After the initial euphoria of the Stonewall riots wore off, starting in the late 1970s and the early 1980s, there was a change in perception some gays and lesbians became less accepting of bisexual or transgender people. Each community that is collectively included has struggled to develop its own identity including whether, and how, to align with other gender and sexuality-based communities at times excluding other subgroups; these conflicts continue to this day.

LGBT Rights

LGBT rights refer to lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender rights. Homosexuality² is criminalised in India by interpretations of the ambiguous Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC). The punishment ranges from ten years to lifelong imprisonment. The law has been used to harass HIV/AIDS prevention efforts, as well as sex workers, men who have sex with men and other groups at risk of the disease. Scott Long, director of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Rights Program at Human Rights Watch sent a letter to Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh regarding the arrest of 4 men in 2006 in Lucknow and another 4 in 2001. However, in most areas of India, this law is very rarely enforced.

As argued by some of the organisations, LGBT issues, such as same sex marriage, gay adoption rights and protection from discrimination should be considered human rights. Canadian courts have recognised some rights under Section 15 of the Canadian charter of rights and freedoms. Part of this debate includes a proposed UN declaration on LGBT rights which condemns discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. The People’s Union for Civil Liberties has published two reports of

the rights violations faced by sexual minorities, in particular, transsexuals (hijras and kothis) in India.

Sexual acts “against the order of nature” remain illegal in India, though the government no longer seeks to prosecute adults engaging in private consensual homosexual acts. In current times, the campaign to decriminalize homosexuality has strengthened. Campaigners emphasize both human rights and health issues, particularly the need to disseminate information about HIV/AIDS.

The skewed treatment may have been due to gender bias, considering that the Manusmriti is the same scripture that has stated that the status of woman in the society is the same (or even lower than) that of man’s land, his cattle and other possessions. The Rig Veda, sculptures and vestiges depict sexual acts between women as revelations of a feminine world where sexuality was based on pleasure and fertility.

Homosexuality is generally considered a taboo subject by both Indian civil society and the government. There are 2.5 million male homosexuals in India according to National AIDS Control Organization (NACO) estimation. Public discussion of homosexuality in India has been inhibited by the fact that sexuality in any form is rarely discussed openly. In recent times, however, attitudes towards homosexuality have shifted slightly. We can find more depictions and discussions of homosexuality in the Indian media and Bollywood.

Religion has played a significant role in shaping Indian customs and traditions. Human sexuality possesses various aspects such as biological, physical and emotional. The phenomenon of sexuality is treated differently in different societies. In some societies, it is taken as normal factor and the necessary education regarding it is provided to individuals while in the others, it is taken

as forbidden topic which is not to be discussed openly.

While homosexuality has not been explicitly mentioned in the religious texts, some interpretations have been viewed as condemning homosexuality. There have been different views on the position of homosexuality within India's main religious traditions. There have been arguments that homosexuality was both prevalent and accepted in ancient Hindu society.

There are various organizations which have implicitly came out in support of decriminalizing homosexuality in India which pushed for tolerance and social equality for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender. There is a vibrant gay nightlife in cities such as Mumbai, Hyderabad, and Bangalore, including discos and nightclubs. The reports of harassment of homosexual individuals and gatherings by the police has seen a gradual decline since 2004. The majority of Indians, according to various polls and surveys, still look down upon the LGBT community. However, many social and human rights activists have been working to promote an increased acceptance of homosexuality. Time Out (Delhi) has a dedicated column covering gay events in Delhi every week. Now with the emergence of several LGBT support groups across the nation, the much hidden queer community has increased access to health services and social events.

In 2005, Prince Manavendra² Singh Gohil, who hails from a conservative principality in the Gujarat state, publicly came out as gay. He was quickly anointed by the Indian and the world media as the first openly gay royal. He was disinherited as an immediate reaction by the royal family, though they eventually reconciled. He has appeared on the Oprah Winfrey show, and is currently appearing on BBC3's Undercover Princes.

In 2008, Zoltan Parag, a competitor at the Mr. Gay International contest said that he

was "scared" to return to India fearing discrimination. He said, "Indian media has exposed me so much that now when I call my friends back home, their parents do not let them talk to me".

On June 29, 2008, four Indian cities including Delhi, Bangalore, Kolkata and Puducherry celebrated gay pride parades. These were the first pride parades in Delhi, Bangalore and Puducherry. Around 2000 people turned out in these nationwide parades. Mumbai held its pride march on August 16, 2008, with Bollywood actress Celina Jaitley coming out to join in the festivities.

The Internet has created a prolific gay cyber culture for the South Asian community. Gay dating websites provided an alternative way for meeting people; online communities also offer a safe and convenient environment for meeting gays all around India. Though Bollywood as the Indian film industry is loosely called that has gay and trans characters. They have been initially ridiculed or abused. Though, there are few positive portrayals in Onir's My Brother Nikhil, I AM, 68 Pages by Sridhar Rangayan, Parvati Balagopalan's Rules: Pyaar Ka Superhit Formula, etc but they have been sporadic and not mainstream.

Queer Theory: An Insight

Queer theory³ emerged as gay and lesbian studies, which in turn was the academic wing of the gay rights movement. Literary and cultural studies that focused on sexuality as a key category was an offshoot of a wide ranging social and activist movement through the 1960s and early 1970s. The Stonewall Riots of 1969-provoked when police raided New York's Stonewall Tavern, a popular meeting place for gays-maybe called as the origin of the gay liberation movement. Organizations like Gay Liberation Movement (GLM), Gay Activists Alliance (GAA), AIDS Coalition to Unleash Power (ACT UP) sought legal, medical, social freedom and rights for gays and

lesbians. Queer theory drew upon the experiences of these movements while adding philosophical and critical insights into the nature of the body, the geography of sexuality and the question of sexual identity.

Queer theory today has political affiliations with women's studies, African American cultural criticism and theory and postcolonial studies. The common commitment to centring the marginalized, emancipation for the oppressed and social justice is what brings them together on one platform. It looks at the history of cultural representations of the gay/lesbian as deviant, sick or criminal, while foregrounding sexuality as an important category of critical analysis when dealing with cultural texts. Queer theory moves between literary analysis and activism because it shows how cultural representations contribute to very real material oppression of homosexuals.

Queer Cultural Studies may be defined as "an attempt to redefine identities and carve out a cultural/political space within the dominant heterosexual paradigm, to simply stop being invisible or the "perverted" or "sick" or "other" of heterosexuality" (Nayar 2007:118). Queer theory is, therefore, resolutely *political* in nature because of its concern with structure of power.

Queer theory, is relatively recent (1990s and after). The turn to 'queer' serves particular purposes. 'Queering' is the process of reversing heterosexuality-as-norm. 'Queer' now refers to not only gay/lesbian issues but also includes other practices, identities and communities-all of which have been marginalized in history-such as bisexuality, sado-masochism, the transgendered and the transsexual. Transgendering, transvestitism, drag and camp, and other sexual identities present the multiple nature of identities that cannot be reduced to one category.

Queer theory⁵ looks at:

- The general construction of sexuality in discourses of medicine, law or religion
- Popular representation of the gay or the lesbian
- The public understanding of alternate sexualities
- The 'hidden history' of homosexual writing and representation
- The institutional (religion, family, medicine, law) structures that undergird popular representations of homosexuality
- The link between sexuality-based oppression and other discriminatory forms such as patriarchy and racism
- The geography of sexuality, with specific reference to ghettoization of gays and homosexuals

Queer theory seeks to:

- Destabilize essentializing identities
- Resist heterosexual cultures through the carnival, transgression and parody
- Be co-sexual: men and women are on equal footing. The term queer is now used to mean both gays and lesbians
- Promote the demand and fight for sexual justice as part of social justice
- Use the AIDS crisis to reflect on practices of homosexuality and battle AIDS-driven homophobia

When the United Nations decided to create a set of global goals to end poverty and inequality by 2030, equality groups pushed for the rights and needs of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people to be taken into account. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), was agreed in 2015 and signed onto by 193 governments on the basis that they apply to everyone, everywhere and will '**leave no one behind**'. The SDGs could have gone further by explicitly calling for

LGBT equality. The 'leave no one behind' principle is especially relevant for LGBT people, who have been repeatedly left behind by national and international development initiatives. Discriminatory laws, projects that don't acknowledge their specific needs and negative social attitudes have all combined to hold LGBT people back. The impact of this is felt by LGBT communities in all parts of the world-lower income, worse health, less education, among others. As a result of which, poverty as a whole will never truly be eradicated until this problem is directly addressed.

The Status of Sexual Minorities in India

The lives of human beings are full of complexities, but LGBT people face much more trauma compared to other people. What is necessary is to understand the sentiments of the LGBT community and also to grant them common human rights but the world lowers its eyes and refuses a discussion over the granting of basic human rights to the LGBT community. It is unpleasant to see that such discrimination exists even in the 21st century. Indian law, on the whole, only recognizes the paradigm of the binary genders of male and female. The most important question with respect to the LGBT community is whether LGBT people be discriminated against by other human beings. Merely being different does not give others the authority to ostracize one from society.

As covered in various studies, homosexual orientation is common in almost every culture and every society. However, homophobia¹ is chiefly the product of a Judeo-Christian morality spread to various parts of the world through European colonialism, which exported its laws and its morality into other local contexts. It has to be noted that homosexuality also finds a mention in the various pre-colonial laws. Homosexuality is seen as an offence in *Manusmrithi*, which however can be

expiated. Lesbianism by contrast merits more serious punishment. Islamic *Shariat* law treats homosexual conduct as a serious offence, though it is being argued by some recently formed gay Muslim organizations that Islamic law can be interpreted in a non-homophobic fashion. It was with the enactment of uniform criminal laws in India, in 1860 that there was a uniform prohibition of homosexual behavior.

Though sexual minorities have always existed in India, sometimes in the forms which are culturally accepted (such as the *hijras*) and mostly due to the invisibility and silence, their issues have never been seriously articulated. It is in recent times that the rights of sexual minorities as an issue have been taken seriously in India by various civil society organisations. With the founding of India's first gay magazine *Bombay Dost* in the late 1980's and the starting of a lesbian collective in Delhi called *Sakhi*, lesbian, gay and bisexual issues were first articulated in a public forum. Today there are organizations, helplines, publications/newsletters, health resources, social spaces and drop-in centers in most of the major cities in India like Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Bangalore, Hyderabad, Pune, Chennai, Patna and Lucknow. The support structures provided are painfully inadequate with few or no such organizations for lesbians, bisexuals and hijras. It is more painful to see that many new emerging organizations die out silently while the established ones have been able to reach out to a small section of sexual minority population due to lack of resources, personnel, government support and extreme societal/state discrimination.

LGBT has become a widely accepted designation for sexual minorities. All members of this community are subjected to similar prejudices rooted in beliefs and traditions about sexuality and gender. The LGBT community, as a social minority group, suffers from various forms of social, political, economic and cultural injustice.

The lack of social recognition has an effect on the capacity of the LGBT community to fully access and enjoy their inherent rights as citizens within their territory. They are often exposed to intolerance, discrimination, harassment and the threat of violence owing to their sexual orientation and gender identity, differently from those who identify themselves as heterosexual.

Democracy¹ has played a vital role in identifying the rights of the LGBT community. It is noteworthy that gay rights have progressed fast in those parts of the world where democracy has been most successful, and the gay rights have struggled the most in the places where democracy has faced difficulties in advancing or has not advanced at all. Democracy also facilitates gay rights by making possible a vibrant civil society and allowing freedom of association. The most sensible approach for the LGBT community would be to fortify existing programmes to promote democracy, civil society and the rule of law. It is due to democratization that today lesbian, bisexual, gay, transgender and 'hijra' communities in India are asserting their right to freedom from discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation.

Problems faced by LGBT People

We do not yet live in a world free from homophobia, transphobia, prejudice and discrimination and we live in a world where majority wins and overpower the voices of the minority. In India, we need a space that listens to those who need to be heard. LGBT people are exactly that—a minority within our own homes, families, schools, institutions, communities, work places etc. Adding to their woes is Section 377 of the Indian penal Code which criminalises Homosexuality. Many of these problems leave many among them feeling isolated, afraid, depressed and even suicidal. So a space for LGBT is needed to look at these specific issues not from a hetero-normative perspective or with pre-conceived binary notions. LGBT is in

fact short for LGBTTTQQIIA+? It includes, lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transexual, queer, questioning, intersex, intergender and asexuals. An in-depth understanding of all these terms and the '+' in the end of the acronym gives us the idea how profound sexuality really is. While there is still so much confusion regarding what constitutes gender and what is one's sexuality, media hold primary responsibility in being sensitive, empathetic and rational while dealing with LGBT issues.

Some major problems¹¹ faced by LGBT people across the world are:

- Marginalization and Social Exclusion
- Impact of Family Reactions on LGBT Children: Conflict and Rejection
- Problem of Homelessness
- Problems of Homophobia
- Harassment of LGBT Students in Schools
- Psychological Distress
- Poor Economic Condition and Discrimination in the Workplace
- Drug Addiction of LGBT people
- Barriers to Care
- Challenges facing LGBT elders
- Victims of hate Crimes and Violence
- Problems of Criminalization
- Legal Injustice
- Problems of Terminology

Media are powerful and unavoidable. We are constantly bombarded by media messages. Media messages have subtle influence on society's way of thinking. Portraying of gender stereotypes by media forms society's perception of gender roles. The over-saturation of gender stereotypes in the media accounts for the misrepresentation of gender roles which gets embedded in the human mind and is passed on from generation to generation as an acceptable view. Over the years the representation of LGBT community in Indian media has found itself

under the scanner. Indian media has witnessed a steady display of LGBT characters some for the comic effect and some, however, stayed true to reality and made an effort to treat the subject in a very sensitive and realistic light but unfortunately to a larger extent the Indian media content could not challenge the traditional myths and have failed to break the 'taboo'. It has been observed that these people are often judged in terms of sexual behaviour. The violence on the issues of sex and body is not only sexual violence but it is also a kind of denial of identity and voice in the society. The role of the media in safeguarding and promoting human rights is contained in Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as also in the Indian Constitution.

Case Studies: From Marginalisation to Mainstream

Dhananjay Chauhan

A resident of Uttarakhand, Dhananjay is a trans female and the first transgender student of Panjab University, Chandigarh. She is pursuing her Masters degree in Human Rights and Duties at the Centre for Human Rights, Panjab University. Chauhan's story is interesting but a challenging one, where she discovered her true self at the age of five. She was more interested in playing with girls as a child. As she grew up, attraction to similar sex confused her which led her into a state of depression. This also affected her studies, where she once excelled. She was molested and sexually exploited not only by students but teachers also. After completing her graduation in 1993, she was forcibly pushed by her family into getting married. Having no feelings for the opposite sex, marriage became even more difficult for Chauhan.

As per Chauhan, To save her wife from the society's tantrums of not bearing a child, she convinced herself to get intimate with her. Slowly and gradually her wife understood

Chauhan's predicament and supported her in her fight to change her gender. Chauhan opted for the study of human rights as she feels the transgender community is living in a shell and they don't know about their rights. She had applied for the course in 2015 but got rejected as this community wasn't recognised by the government then. She wishes to work for the welfare of the trans community after the completion of her course. She is also the director of Saksham Trust, which organises Pride Walk each year.

RJ Shanthi Sonu

Transgender Radio Jockey, Shanthi Sonu at CR Radio Active 90.4, a community radio station, initiated by the Jain Group of Institutions in Bengaluru, Karnataka, has suffered stigma in the past as a transgender first, and as a sex worker later. Now, she holds her head up high in a career that gives her happiness.

She is someone who had to face a number of hardships but hadn't given up something called 'hope'. Now in her thirties, Shanthi was earlier known as Shankar for 19 years of her life before she decided to take a stand and change her identity to the one she most closely associated with her soul. She underwent the surgery required to become a woman and yet her fate for a long period of time hadn't changed. Shanthi was a sex-worker for ten long years and after she has started working with Radio Active, the tone, attitude of people around and everything much has changed for good in her life. She was born in a family that had extreme poverty. Her father practically didn't have a job and was alcoholic and her mother was a domestic worker. She liked to draw rangoli in front of her house. Her mother would often tell her that it is a girl's responsibility or chore. Boys shouldn't be drawing rangolis. Instances like these made her feel more feminine. She used to enjoy being in the company of girls. She couldn't pursue her studies further beyond class IX. Transgenders have practically no option in

the country today. They are forced to resort to begging or sex work which is extremely unfortunate.

Talking about the discrimination for transgenders she added, “She always get to listen to voices like ‘hijra’, ‘chakka’ behind her back. Shanthi got emotional when she shared a harrowing experience, an incident that really questioned her on her choice to continue as a sex worker. One night when she was waiting for customers she was gang raped by 7 men in the outskirts of the city, in a forest. She pleaded and begged them to leave her but they just continued with the atrocities. She even requested them to use condoms kept in her bag, but they just didn’t want her to speak anything. They completely abused her soul more than anything. With some alertness, she could manage to escape from there and reached home. But that incident made her feel too vulnerable.

Today, she runs a show which talks on the lives of sex-workers, their issues and journey. She also features cookery shows and other variations on radio. She takes pride in mentioning that the bag which used to carry a pack of condoms today holds a recorder and a mike. Shanthi Sonu is not the first transgender radio jockey, but she has enough confidence and voice to express the faceless and silent voices who are unheard in the crowd.

RJ Priyanka

Ms. Priyanka, a 27-year-old transgender, hosts *Yaaru Ivaru* (who is this person?), every Thursday on CR Radio Active 90.4, a community radio station, initiated by the Jain Group of Institutions in Bengaluru, Karnataka. The programme focuses on the problems of LGBT community. According to her, “Radio has given her an opportunity and a platform to touch the lives of people. Life was a struggle. There were times when her parents would feel ashamed to face their neighbours. But today, they are proud of her achievements. It is important to fight it out”.

Through her programme she discusses the problems face by her community in the area of housing, occupation and education and in the process imparts important life lessons. She is a role model for her community and actively works for the upliftment of her community. But the journey wasn’t easy for Priyanka who was born as Raju. She was mocked and teased by friends in school for her feminine behavior. This prompted her to dropout in Class VIII. In 2000, without her parents’ approval, she went to Mumbai for a sex-change operation. Her life has changed drastically ever since. Priyanka is not interested in talking about her past and the stigma that her community faces. She not only wants to empower her community but also wishes to work for the upliftment of all marginalised communities.

Conclusion

“If liberty and equality, as is thought by some, are chiefly to be found in democracy, they will be best attained when all persons alike share in the government to the utmost”- Aristotle

Aristotle in 350 BC emphasized on the involvement of all people alike in the government. In the 21st century, this paper extends the scope of Aristotle’s teachings and applies it to achieving good governance by emphasizing that the onus of good governance is not vested in the government alone but is facilitated by the participation of all people in their best capacity. Good governance is efficient decision making that proves beneficial for a majority of the people irrespective of their gender. Each being in this Universe is indeed unique and an integral part of nature. It would be wrong to judge and discriminate people who may be different from the stereotype which is again man made. It is high time that we all live and let live others and realize that every individual in this country has equal rights and right to live with dignity and respect irrespective of their gender identity including Gay, Lesbians, transsexuals, transgenders,

hijras etc. It would be unjustified to consider LGBT (people) as offenders merely for having exhibited their natural sexual orientation and gender identity.

Invisibility of statutory laws makes LGBT people susceptible to gender violence and other human rights abuses. India must repeal current discriminatory laws and design equal opportunity legislation. Infact, not only government but also the social activists and general public must come forward to support the LGBT people for their decent and peaceful living. In order to protect their rights, there has to be a change in the present Indian Social Structure where these people are looked down upon. The society must accept LGBT people as part of its structure, only then any kind of law may be successfully implemented in an effective manner to protect their rights.

With the advancement in media and communication technology people are getting to notice the presence of LGBT community. Indian media should make efforts to sensitize people and break the stereotypes associated with this community and represent them in a more mature way so that they are socially accepted by the society. Various Ngo's are working for the rights of the transgender people across different states in India. The LGBT people have formed groups to organize protests for their human rights. Unless the basic demands of the LGBT community are met, unless the ostracising acts are checked and controlled and unless the welfare programmes reach out to all the people belonging to the community, inclusion of the LGBT community cannot be achieved completely.

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PUBLIC RELATIONS: A PATH TOWARDS INCLUSIVE GROWTH

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Abstract:

The concept of Inclusive Growth emphasizes on the equal growth and development of all, giving equal opportunity to everyone to grow in such a manner that no one is exploited and the benefits of prosperity is shared equally amongst everybody. In the present digital era of media expansion, media has emerged as a very significant platform for dissemination of messages and sharing of thoughts and opinions, enabling the masses to be enlightened and empowered and also awakened about the meaning and relevance of “Inclusive Growth”.

Public Relations professionals serve a major purpose acting as communication professionals, interacting with diverse publics, creating an ideal environment of two-way communication and acting as watchdogs protecting the interests of just not the concerned organization but also of the publics in an equal manner thus taking care of their welfare and well-being. In the present scenario of Participatory Corporate Culture, Public Relations (PR) has emerged as one of the most important tool for the achievement of the goal of Inclusive Growth.

The paper tries to uncover the role of PR in the Inclusive Growth of the nation by acting as bridges of communication and mutual understanding. The study also focuses on how the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) can be an effective means for the growth and development of the underprivileged and poor sections of the society either in the field of health or education or livelihood, thus bringing them at par with the masses. To make the study primary data based, it makes a detail Case Study of an NGO working for the upliftment of poor children and explores by employing Interview Method as to how its CSR Activities are contributing significantly towards the enlightenment of the deprived ones leading towards the Inclusive Growth of all.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Empowered, Inclusive Growth, Public Relations, Underprivileged, Upliftment*

“Bahujan Hitaya, Bahujan Sukhaya” or “Sabka Saath-Sabka Vikas” are golden words emphasizing on one underlying fact that a nation’s true development is always based on the development of all, irrespective of region, religion, class, caste, age or gender. India is a land known for its unity in diversity, having people of different culture, caste or creed residing together strongly interwoven into a spirit of unity and fraternity.

The time is such that there is a growing realization that if India wants to carve a strong image of itself in the global landscape, the concept of Inclusive Growth is the need of the hour. A nation in order to survive in the long run and to achieve the goal of sustainability, requires the all round development of the country with equal emphasis being given to the growth and prosperity of all. According to Diane Richler,

"Inclusion is not a strategy to help people fit into the systems and structure which exist in our societies; it is about transforming those systems and structures to make it better for everyone. Inclusion is about creating a better world for everyone."

The real essence of Indian society has always been togetherness and the concept of Inclusive Growth revolves around the same principle emphasizing on the creation of such a society which is based on the ideology of equal growth of all, giving equal opportunity to all to grow and express their opinion as well as equal responsibility of all towards the development of the nation in such a manner where no one is exploited and no one benefits at the cost of the other.

Media has always been one of the strongest driving factor behind every positive change taking place in the society. It has always been a strong vehicle for transforming the lives of mankind, playing the role of facilitator of development, disseminators of

information, and an agent of change. In such circumstances, we can expect the media to play an equally responsible role in the attainment of the goal of Inclusive Growth of the nation. All kinds of media, whether print or audio or audio-visual can act as strong tools for dissemination of messages which not only informs us about our surroundings but at the same time they change our perception, attitudes and priorities. Media has highly developed both in terms of number and content and in such scenario various forms of media ranging from newspapers to Web 2.0, all have provided a platform to the masses to voice their opinion and share their thoughts through open discourse and dialogue and to raise mass concern for issues like hunger, unemployment and insecurity, human rights and gender issues and above all the latest concept of Inclusive Growth. Media has emerged as a strong medium for creating awareness about Inclusive growth of the society and thus motivating each individual to fight for his interests and needs leading to empowerment of the masses.

In the keynote address delivered at a seminar on 'Communication for Inclusive Growth', organised by the Chandigarh Chapter of Public Relations Council of India (PRCI), Vipin Pubby, Resident Editor of The Indian Express, underlining the role of media as a force multiplier in creating awareness and informing the general public said, "No country can progress if only a section of population is doing well. All sections of the society should reap the benefit of progress and development. Communication plays a big role in bringing all people together."

The concept of Inclusive Growth does not just imply the inclusive growth of the Indian society giving equal representation and equal opportunity for development to all but it also means the inclusive growth of all stakeholders of an organization in an equal manner, where the cooperation of each one of them is important for the fulfillment of the

corporate mission as each stakeholder group is important with its own set of skills and expertise and its only the feeling of “We” which can help an organization to stand strong in the present ever changing and dynamic business environment.

ROLE OF PUBLIC RELATIONS IN THE ATTAINMENT OF INCLUSIVE GROWTH

With the ever increasing impact of Globalization, Economic Reforms and Liberalization, a new Participatory Corporate Culture has emerged which supports people’s inclusive growth and development and the need for securing an active participation of the people in all key decision making processes of the organization, leading to Value Co-Creation. Informed and Involved Citizenry is the need of the hour and forms a major aspect of a sound Corporate Governance Practice. Public Relations Professionals being communication managers and experts can play an instrumental role by using all latest communication strategies and tools in the direction of disseminating timely, accurate and balanced information to publics and at the same time receiving their feedback on various aspects of functioning of the organization to secure their active involvement in its functioning.

It has been rightly said that Public Relations act as the strongest bridge of communication between an organization and its concerned stakeholders. They are the people behind creating a strong Corporate Identity by employing various credible and consistent channels of communication resulting in the creation of a good Corporate Image amongst the public as desired by the organization. Public Relations Managers besides acting as Analysts, Advisor, Advocate and Antennae for the management of the organization also serve as watchdogs representing the needs and demands of the concerned publics. They are the sole person responsible for thinking in the direction of growth and development

of just not the organization but also of all the stakeholders in an equal manner.

Since times immemorial PR has always been used as the strongest device to reach out to the people, to influence public opinion and to build credible relations, thus uniting the masses into one, aptly executing the ideology of “One Nation-One Voice”. Mahatma Gandhi was always called as the best PR person because of his exemplary skills of winning the hearts of the masses by his ideologies which highly inspired them and united them into one strong nationalist force against the British Government. Thus it would not be wrong to say that his PR strategies were to a great extent aimed at achieving the goal of “One Nation-One Voice”. As rightly said by Dyer Samuel Load in Public Relations Quarterly (2007) that, “An organization has actually no choice whether to “have” public relations. All organizations are communicating with all audiences that are of importance to them. The decision is not whether to have PR, but whether these relations will be handled in a planned, organized manner, or allowed to be accidental, haphazard and possibly inconsistent”. The definition clearly establishes a fact that if a group or an organization wants to win public trust and support, PR is the sole communication function which acts as a very credible information source as well for the masses thus securing mutual understanding and cooperation leading to the building of bridges of trust.

The fact cannot be denied that whenever the question of creating bridges of understanding, cooperation and trust in an organization comes to the mind, the constructive and indispensable role of Public Relations (PR) professionals cannot be denied. In today’s fiercely competitive business market, dawn of new information age and media explosion, building equal strategic alliances with the partners of an organization and generating stakeholder satisfaction has become the need of the hour

and the only experienced and extremely professional personnels who can contribute significantly in the direction of building mutually beneficial ties with the public and who impartially thinks about the welfare of all publics are the PR Practitioners.

Speaking on the concept of inclusive growth Mr. Narendra Modi while addressing the 60th birth anniversary of spiritual leader Mata Amritanandamayi in Kollam said that, “The concept of inclusive growth is not new for India. This has been the message given by our sages since ages. Recalling that ancient Indian sages had given messages like, “Loka Samathsa Sukhino Bhavanthi (let the whole world be happy) ” and taught rulers to conduct affairs of the state with this concept. Further commenting on the occasion, Mr. Modi said, “ I firmly believe that if we stick to these ideals , India could march forward and become a super power”. The underlying principle of Mr. Modi’s philosophy of Inclusive Growth centers around the fact that people should be actively involved to serve the people and all projects undertaken should revolve around a Participatory Work Culture and through it the development of society at large.

Whether it is Mr. Modi’s concept of “Sabka Saath- Sabka Vikas” or his flagship Campaign of “Make in India”, we find an universal call in each one of them towards the attainment of the goal of building relations with all sections of the masses, thus leading towards the achievement of “One Nation one Voice”. An in depth analysis of Modi’s campaigns reveal a major fact that all of them are brilliant PR exercises in the direction of striking the mental chords of the people and uniting them to work for the achievement of the universal vision of “ One Nation One Voice”.

THE PRESENT ERA

Gone are the days where an organization just used to be concerned about the commercial benefits of the proprietor. It had a single-

minded approach of just framing such policies which benefit the owner. The present times is dominated by the principle of Corporate Citizenship, which includes a wide array of concepts in its domain like Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Sustainability, Performance Measurement, Return on Social Investment, Inclusive Growth, all pointing out towards the changing dimensions of the roles and responsibilities of a Public Relations Manager in the present times as most of these areas come under the jurisdiction of the PR professionals and they are solely responsible for framing PR strategies and action plans to achieve these goals. Ever since these concepts have become associated with the principles of Corporate Governance, the concept of “Sabka Saath Sabka Vikas” envisioned by our honourable Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi has become an integral part of the functions of Public Relations Professionals.

Today, with distrust of the corporate world at an all-time high, corporate credibility is an over-riding factor. Whether they like it or not, companies today are at the mercy of public constituencies. That means there is growing recognition of the need to foster a good reputation by developing positive relationships with various publics.

Quite literally, public relations is managing relations with various publics, a role that grows in importance as reputation becomes ever more critical to business success. Companies can restore trust in a number of ways, many involving traditional PR strategies, such as:

- Using integrity and fairness as criteria for all business decisions;
- Maintaining an emphasis on quality of products or services;
- Openly sharing truthful information with all publics;
- Actively seeking input from publics and being responsive to concerns;

- Renewing a commitment to local communities; and
- Creating forums to encourage dialogue with constituencies.

The bottom line is that companies must make it a priority to value the needs of all publics, and to forge good relationships with them. The cornerstone of a good relationship is trust, and trust is based on open and honest communication. Effective PR tells a company's story in a way that is accurate, honest, and easy to understand, helping in the establishment of a reputation which is credible and authentic. A good relationship also requires a willingness to listen, and true Public Relations is a two-way process. PR professionals recognize that to manage relationships, they must understand and respect public concerns and viewpoints. They must also go a step further, to serve as the public's advocate within an organization and such kind of thinking can play a major role in bringing together diverse sections of the community and uniting them strongly into one with the sole objective of working for the growth of the organization and thus the betterment of the nation at large.

Every organization for its smooth functioning requires sound and trustworthy relations with all publics and a strong Corporate Image amongst the masses, besides sound corporate governance principles and programmes. This fact in itself necessitates the day by day increasing demand for Public Relations in almost every organization. Growing significance of public opinion and public participation have made almost all business enterprises no matter whether public or private realize the importance of two-way communication practice, public involvement and the establishment of two-way mutual understanding and relationship building with its internal and external public.

No matter whether its relationship management or cross platform marketing or crisis management or investor relations or

reputation management or creating and enhancing online presence and image shaping or management of Digital Business and Brand building or delivering strategic counseling or advisory services, every such function requires building up a consistent two-way communication system with a strong base of trust and mutual concern between the organization and its partners and PR is the only discipline or department specialized in this area. Every organization, whether it be a for-profit business, not-for-profit organization, educational institution or government agency, depends on people. Their attitudes, attention, understanding and motivation can be critical to the success or failure of the organization and as a result most of the organizations respond to the call of public relations these days which has fuelled its growth as a strategic management function.

But still to achieve the idealistic vision of "One Nation- One Voice", a lot needs to be done.....Public Relations Professionals have to take the plunge and adopt various well planned PR Programmes and measures which would turn out to be instrumental in the direction of securing socio-economic development of the nation at large and more and more of people's equal participation in the development process.

CSR: A MAJOR PR TOOL TOWARDS THE REALIZATION OF THE GOAL OF INCLUSIVE GROWTH

In modern times with tremendous emphasis being given to Corporate Social Responsibility, if there is someone who can make a difference and create an impact on Corporate Policies and Corporate Mission Statement, then they are the Public Relations officials who can strive to bring inclusive growth and an all round human development and overall community welfare by their various innovative projects and campaigns in this direction. 'Sabka Saath- Sabka Vikas' is a philosophy that truly suits the present expectations from a Public Relations

Practitioner as today companies are recognized not just on the basis of their position in the commercial market but the concept of Corporate Citizenship has also assumed a great significance. Corporate Citizenship emphasizes on the fact that the aim for a business organization is to create higher standards of living and quality of life in the communities in which they operate, while still preserving profitability for stakeholders. The concept of Corporate Citizenship revolves around the meaning of CSR given by Archie B. Carroll which means an organization cannot be just economically responsible but social, legal and ethical parameters are also equally significant to analyze the responsibility of an organization towards the community and to call it a good Corporate Citizen.

Needless to say that therefore Public Relations professionals have to expedite their work more effectively in the direction of satisfying all these philanthropic, economic, legal and ethical expectations of society and secure an all round development. Inclusive Growth means people's development, empowerment, employment and participation of all in an equal manner in order to achieve the goal of "Sabka Saath- Sabka Vikas" and thus an all round holistic development of the nation.

Public Relations Professionals have to take the plunge and adopt various well planned PR Programmes and measures which would turn out to be instrumental in the direction of securing socio-economic development of the nation at large and people's participation in the development process. The multi-dimensional functions which comes under the jurisdiction of a Public Relations Manager needs to be expanded beyond the boundaries of just securing a competitive edge and a good image for an organization. The concept of Inclusive Growth and the role of Public Relations Managers in it means that the time has come for them to step out of their routine affairs of just handling all communication and publication functions of

their organizations. The need is for Public Relations Managers to take an initiative and plan out various constructive PR measures which would be like stepping stones in the direction of creating a more informed and a more developed society.

Public Relations Managers being experienced professionals in the field of creating and preserving cordial goodwill relations between an organization and its stakeholders, can be the best persons to think about their welfare too at large and create a perfect "win-win" situation for both the organization and its publics. The present trend says that it is just not the responsibility of government to take care of development of the nation but the efforts should be made by every person in this direction and equal opportunities should be granted to all to showcase their skills and knowledge and to contribute in the field of all round development. Sustainable growth which is demanded by today's public also requires inclusive growth. As rightly said by the OECD Secretary General, "Tackling inequalities in incomes, health outcomes, education and well-being, requires breaking down the barriers to inclusive growth and reaching new frontiers in policymaking and implementation. Everyone should be able to realize their potential and to share the benefits of growth and increased prosperity."

When we talk of in terms of Inclusive Growth, the concept of CSR cannot be neglected. The very principle of strategic CSR speaks about the overall development of the society on all fronts and the legal, economic, ethical and philanthropic responsibility of an organization towards its stakeholders. Presently, when the Indian Government has made Inclusive Growth a key element of their policy clearly stating that, "Achieving a growth process in which people in different walks in life feel that they too benefit significantly from the process." (Ahluwalia, 2007), CSR can serve a major purpose by aiming at the development of the

nation too by satisfying the varying needs of the deprived, exploited and helpless people creating good community relations along with the profit maximization of the company.

Ashok Chauhan, MD & CEO, BSE Ltd, said that “The Indian corporate are changing from not interested in doing social responsibility activities to active CSR involvement. The modern India demands corporate to not only be responsible towards its stakeholders but also towards customers, employees and to the country.”

The theory of inclusive growth which speaks about the growth and development of everyone in the same manner, somewhere having a pro poor approach striving to seek the participation of all in the development and prosperity of all. In this direction Indian companies can play a major role by initiating various innovative programmes and projects in the field of health, employment, livelihood and education through their different CSR efforts conducted on a routine basis, thus contributing significantly in the socio-economic development of the nation and paving the path towards the inclusive growth of the country.

According to Dr. Nanjunda (2015), “It is found that CSR has much bigger implications for development of any country. It reduces dependency on the government for social expenditure and helps for speedy inclusive growth.” Ever since the government has made it mandatory for the companies to spend 2% of their profit behind CSR activities, the concept has become an indispensable element behind securing the equitable development of all as it encompasses the persistent efforts of corporations towards securing the economic and social development of communities in which they operate, thus helping in the development of the society in many ways and leading towards the achievement of the goal of Inclusive Growth”. Strategic CSR has motivated the companies to introduce all such programmes and projects which are

meant for the betterment of the needy people of the society, no matter whether its offering services towards the socio-economic growth of the poor and underprivileged ones or it is in terms of providing vocational training to the deprived enabling them to earn their livelihood or starting a literacy project or contributing towards rural development through various innovative programmes. Corporate Social Responsibility is a concept that integrates a company's social concerns with their business operations. As rightly said by Dr. Vastradmath, N., “The corporate sector has a vital role to play in ensuring that the private investment flows in these rural areas that have been left out of the development process till date and work for sustainable development of rural areas in general.”

Highlighting the significance of CSR as a major PR Tool behind Inclusive Growth of the nation, S.K. Panda, secretary, ministry of textile said at the “ CSR for Inclusive Growth” conference organized by Governance Now magazine that,

“Corporates should focus on resolving environmental degradation and social exclusion. When we talk about sustainability or sustainable development, we have to focus on environmental degradation, keeping a tab on pollution, carbon emission, global warming.” Panda also remarked that, “ Corporates can't prosper while the society is moving towards failure. India has 1/6th of the of the world's population, but it has only one 1/16th of the world's resources.”

The statement of Panda makes it amply clear that for a nation to prosper and bring an all round development of all and to achieve the goal of sustainability, CSR strategies and policies can be the best means to achieve the objective as Inclusive Growth by its very definition implies an equitable allocation of resources with benefits incurred to every section of the society.” (Bagg, 2011)

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The following were the objectives behind the study:

1. To make an in-depth study about the meaning, implication and relevance of Inclusive Growth
2. To develop an understanding as to how PR professionals can be major agents in the area of inclusive growth by building mutually beneficial ties with the public and impartially thinking about the welfare of all publics.
3. To understand the relation between CSR and Inclusive Growth and how this principle of Corporate Citizenship and Corporate Governance can play a major role in the Inclusive Growth of the nation.
4. To make a detail Case Study of a non government organization (NGO) and to critically study its various CSR efforts in the direction of realization of the goal of Inclusive Growth which is basically a pro poor concept striving for the equitable distribution of resources and the equal development of all.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the major objective of the study was to develop an understanding about how Public Relations can contribute towards Inclusive Growth by carrying out its chief function of satisfying the needs and taking care of the welfare and well being of all the publics of an organization in an equal manner. In order to frame a better idea on the issue the relation between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Inclusive Growth has been studied.

To make the study more factual, it employs Case Study method to develop a deeper understanding about how CSR related efforts of an organization can help in bringing about the Inclusive Growth of the nation by imparting significant function in the area of health, education, environment and

livelihood. As a part of the Case Study method, it makes a detail study of an NGO which has been rendering highly important service to the poorer sections of the society in the area of health and education as a part of its CSR Activity. Interview was also conducted of the chief managing personnel of the organization along with a senior and experienced volunteer of the NGO to know about how the various CSR projects and programmes of their organization is contributing towards the welfare and well-being of poor children in the area of health and education thus leading towards the Inclusive Growth of all .

CASE STUDY

Dream Girl Foundation is one such step towards helping the needy and underprivileged sections of the society thus serving as a major CSR initiative in the form of empowering the poor and weaker ones. The very motto of the organization, “we are changing thousands of dream into reality” speaks about the mission of the organization which is chiefly empowering the poor children of the society by imparting fundamental and elementary education to them as well granting services in the area of health care.

Dream Girl Foundation is one of the eminent non-profit organization engaged in providing a better future to the underprivileged girls of the society. The organization has been making sincere efforts to reduce the miseries faced by the children in the area of Delhi and Mumbai. Education is the basis of development, thus the organization provides education to the girls in order to enhance their as well as the future of the country. A woman is the creator of this beautiful world and Dream Girl Foundation makes sure that she gets a respectful life.

The NGO works hard to provide better health, education and shelter to the girls with a team of teachers, medical practitioners and other volunteers, who whole heartedly work

for the betterment of deprived girls. The organization also focuses on providing proper medical facilities to the children. The team members leave no stone unturned to prevent exploitation against girl child and to provide for the betterment of impoverished girls.

The organization works with great dedication and sincerity for the overall improvement of girls including education, sanitation, health, income generation, AIDS awareness and other major issues. As a major means to Inclusive Growth, the organization makes the underprivileged girl children capable enough so that they can compete and come at-par with this fast growing community and tries to work hard to provide a better future to the deprived. The organization works as a catalyst and tries to fulfill the basic requirements of life such as food, clothing, shelter, education and health to the needy children. The organization has been very active in making arrangements for proper health treatment of various critical diseases through its financial assistance to ensure that a girl child gets proper education and medical facilities.

The NGO provides assistance in the area of health and education to the poor and deprived ones of the society. Following are the functions carried out in these areas:

Education- Dream Girl Foundation works rigorously to educate every child they come across from the weaker sections of the society and give them an ability to stand on their own feet and contribute towards the economy of the nation. The NGO has organized a number of camps and workshops in various areas to create awareness about the importance of education among the people. The organization also helps the children in monetary terms. Further, it provides stationary to the needy children. The main motive of the NGO is to create awareness about education amongst the marginalised children.

Health- In the Field of Health Care the organization works for providing Health Benefits, conducting awareness programmes, providing free Health services for poor & needy children, taking care of providing financial assistance in case of certain critical ailments, providing nutritious & healthy meals and above all organizing health camps, workshops dealing with health related issues and health plays etc. Through workshops and plays the organization tries to create awareness about health issues, diseases and essential precautions that can be taken in order to stay healthy. At times the organization also demonstrates this through plays and nukkad nataks that further help in creating awareness in the rural areas. A very commendable aspect of the functions of this NGO is that it helps the needy children suffering from major health disorders by bearing the cost of their medical treatments and make the medicines available at cheap rates. The mission and vision of the organization is to raise the medicinal clinical benefits for small and weaker sections.

(Source: Dream Girl Foundation)

FINDINGS OF THE INTERVIEW

To gather more detail information about the mission, objectives and the nature of operations of the NGO and to make the study more fact based, interview was conducted. For this purpose, the chief of the NGO holding the position of the Manager of the organization was interviewed along with an experienced volunteer serving the NGO from a long time.

On being asked about the chief function of the organization, they replied that the NGO works in the direction of providing health and education services to the very poor and underprivileged children of the society, thus acting as significant catalysts of positive change in their lives. They also revealed that the NGO works for children upto the age of 14 yrs and has been actively working in the Delhi, NCR region as well as in Virar(East),

a suburban area in Taluka Vasai, Palghar district of Maharashtra.

The interviewees were also asked as to what was the source of finance behind the running of the organization and the manager replied that it chiefly functions on the basis of funds raised from different projects and programmes as well as donation received from people.

A key area of the case study was to know the organizational structure of the NGO and the key officials behind its operation. The interviewees said that the organization basically runs on the sincere and dedicated efforts of skilled volunteers chosen from all over India. There are 5-6 permanent staff members of the organization headed by the Manager followed by fund raisers, project managers and project teachers. The manager also replied that at present the NGO has almost 1000 registered volunteers and whenever they want to implement a project, an email is sent to all the volunteers explaining the nature of the project and the area of specialization required from the volunteers to be associated with the project. On receiving the email reply of interested volunteers, the organization conducts telephonic interviews of the volunteers finally leading to the selection of the best volunteer ready to deliver his specialized knowledge for the successful execution of the project. The manager also gave a useful piece of information that the organization also advertises on Google Ad world to recruit volunteers for the organization.

The most important part of the case study was to study the contribution of the organization towards empowering the poor and deprived children finally leading to Inclusive Growth. The manager described that the NGO works chiefly in the area of providing health and education services for the poor and needy children up to the age of 14 yrs. As a part of its function, the organization runs non-formal education centres in the backward urban areas of Delhi-

NCR region, Gurgaon and Virar (East) region of Mumbai. Children of slum dwellers and laborers who basically cannot afford to go to private school to receive education are selected for these centres. The volunteers conduct survey and select families who belong to poor economic strata of the society and their children are selected for receiving education at the centres. The manager pointed out that their education centre in Virar (East) region of Maharashtra is located near Jivdani Temple, a very famous tourist destination of suburban Maharashtra. The temple area is surrounded by slum area called Arnapada which is inhabited by laborers who work in the near by areas for their daily livelihood. The area is so undeveloped that there are no private or government schools near by and nor even proper water or sanitation facility in the area. In such conditions, the education centre of Dream Girl Foundation serves a major purpose of making the poor children of the laborers who cannot afford to go to private schools to get at least the basic elementary education. He also expressed that as the area for this centre is very small, hence the centre conducts combined classes. The Virar (East) centre has 30 students and the centre is managed by two persons, namely one teacher and one volunteer. The class timings are different in Delhi and Mumbai region. The classes are run from 10-12 in Delhi-NCR region and from 11-1 p.m. in Virar (East) region of Maharashtra. To achieve the goal of Inclusive Growth of all the sections of the society, the centres play a major role in disseminating knowledge to the poor children where they are taught English, basic Mathematics like tables as well as poetries so that they at least become semi-literate to face the world. Another major fact which was explored as a part of the interview was that the NGO also convinces the parents to enroll their child in the nearby schools for higher education and at times helps some of the studious and intelligent children in getting admission in the nearby schools and also bears the fee for them. The centre not only pays the admission fee but it also provides

the basic requirements of admission like uniform and stationaries to the children who get admission in the schools.

The Virar centre is managed by a well qualified teacher who has been appointed to provide the children with basic education required. The teacher besides teaching the students is also responsible for convincing the parents of the children by visiting the families from door to door and thus enlightening them about the importance of education in life. The interview revealed that the members of the organization feel that their sincere efforts help in getting the basic necessities of the poor children get fulfilled like other kids of the society, thus playing a major role in bringing them at par with other children and helping in the Inclusive Growth of all.

The interviewees were also asked about the functions of Dream Girl Foundation in the area of health. A noticeable exploration of the interview was that the manager reciprocated by revealing that the organization provides financial help to those poor children who are suffering from serious health problems like cancer, heart problems like hole in the heart, tumors etc and their this endeavour has been given the name of Health Project, "Zindagi". He discussed about the fact that volunteers conduct surveys like they visit AIIMS hospital in Delhi or sometimes they get applications from the side of poor parents seeking financial help from the NGO for the treatment of the health problem of their children. The NGO before deciding about whether to provide financial assistance or not , it first conducts a rigorous investigation related with checking the background of the child. The volunteers gather complete information about the financial status of the family of the aggrieved child and then after gathering all facts and information the final decision is taken. The financial help granted from the side of the NGO is mostly in the form of bearing the cost of treatment or surgery of the poor child suffering from

critical health problem. The manager remarked that till now the organization has dealt with almost 10-11 such cases where they have provided financial support to the poor families by paying the cost of operation of the affected child.

Some testimonials of financial help provided by Dream Girl Foundation to the diseased children as a major part of its Health Project named "Zindagi", a CSR effort

8 years old girl Preeti, who is suffering from a very rare disease of developing copper in her lungs. With the help of donors the organization has successfully raised sufficient funds for Preeti and now treatment of Preeti is going on in AIIMS.

Madan Kumar, a 7 month old child who was suffering from cardiac disease of hole in heart and as prescribed by the AIIMS doctor a sum of Rs. 40,000/- excluding approx Rs. 10,000/- on Medicines was needed for his treatment. Dream Girl Foundation has decided to take over the charge to add one more in the list of more fortunate people and within 20 days they were able to submit the required amount to the AIIMS hospital with the help of their donors.

Kashish was suffering from Atrial septal defect formally known as hole in heart. Doctors of AIIMS had estimated a total amount of Rs. 60,000 of whole procedure in which two operations were required. The whole amount of first operation of baby Kashish has been paid by Dream Girl Foundation with the support of their Donors.

Tanvi was suffering from the pain of having a hole in her heart. Within 30 days Dream Girl Foundation had successfully submitted the required amount to AIIMS Hospital and now she has been successfully operated in AIIMS

Rohit was suffering from nerve blockage in his neck. Dream Girl Foundation, has pledged to help Rohit fight his disease to win the battle for his life

(Source: Dream Girl Foundation)

CONCLUSION

Finally to conclude we can say that if India wants to be a super power and secure a place for itself in the global front, Public Relations people have to come in the forefront and take an initiative by introducing various programmes, planning innovative CSR projects and secure the participation of the public in all development projects of the nation. They have to act as perfect liasoning officers between an organization and its public representing their viewpoints, needs and demands in front of each other in such a manner in order to bring about an equitable growth and development of both the two sides, leading to the inclusive growth of all and finally resulting in the development of the nation as a whole.

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GENDER (IN) EQUALITY AND BRUTALITY: A VIEW FROM MEN'S LENSES

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Delegation to the 2nd **International Congress on Human Rights & Duties**
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Abstract:

After the brutal Nirbhaya gang rape witnessed by India, the entire focus was shifted to women's protection. In the process of providing stronger protection to women what we have ignored is the problems faced by men as a consequence of the steps taken for women. This paper is an attempt to look at gender roles from the point of view of a man. While there are serious discussions pertaining to women empowerment (which is necessary, considering the amount of growing atrocities against women), victimisation of men is a topic that is not much discussed in India. Probably, this is due to the 'typical' notion of 'masculinity' prevalent in our society, and the popular filming of men as being physically stronger than women. The research paper starts by discussing the discrimination against men under Indian laws. It will then try to look into the reason for such discrimination besides giving a bird's eye view of the domino-effect of masculinity on both the sexes. The paper also will be analysing the present situation with respect to the given topic by referring to various newspaper articles and available (though scanty) statistics on the same. The discrimination against men would be dealt in detail by the author while distinguishing between gender neutralism and gender protectionism. The views of the Hon'ble Supreme Court has also been cited in places where required. The motto of this paper is to encourage gender neutrality and appeal for the abolition of gender blindness.

During the course of validating and analysing resources that the researcher has relied upon, it has been strongly felt that the ambit of this area of law is underdeveloped, especially in India, and still people abstain from discussing openly on such topics. And therefore, the researcher has found in the course of looking for information that the information is unorganized and scattered. The researcher will be working on the available information through the resources previously categorized to emphasize on the relevant issues pertaining to the topic.

There are essentially two kinds of resources used for the completion of this research paper – Secondary (Articles – Both online and offline, Journals, and Encyclopaedias) and Tertiary resources.

Keywords: *Egalitarianism, Gender Discrimination, Masculinity, Men, Victimisation*

1. HYPOTHESIS

The choice of the topic is clearly indicative of the fact that the researcher feels that the topic is less discussed. Victimisation of men is a rare topic about which people talk. And the researcher is of the opinion that there are a lot of instances where men are discriminated when compared to men. The loopholes in the law, and the legislations aimed to protect women, as Art. 15 (3) empowers the State to make 'special provisions' for women¹, of the Indian Constitution are misused by women. This however, will prove to be detrimental for the society. And there is no reason for not treating the men, equally at par with women. The aim of the country should be to ensure that there is no law which renders the men to be discriminated on the grounds of their gender.

INTRODUCTION-

Every other day, when we open the newspaper, we can see at least one news on the atrocities against women. Since time immemorial, women have been subjected to infinite forms of discrimination and have always been dominated, by the patriarchal society peopled in India. Women, have succumbed to these atrocities for a long time, but after the feminist movements, their grievances have been brought to the forefront. Although we cannot say that the crimes against women have decreased, but we can assure that everyone is aware of the discrimination, atrocities and violence faced by them. But when it comes to men, most of us are not aware of their grievances and problems. This paper addresses some of the problems faced by men.

I am quite sure that some of the readers of this article might completely disagree with me, or accuse me of being an anti-feminist,

¹ Article 15(3), Constitution of India, 1950

Art.15 (3):“(3) Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from making any special provision for women and children.”

or someone advocating men's movements, or a misogynist. However, I would like to clarify here that I am neither anti-feminist, nor misogynist. This contention would be proved towards the end of this paper when I talk about equal rights for all. I do not believe in subjugating the rights of men while advancing the cause of women, or vice versa. Rather, feminism, according to the researcher means women having equal rights as men, not rights super ceding men. People who advocate greater rights for women when compared to rights of men are called feminazis. They try to achieve superiority over men. The researcher, simply, firmly believes in providing equal treatment to both the genders. As a feminist myself, I understand, and to some extent share, the reluctance in discrimination faced by men, but also believe that addressing the problems faced by men is equally significant. This is not, by the least, an attempt to malign the character of a woman.

Although the stigma of discrimination and violence is towards women, men also fall prey to discrimination and other forms of atrocities faced by men. It is very often that people openly talk about men's rights. Rights of women and duties of men are frequently talked about. What about rights of men and responsibility of women? Where is the forum in which we talk about it? We do not have an answer to this question.

2. NEED FOR MEN'S RIGHT IN PATRIARCHAL SOCIETY-

The first question that the researcher faced during the course of research was that “*Is there really a need for men's law in a patriarchal society like India?*” This portion of the project would be dealing with the answers to the above question. This will be done by referring to real life case studies.

Similar to the discrimination against women

, victimisation of men is not anything new which has suddenly propped up during these days. It existed from a long time, but the discrimination against women was more prevalent, and that is why though discrimination against men is prevalent, yet, it is invisible. Also, men abstain from publicly saying that they have been tortured by women.

It has existed from old ages; even in the *Mahabharata* it can be found. King Shantanu wanted to marry Ganga. She told him that she would marry him on one condition, that he must never ask her where she is from or the true nature of her origin. He must also never question her on any of her actions - good or bad. He must stand by her on all counts, and the day he acts against any of these conditions, she shall leave him. When the first child was born, Ganga took to the child to the Ganges and cast it into river – immediately drowning and killing the new born. Shantanu saw it but he could not stop himself from asking Ganga any question mindful of the promise he made to her. As the years passed, Ganga gave birth to 6 more children and to each one, she did the same.

An argument to this by feminists would be that the Indian mythologies contain more instances to show the male-domination in our society from the age of Ramayana and Mahabharata. For example, the Kauravas publicly undressing Draupadi, Ram's *agnipariksha* to Sita and Ravana abducting Sita suggest women were portrayed as lustful fancies of powerful men. But, the grievances of women are being addressed these days and the perpetrators being punished. Media has played a rather major role in bringing all the female discrimination to the forefront. However, media has failed to bring the discrimination of men in a proper way. We can find such articles only in regional newspapers, never is it seen in the national newspapers.

Also, in the present time, there has been an increase in the atrocities suffered by men. Men are sexually exploited, false rape and

dowry cases are filed against them, harassed and always threatened. The only option that they are left with is divorce. Even when they seek divorce, they are charged with false molestation cases.

3. GENDER BLINDNESS

This section of the paper has been titled as gender blindness because it will be trying to establish a clear distinction between gender biased, gender blind and gender neutral laws in India. Given the increasing number of heinous crimes everyday against women and their vulnerability, special protection of women is necessary and we cannot deny that. Art. ... of the Indian Constitution mandates the State to make special provision for women and children. However, in the course of enacting special laws for women, it as to be noted that cynical misuse of the laws do not take place. These laws which are made to protect women should not pose a threat to men. Basically, the laws which are made to save a life should not in the course of saving a life, take or ruin another life.

Now, according to me, gender blindness means those laws which are not in consonance with gender equality. This is because such laws, inter alia seem to have presumed men to be the perpetrators and women as the victim. Besides, the language, words or phrases used in many provisions also seem to show that such crime can only be committed by men, and not women- thus discriminating men on the grounds of their gender.

The first example of a gender blind law in India would be 498A, which is popularly known as the anti-dowry law. This law was made with the bona fide intention *to combat the menace of dowry deaths and harassment to a woman at the hands of her husband or his relatives*². This provision of law has left a plethora of loopholes for its misuse. It is more misused, than used. Sec 498 is the most

²In *Onkar Nath Mishra & Ors vs State (Nct Of Delhi) & Anr* on 14 December, 2007

abused law in the history of Indian jurisprudence. It is widely used as a tool of extortion and intimidation by women, thus rendering a large number of families completely terrorised and ruined. Although this law has been successful in many cases in punishing the dowry seekers, it has also given absolute power to a woman with 'oblique motives'³ to file a false complaint, because, as per this provision, all a woman is to do is to file an oral or a written complaint, she can give the name of her husband or any other person in her in-laws without giving any evidence of the truth of her statement. Adding to the problem is that the accused is presumed to be guilty and imprisoned, unless proved innocent. The charges are non-bailable (until there is a court hearing), cognizable (police may arrest without a warrant) and non-compoundable (prosecution cannot be withdrawn or settled between parties). The Hon'ble Supreme Court has said that 498 'has lent it a dubious place of fright' by 'disgruntled wives.' And, it has also referred to the false cases filed under this section as the *new legal terrorism*⁴, and the provision is intended to be used a shield and not assassins' weapon⁵. Today this law has turned draconian in nature and we hear tales of it being misused by several women who use it as a tool to extract more money out of men in divorce proceedings which has earned several men the tag of an ATM machine⁶.

Another gender-blind law is the provision for *assault or criminal force to woman with intent to outrage her modesty*⁷. This section prescribes punishment for doing the abovementioned act; however, it does not include the conduct of a woman outraging the modesty of a woman. The Shorter Oxford

English Dictionary (Third Edition) defines the word "modest" in relation to woman as follows: "Decorous in manner and conduct; not forward or lewd; shame fast" Hence (in later use also of men) scrupulously chaste. "Modesty" is defined as the quality of being modest, and in relation to woman, "womanly propriety of behaviour; scrupulous chastity of thought, speech and conduct"⁸. Also, the Hon'ble Supreme Court has opined that "The essence of a woman's modesty is her sex"⁹. "When a female can possess the element of modesty (which is the attribute of her sex¹⁰) or decency from her very birth¹¹, then why cannot men also possess the same attribute from birth? This answer to this question needs to be introspected.

Similarly, under [Section 354 A of the Indian Penal Code](#), a man can serve up to 3 years of imprisonment for sexually harassing a woman, but there is no such law made for men who are sexually harassed.

Also in the law on stalking¹², stalking is defined¹³ in a language which shows men as perpetrators and women as victims. The law itself says it's an offence only if it's a man doing it, and only if the victim is a woman.

⁸ *Major Singh Lachhman Singh vs. The State*, AIR 1963 P H 443, 1963 CriLJ 390.

⁹ *State Of Punjab vs. Major Singh*, 1967 AIR 63, 1966 SCR (2) 286

¹⁰ *Ibid*, Bachawat J: The essence of a woman's modesty is her sex. Even a female of tender age from her very birth possesses the modesty which is the attribute of her sex.

¹¹ *Supra* note 10.

¹² Stalking is defined us 354D, IPC, 1860

¹³ (1) Any man who—

1. follows a woman and contacts, or attempts to contact such woman to foster personal interaction repeatedly despite a clear indication of disinterest by such woman; or
2. monitors the use by a woman of the internet, email or any other form of electronic communication, commits the offence of stalking;

³ *Sushil Kumar Sharma vs Union Of India And Ors* on 19 July, 2005

⁴ *Supra* note 3.

⁵ *Ibid*.

⁶ <http://www.oneindia.com/india/interview-men-are-not-atm-machines-for-their-ex-wives-1666306.html>

⁷ Sec.354, IPC

The rape law, as provided in Sec.376 of the IPC is very popular and needs no introduction. The provision considers rape on women only, by men. There is no room for adult male victims. It does not consider the other way round, i.e., man being raped by a woman. One key area identified in female rape is the role of newspapers in dispelling or fuelling rape myths¹⁴. Although the news channels, especially the national newspapers and news channels do not cover such cases. The Police also are reluctant in filing a complaint; rather it makes a mocking the masculinity of the complainant. This also leads to a lack of numerical evidence and under-reporting of male rape. Thanks to Section 377 of the IPC which penalises all acts of non-consensual carnal intercourse, in turn including male on male rape. Many state agencies like the police are still using a woman-focused model of victimisation when dealing with male rape victims, when a specific male-focused model of victimisation is required, as male rape victims experience rape differently to female rape victims, for example, males may question their 'masculinity' if they were raped¹⁵.

4. GENDER NEUTRALITY V. GENDER PROTECTIONISM

It is very important to chalk out the difference between gender neutrality and gender protection. On the one hand, gender neutrality is important; on the other gender protectionism is also important. It is time to realise the below formulae:-

GENDER RIGHTS= WOMEN'S RIGHTS + MEN'S RIGHTS

We, therefore, cannot deny the basic human rights to any of the gender. If we cannot acknowledge alternative masculinities and

¹⁴ Male Rape: The Emergence of a Social and Legal Issue, By N. Abdullah-Khan

¹⁵ [http://www.internetjournalofcriminology.com/javaid male rape the invisible male ijc jan 2014.pdf](http://www.internetjournalofcriminology.com/javaid%20male%20rape%20the%20invisible%20male%20ijc%20jan%202014.pdf)

femininities and see the resistance, the strength, of both men and women, we cannot successfully challenge the dominant mode of gender identities and gender relations (which arguably facilitates problematic and dangerous outcomes for both men and women)¹⁶.

Viewed from a man's perspective, she (the woman) challenges patriarchy and disrupts masculinity, because masculinity is structured in binary opposition to femininity (male versus female, strong versus weak), and strengthening the female position means weakening the male position¹⁷.

Over the years, people have formed an opinion that gender means women. Men have never been focussed upon; especially their sufferings have always been ignored or presumed that they do not suffer. Although, on a comparative basis, women have suffered more than men, yet, it does not mean that the so called protectors never fall a prey or they do not need protection. This has led to an imbalance in the understanding of gender roles and gender rights. It has given birth to gender dichotomy.

If we keenly observe the gender roles imparted to us in our childhood, we realize that society has classified human qualities as masculine and feminine. Neither the nature nor God has not done so- this is clear from the text of Rig Veda:-

"O women! These mantras are given to you equally (as to men). May your thoughts, too, be harmonious. May your assemblies be open to all without discrimination. Your mind and consciousness should be

¹⁶ From Boys to Men: Social Constructions of Masculinity in Contemporary Society, By Tamara Shefer

¹⁷ Super Bitches and Action Babes: The Female Hero in Popular Cinema, 1970-2006 By Rikke Schubart, at pg-86.

harmonious. I (the rishi) give you these mantras equally as to men and give you all and equal powers to absorb (the full powers) of these mantras.¹⁸

The notion of men and women being opposites or at two poles is thus a creation of man. Therefore, with changing times, the notion can and should change. There can be a woman who possesses masculine qualities, and similarly, there can be a man with womanly qualities. A beautiful human is someone who has the best qualities of both man and woman. When I am strong and gentle, when I am rational and emotional, when I am brave and compassionate like Buddha. A man can only be a Buddha if he has feminine qualities also. A Hitler can never become a Buddha¹⁹.

In the case *Budhan Choudhry and Ors. v. State of Bihar*²⁰, a contention was raised that a provision of law may not be discriminatory but it may lend itself to abuse bringing about discrimination between the persons similarly situated. The court repelled the contention holding that on the possibility of abuse of a provision by the authority, the legislation may not be held arbitrary or discriminatory and violative of Article 14 of the Constitution.

5. CONCLUSION

Men have always been the privileged partners in the binarism of genders, invisibilised by their normativity, yet assumed to be the centre by their dominance²¹. Most of the people are not even

¹⁸ Rig Veda

¹⁹Renowned women rights activist and gender trainer KAMLA BHASIN talks to Shamsuddoza Sajen , Sr.

²⁰*Budhan Choudhry and Ors. v. State of Bihar*, AIR (1955) SC 191

²¹ From Boys to Men: Social Constructions of Masculinity in Contemporary Society, By Tamara Shefer

aware that men are sexually harassed as well. It is very sad to hear learned people commenting that *there are no instances of women raping men*²² and asking *where are the cases of sexual violence against men*²³? Male discrimination should be seen as a social issue, not as a normalisation as it looms across the socio-legal aspects of the society.

The Justice Verma panel had recommended that sexual assault be made a gender-neutral crime. However, it did not happen. I think that making the crime gender-neutral would have helped men who are raped.

Justice Virender Bhat, passing final orders in a false rape case filed in Delhi recently said, "The evil of perjury has assumed alarming proportions in cases depending upon oral evidence and therefore, the time has come to deal with this menace with an iron hand."²⁴

It has been suggested by Groth and Burgess (1980: 810) that because of the scarcity of data on the victims of male rape due to a 'combination of cultural, social, legal and

²² While opposing gender-neutral rape laws, Delhi advocate Vrinda Grover said, "Why should rape laws be gender-neutral? That would be making a mockery of what is actually happening in the country. There are no instances of women raping men. I don't think men are facing serious sexual violence as women. Consider the brutality and intensity of sexual violence against women. Hope the home minister does not put out a bill that delays or obfuscates discussions on the issue".

²³ D. Geetha, a Chennai based lawyer specializing in women's issues said, "Where are the cases of sexual violence against men? Tackling sexual violence against women and the way they are treated in our society is the need of the hour. They are vulnerable at home, work and even in police stations. Rather than working for gender neutral law, we should work to strengthen the justice delivery mechanism for women."

²⁴<http://www.tehelka.com/2015/10/laws-give-licence-for-legal-terrorism-deepika-narayan-bhardwai/>

psychological issues, male rape remains one of the most unaddressed issues in our society²⁵.

We had our traditional patriarchy but now we have modern capitalist patriarchy, which is very powerful. Because we live together, we are not enemies. Justice comes after the rape of a woman. I am more interested in preventing a rape. How will I prevent rape? By changing the mindset of boys and men. By changing the mindsets of families who do not control their boys. We need to work much more on ourselves. I felt when those five men raped a woman that I was responsible for producing five rapists. They are not borne. We produce them. We know rape is not a crime of sexuality but it is a crime of power. We have to work on implementing our laws. We have to really change everything because everything is patriarchy²⁶.

Gender equality is the bedrock necessities of all equalities. Gender equality is a public and social commitment. And, therefore, we are all together responsible for a solution. Gender inequality is indispensable if we want development.

Gender is used as a way to construct our children's reality. Gender communication to children: colour- pink/ blue, crying, toys

Men's Rights and Men's Issues are not limited to false dowry cases. Our main concern is male hatred in the society and socially accepted discrimination against men²⁷.

There have been several changes in order to combat false cases. For example in the Domestic Violence Act, not only men, but women can also be prosecuted. The Supreme Court has held that a woman can also be "perpetrators and abettors of domestic violence" and therefore, they can also be punished.

If there can be He for She, then why cannot we have She for He? We (men and women) are not enemies of each other, and we have to support each other in cases where required.

It is well settled that mere possibility of abuse of a provisions of law does not per se invalidate a legislation. It must be presumed, unless contrary is proved, that administrative and application of a particular law would be done "not with an evil eye and unequal hand" -(*Thangal Kunju Musaliar v. M. Venkatachalam Potti, Authorised Official and Income-Tax officer and Anr.*)²⁸.

Sweden has already set up the world's first rape crisis centre exclusively for men. [Sodersjukhusct hospital](#) in the country has started a 24-hour care for men and boys who have survived rape and sexual violence²⁹.

As observed in *Maulavi Hussein Haji Abraham Umarji v. State of Gujarat*,³⁰ *Unique Butle Tube Industries (P) Ltd. v. U.P. Financial Corporation and Ors.*,³¹ and *Padma Sundara Rago (dead) and Ors. v. State*,³² while interpreting a provision, the Court only interprets the law and cannot legislate it. If a provision of Law is misused and subjected to the abuse of the process of law, it is for the legislature to amend, modify or repeal it, if deemed necessary.

The situation in India is slowly changing. About 498A, the Apex Court has ruled in a case that *the attitude to arrest first and then proceed with the rest is despicable. It has become a handy tool to the police officers who lack sensitivity or act with oblique motive*³³. It has directed the state government to ensure that police do not resort to arresting in all offences punishable up to seven-year jail term including dowry harassment cases.

²⁵ Male Rape: The Emergence of a Social and Legal Issue, By N. Abdullah-Khan

²⁶ Kamla Bhasin

²⁷ <http://www.oneindia.com/india/interview-men-are-not-atm-machines-for-their-ex-wives-1666306.html>

²⁸ AIR (1956) SC 246

²⁹ <http://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2016/06/male-survivors-of-sexual-violence/>

³⁰ [2004] 6 SCC 672

³¹ [2003] 2 SCC 455

³² [2002] 3 SCC 533

³³ *Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar*, 2014 Indlaw SC 425; (2014) 8 SCC 273; AIR 2014 SC 2756; 2014 CRLJ 3707; 2014 (210) DLT 599; 2014 (2) G.L.R. 1848; JT 2014 (7) SC 527;

THE INTERNATIONAL CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST WOMEN AND POLITICAL STATUS OF WOMEN IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Marginalization and under-representation of women in important decision-making bodies is a universal phenomenon. Therefore, empowering women has become one of the critical issues of the 21st century. There seems to be a consensus emerging that the most effective therapy to this malady is empowering women by granting them political and legal rights and ensuring their effective implementation. It has been also advocated by most of the important conventions relating to rights of women like the International Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) and other instruments. Incorporation of political and legal rights of women in the constitutional and legal system of a given society is the best way to empower women. The well-defined political and legal rights for women in the constitution will provide a concrete foundation for them to stand up confidently against the crimes and atrocities in the patriarchal society. Participation of women in the political decision making endorsed by the legal system of the country provide them a self-protective shield, which supports them strongly to beat all the odds in the patriarchal society as per law. Moreover, a legal claim in the social, economic and political fields is very important for women to deal with their grievances effectively. In the light of the aforementioned assumption, this paper analyses the impact of the CEDAW in India with special emphasis on participation of women in political decision making. To assess the impact of CEDAW on women participation in political decision making in India “before and after” approach has been used for this study. Women participation at the local level is comparatively high to the representation of women in the parliament due to reservation policy at local level. Despite this their participation does not touch the real essence of empowering them politically.

Keywords: *Women empowerment, Political participation, Legislation, and CEDAW*

Study of women has always been countered with gruesome subjectivism. They have been culturally or forcefully pushed toward their limitation and over the period of time it grossly amounted to become a universal phenomenon. This has led to the under

representation in every prominent decisional making institution in the society. From this immemorial they have been forced to accept their inferior position in the society. This subjugation and subordination has been legitimized on the basis of male dominated cultural values and social milieu. It is in the

20th century that women representation, their marginalization and subtle pattern of peripheralisation became a prominent issue of debate and discussion. The establishment of the United Nations in 1945 indeed provided impetus to the feminist movement and thereby since of their empowerment through effective participation in the decision making bodies. It emphasized that empowering women is an important feature for seeking human rights globally. Therefore, Millennium Development Goal was designed by the United Nations which shows sensitivity toward addressing the issue of women. Truly the Charter of the United Nations granted some degree of dignity to the women under the shadow of equal rights to the men and women. The Commission on the Status of Women (CWS), a principal institution was set up exclusively under the guidance of United Nations to effectively address the women issue at the global level. To achieve its purpose of equality between men and women United Nations adopted many Conventions and Declarations for example Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966, Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989, The Convention on the Political Rights of Women 1953, and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women 1979 etc. similarly there are other several important conferences were also held in Mexico City, Copenhagen, Nairobi and Beijing under the aegis of United Nations to strengthen the status of women.

Women Empowerment

The phrase women empowerment is used in two broad senses i.e. general and specific. In a general sense, it refers to empowering women to be self-dependent by providing them access to all the freedoms and opportunities, which they have been denied in the past only because of their just being

‘women’. In a specific use in two broad sense women empowerment refers to enhancing their position in the power structure of the society.¹

According to definition “**Empowerment is the expansion of assets and capabilities of poor people to participate in, negotiate with, influence, control, and hold accountable institutions that affect their lives.**”² it cannot be denied that political representation is included in the institutions mentioned in the definition of women empowerment. In its broadest sense, women empowerment is the way to enjoy freedom of choice and action. It means increasing one’s ability to engage in decisions that affect one’s life.

Women empowerment may mean equal status to women, opportunity and freedom to develop her-self. The focus of empowerment is equipping women to be economically independent, self-reliant, have a positive self-esteem to enable them to face any difficult situation and they should be able to participate in the process of decision-making.³

State and its agencies are the most powerful decision making bodies of our time. Then the empowerment of women will be a hoax if they are not given their due representation in the state and its maintained institutions.

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women

Among all the important conventions adopted under the aegis of the United Nations for the purpose of women empowerment, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) is the most important one adopted in 1979, the Convention was recognized as an **international bill of rights for women**. It came into force on 3rd September, 1981 and

has 30 articles which are divided into six parts.

Part I (Articles 1-6) focuses on non-discrimination, sex stereotypes, and sex trafficking.

Part II (Articles 7-9) outlines women's rights in the public sphere with an emphasis on political life, representation, and rights to nationality.

Part III (Articles 10-14) describes the economic and social rights of women, particularly focusing on education, employment, and health. Part III also includes special protections for rural women and the problems they face.

Part IV (Article 15 and 16) outlines women's right to equality in marriage and family life along with the right to equality before the law.

Part V (Articles 17-22) establishes the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women as well as the states parties' reporting procedure.

Part VI (Articles 23-30) describes the effects of the Convention on other treaties, the commitment of the state parties and the administration of the Convention. It is the most important instrument for the protection of women at international level and played crucial role in the empowerment of women.⁴

Political Participation

There seems to be a consensus emerging that the most effective therapy to the marginalization of women is empowering women by granting them political and legal rights and ensuring their effective implementation. Incorporation of political and legal rights of women in the constitutional and legal system of a given society is the best way to empower them. The well-defined political and legal rights for women in the constitution will provide a concrete foundation for them to stand up confidently against the crimes and atrocities in the patriarchal society. Participation of women in the political decision making endorsed by the legal system of the country provide them a self-protective shield, which supports them strongly to beat all the odds in the patriarchal society as per law. Moreover, a legal claim in the social, economic and

political fields is very important for women to deal with their grievances effectively.

Now question arises what is the meaning of political participation? In article 7 and article 8 CEDAW discusses the political participation in the following term:

Article 7

States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in the Political and public life of the country and, in particular, shall ensure to women, on equal terms with men, the right:

- (a) To vote in all elections and public referenda and to be eligible for election to all publicly elected bodies;*
- (b) To participate in the formulation of government policy and the implementation thereof and to hold Public office and perform all public functions at all levels of government;*
- (c) To participate in non-governmental organizations and associations concerned with the public and political life of the country.⁵*

Article 8

States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure to women, on equal terms with men and without any discrimination, the opportunity to represent their Governments at the international level and to participate in the work of international organizations.⁶

In the modern concept political participation is not limited to simply participation in government making like traditional concept. In the democracy political participation has been expanded from right to vote to participation in decision making process, political activism and political consciousness etc. In others words political participation means not only exercising the right to vote, but also power sharing, co decision making, co policy making at all levels of governance of the state.⁶

Before we delve deep into the issue of political participation of women it is important to evaluate the meaning of the term political participation.

The International Encyclopedia of Social Sciences defined political participation as the principal means by which consent is granted or withdrawn in a democracy and rulers are made accountable to the ruled.⁷

Verba and Pye define it as, "Those activities by private citizens that are more or less directly aimed at influencing the selection of governmental personnel and the actions they take".⁸ In continuation examining the modes of political participation **Schonfeld** has mentioned ten types of activities which include (1) running for or holding public or party offices, (2) belonging to a party or other political organization, (3) working in an election, (4) attending political meetings or rallies, (5) making financial contribution to a party or a candidate, (6) contacting a public official, (7) publicly expressing a political opinion to convince others, (8) partaking in political discussion, (9) voting, and (10) exposing oneself to political stimuli.⁹

On the basis of above definitions we can say that political participation is not just restricted to casting vote but it also includes other activities in it, for example membership of political party, electoral campaigning, attending party meetings, demonstrations, communication with leaders, holding party positions, contesting election, membership in representative bodies, influencing decision making and other related activities.¹⁰ In fact their activities in the political and social arena must be considered as an international parameter to judge the effective and genuine participation of women in the political decision making process.

Indian Constitution and Women

The issue of marginalization and under representation of women has become global phenomenon. Women's concerns are still given second priority almost everywhere. According to the Report of the World Conference of the UN Decade for Women, Copenhagen, July 1980: "While Women represent 50 per cent of the world adult population and a-third of official labour force, they perform nearly two-thirds of all working hours, receive only a-tenth of world income and own less than one per cent of the world property".¹¹ India is also unable to break this reality although since independence India was gender sensitive. It recognized women as a special group with the establishment of non-discrimination provision on the basis of sex. Indian constitution has wide range of provisions for women which starts with the **Preamble** and extent through, **Part III, Part IV** and others provisions. **Preamble** defines the basic structure of the constitution shares the protection of women in the form of equality. **Part III and Part IV** of the constitution are fully conscious to the women well-being. Articles related to the rights for women are in the following.

Article 14 provides equality before the law or equal protection of law to its all citizens including women

Article 15 enshrines the non-discrimination principle and prohibited discrimination on the basis of inter alia sex. 15 (3) has worth to discuss because it provide special provision for women.

Article 16 emphasizes on the equality of opportunity in public employment by preventing discrimination on the basis of inter alia sex.

Article 21 protects the life and liberty and includes basic rights.

Article 23 prohibits the exploitation and trafficking in human being.

Although **Part IV** of the Constitution containing **Directive Principle of State Policy (DPSP)** is not justiciable yet it cannot be simply ignored. It has the potential to address the women issues in multi-dimensional way.

Article 39 protects the right to an adequate means of livelihood, health and equal pay for equal work for both men and women. Besides this it protects to the citizens from economic necessity which force to them to engage in occupation, unsuited for their age or strength.

Article 42 provides maternity relief and just and human condition of work.

Article 47 talks to increase the level of nutrition and standard of living of its people.

India strengthens her constitutional provisions by signing and ratifying the international convention CEDAW on the 30th July, 1980 and on the 9th July, 1993 respectively. In fact India was under CEDAW obligation after ratifying it i.e. 1993. However, as a signatory to the convention in 1980, India was under moral obligation to deal with the grievances of women in accordance with the provisions of CEDAW. Therefore, the paper analyses the issue of political participation of women in two parts to evaluate the impact of CEDAW on the women particularly on the political status of women in India. The analyses periods have been divided into two parts, first part deal with the period of before signing the CEDAW i.e. 1947 to 1980 and second part deal with the period of after signing the CEDAW 1980 to till now.

Political Status of Women Before 1980

It is considered that the actual social status and effective level of political participation cannot be understood in isolation. It is interlinked with socio economic conditions, political climate and inequalities inherent in the traditional social structure, its norms and values, custom and rituals.¹²

In the aforesaid it has been discussed that India since independence is committed to provide space for gender equality. There have been various shifts in policy during the past years from the concept of welfare to empowerment. Meanwhile India's approach towards the women well-being in 70s, development in the 80s and empowerment in

90s are remarkable contribution in history of women welfare. By standing on the developmental approach India passed bunches of special provision under the guidance of women welfare i.e. **The Special Marriage Act 1954** with the provision of inter caste marriage provides freedom of choice in the matters of matrimony. Moreover, **The Hindu Succession Act 1956** introduced the right to have equal share in property. **The Immoral Trafficking Act 1956** that protected the women from illegal human trafficking. **The Maternity Benefit Act 1961** just added another feather in the cap to procure extra privilege to women in the field of labor force with granting maternity leave and its **Amendment Bill 2016** was passed in Rajya Sabha which seeks to increase maternity leave from 12 weeks to 26 weeks. **The Dowry Prohibition Act 1961** tried to remove stereotypes practicing on the women for not bringing dowry. **The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act 1971** saved the life of many female from infanticides. Actually it made a water tight compartment for the sex selective abortion which was frequently practiced. **The Equal Remuneration Act 1976** recognized women equal to men in term of work and provided provision equal pay for equal work to men and women.

Despite legislative acts women continue to remain marginalized in decision making bodies. **The Committee on the Status of Women** in India CSWI in its report "toward equality" 1974 recognized tokenism in women representation and reveals that political parties have "tended to see the women voters and citizens as appendage of the male...."¹³

The above discussed argument is based on initiatives taken by the government in past certain years to provide legal opportunity to empower women. But analyzing political power shared by the women within the specific years let us more central toward the addressing result. Political participation

means not only exercising the right to vote, but also power sharing, co decision making, co policy making at all levels of governance of the state.

Political Status of Women After 1980

As we discussed that the actual status of women in politics is interlinked with socio and economic condition of women. After signing the CEDAW India adopted and enacted several acts and policies for the improvement of women socio economic condition in compliance with CEDAW. **Indecent Representation of Women Act 1986** was enacted to prohibit indecent representation of women through advertisement or in publications, writings, paintings, figures or in any other manner. **Commission on Sati Act 1987 Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987** is law enacted by Government of Rajasthan in 1987. It became an Act of the Parliament of India with the enactment of the Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987 in 1988. The Act seeks to prevent Sati practice or the voluntary or forced burning or burying alive of widows. **The National plan of Action for the Girl Child 1991-2000** is a specially formulated action plan by the Government of India to protect and promote the Girl Child. This plan seeks to prevent female feticide and infanticide, eliminate gender discrimination, provide safe drinking water and fodder near homes, rehabilitate and protect girls from exploitation, assault and abuse. **The National Commission for Women 1992 (NCW)** is a statutory body of the Government of India, generally concerned with advising the government on all policy matters affecting women. The objective of the NCW is to represent the rights of women in India and to provide a voice for their issues and concerns. **National policy for the Empowerment of Women 2001** was prepared by the Department of Women and Child Development with the goal advancement, development and empowerment of women. **The Protection of**

Women from Domestic Violence Act 2005 was like a momentum in the favor of women. It prohibited one of the most prevailing and justifiable evil of Indian society that is domestic violence. **The Prohibition of Child marriage Act 2006** provides 18 year minimum age for girls. Minor girl generally was victim of child marriage. Women and girls have been protected from the harmful conditions those occurred in the result of child marriage through this act. **The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012** was enacted to protect children from sexual assault. **The Criminal Law Amendment Act 2013** was enacted to make the punishment more rigorous for offences like rape. Due to amendment act now Indian Penal Code includes new offences like acid attack, sexual harassment, voyeurism and stalking and disrobing a women etc. in its purview. **Sexual Harassment Act 2013** seeks to protect women from sexual harassment at their place of work.

The next mile stone attached to real women empowerment done by the enactment of The 73rd Amendment Act 1992 which provides three tier system of local Government with associated clause made mandatory for the 33 percent reservation of seats for women in Panchayati Raj Election. It was the first time where not just well-being of women is targeted besides that it also endorses platform for the real development of women agency. This amendment was made in order to improve the position of women especially at the grass root level and thus, providing political choice at ground level. In addition to this, the 74th Amendment Act 1992 made the provisions relating to Urban Local Governments (Nagarpalikas). The total seats (including the seats reserved for women belonging to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes) to be filled by direct election in every Municipal (Nagarpalikas) election, not less than one-third shall be reserved for women and such seats may be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in Municipality. The most

prominent feature of the 73rd and 74th amendment is one third reservation of elected offices for women and for SCs and STs in proportion to their population. Women political participation at local level is satisfactory at least on paper. There are 13.42 lakhs Elected Women Representatives in Panchayat raj Institutions which constitute 46% of total Elected Representatives¹⁴ but they acted merely as the dummy of their male family members. Interestingly there are some states which are more sensitive towards women participation at local level and they exceeded reservation from 33% to 50% in their respective states. Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, West Bengal and Uttrakhand etc. are some example of that states.¹⁴

The second mile stone in compliance with Article 7 and 8 of CEDAW which discusses the political participation of women was the introduction of **women Reservation Bill in 1996**, which seeks to reserve 33 per cent of all seats in the Lower House of Parliament of India, the Lok Sabha and in all state Legislative assemblies for women. The Bill has been passed by the Upper House Rajya Sabha in 2010 but unfortunately bill is still pending in Lok Sabha.

Conclusion and suggestions

After signing the CEDAW in 1980 India adopted various measures to enforce its provision. It led to marked improvement in the political participation of women and their empowerment. According to data given in the tables, improvement can be noticed in the percentage of women MPs from 5.15% in 1980 to 8.9% in 1984. The 16th Lok Sabha Election was remarkable with 11.23% women MPs. There was improvement of 3.37% in average percentage of women MPs during the first period and second period. The percentage of female contestant has been increasing and reached at the average percentage of 5.29 while during the first period the average percentage of female

contestant was 2.94. It is delighting to mention that percentage of women winning candidates has always been high against percentage of man winning candidates. However this percentage of female winning candidates declined from average 39.59 in first period to 13.72 in second period. The participation of women as CM and Governor of state has been improved with average 3.11 which quietly high against the first period. Women as voter completed tough task and successfully reduced huge gap between men as voters and women as voters. The 16th Lok Sabha Election was remarkable in terms of women voter turnout. The difference between percentage of male voters and female voters was reduced to 1.46 which was 16.68 during initial elections. Rajya Sabha has also noticed increment in women members from 8.25% to 10.78%. (All data collected from reports of various Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha election of Election Commission of India (interpreted in percentage format)

Data at state level extract from

Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_female_Indian_chief_ministers (drive number of seats from archive data

The Constitution of India provides rights to all women against discrimination on the basis of sex, caste and place of birth etc. yet we can notice that participation of women in political decision making bodies is not impressive. The numbers of women politicians is low as compared to men.

No doubt improvement can be noticed in women voting turnout but participation as voters cannot be considered as reliable basis for measurement of political participation. But Mostly women vote under the influence of male members of their family.

In fact participation of women in local bodies is a welcome sign. The participation of women in local government makes other women confident to serve in various professions and lead to breaking stereotypes

about women's roles in society and public spheres. Society had gained confidence in women as good public administrator and acknowledged the sincerity and commitment of women to their duties. Nevertheless, it must be mentioned here political participation of women has been increased due to reservation policy but they acted merely as the dummy of their male family members. This advocates the possibility of variations between participation of women on paper and what actually exist on ground. It is easy to collect quantitative data of political participation of women at local level but to measure qualitative data on the aspect of their active participation is difficult. Therefore, data on their awareness about their rights and its usage is still vague. It can be easily observed that the condition of women in politics has been improved after signing CEDAW by India.

Only reservation cannot solve the problem unless and until women are given equal power to function effectively. The male representative should establish understanding with female representatives and give due respect and attention to their opinions. Initiatives should be taking place at large scale to aware women about their role as representative by the government and NGOs.

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THE INTERNATIONAL CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION
AGAINST WOMEN AND POLITICAL STATUS OF WOMEN IN INDIA

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GENDER INEQUALITY IN INDIA

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Abstract:

The present conceptual paper on gender inequality in India not only concerned with socio-economic aspects like what is gender inequality, how it is exist in India, the types of gender inequalities and what are the reasons behind the gender inequalities but also critically analyzing the various laws that increase gender inequality in India like Hindu laws of inheritance, Age of consent, The Goa Law on polygamy etc. The paper also draw a light on the programs launched by the Indian government to overcome the gender inequality from the country. The paper gives attention towards the challenges which hindrance in removing gender inequality and also provides the ways how these waterlogs can be removed.

Keywords: *Gender, Inequality, Problem. Rights, India*

Gender equality is achieved when women and men enjoy the same rights and opportunities across all the sectors of society, including economic participation and decision-making, and when the different behaviors, aspirations and needs of women and men are equally valued and favored. But in India it is not easy to bring gender equality because in India the society is controlled by men. It is clear from the fact that rejoice in celebrations when a boy is born, and if it is a girl, a muted or no celebrations is the norm. Love for a male child is so much that from the times immemorial we are killing our daughters at birth or before birth, and if, fortunately, she is not killed we find various ways to discriminate against her throughout her life. Though our religious beliefs make women a goddess but we fail to recognize her as a human being first; we worship goddesses but we exploit girls. In India we are a society of people with double-standards as far as our attitude towards women is concerned; our thoughts and preaching are different than our actions.

1. Definition and Concept of Gender Inequality

'Gender' is a socio-cultural term referring socially defined roles and behaviors assigned to 'males' and 'females' in a given society; whereas, the term 'sex' is a biological and physiological phenomenon which defines man and woman. Therefore, gender may be understood as a man-made concept, while 'sex' is natural or biological characteristics of human beings.

Gender Inequality, in simple words, may be defined as discrimination against women based on their sex. Women are traditionally considered by the society as weaker sex. She has been accorded a subordinate position to men. She is exploited, degraded, violated and discriminated both in our homes and in outside world. This peculiar type of discrimination against women is prevalent everywhere in the world and more so in Indian society.

UN Secretary General Kofi Annan has stated, "Gender equality is more than a goal in itself. It is a precondition for meeting the challenge of reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and building good governance."

According to me "gender inequality is a worst situation in which we make girls deprived of their rights and force them to do what we expect that they should do"

1. Reasons for gender inequalities

- a. **Patriarchal society---** Patriarchy is a social system of privilege in which men are the primary authority figures, occupying roles of political leadership, moral authority, control of property, and authority over women and children.
- b. **Son preference---** A key factor driving gender inequality is the preference for sons, as they are deemed more useful than girls. Boys are given the exclusive rights to inherit the family name and properties and they are viewed as additional status for their family.
- c. **Discrimination against girls-----** While women express a strong preference for having at least one son, the evidence of discrimination against girls after they are born is mixed. A study of 1990s survey data by scholars found less evidence of systematic discrimination in feeding practices between young boys and girls, or gender based nutritional discrimination in India.
- d. **Dowry-----** in India, dowry is the payment in cash or some kind of gifts given to bridegroom's family along with the bride. The practice is widespread across geographic region, class and religions.
- e. **Poverty:**In India of the total 30 percent people who are below poverty line, 70 percent are women. Women's poverty in India is directly related to the absence of economic opportunities and autonomy, lack of access to economic

resources including credit , land ownership and inheritance, lack of access to education and support services and their minimal participation in the decision making process.

- f. **Lack of Employment Facilities:**Women are not able to resolve the conflict between new economic and old domestic roles. In both rural and urban India, women spend a large proportion of time on unpaid home sustaining work. Women are not able to respond to new opportunities and shift to new occupations because their mobility tends to be low due to intra-house hold allocation of responsibilities.

2. Nine laws in India that make women less equal than men

- a. **Hindu laws of inheritance---** according to the Hindu inheritance law, the property of a woman who dies without a will is handled differently from that of a man. In the absence of spouse and children, the husband's heirs inherit the woman's estate.
- b. **Parsi laws of inheritance---** Despite decreasing numbers in the Parsi community, those who marry outside the community are penalized. A non-parsi woman who is either a wife or a widow of a Parsi man cannot inherit. However, their children can. But again, a Parsi woman marrying a non-Parsi man cannot be considered a part of the Parsi community.
- c. **Prohibition of Child Marriage Act:** The law only prohibits the marriages of children; it does not render them illegal once they actually happen. The married children, however, have the right to declare it void. A woman can call off a marriage until she turns 20, whereas a man has till age 23.
- d. **Age of consent:**Sexual intercourse with a girl below the age of 18 is considered rape. But since child marriages are not illegal, a man can legally have sex with his wife even if

she is a minor, as long as she is above the age of 15. Further, marital rape is still not criminalized in India.

- e. **Marriageable age:** The minimum age for marriage for a boy is 21, but 18 for a girl. This is a legal extension of the patriarchal mindset that believes that a wife should always be younger than the man.
- f. **Rape of a separated wife:** The rape of a separated wife carries lesser punishment than the rape of any other woman.
- g. **The Goa Law on polygamy:** A law recognizes the second marriage of a “Gentile Hindu” man of Goa if his previous wife does not have any children before the age of 25 or if she does not have a male child by 30.
- h. **No right to marital property:** Upon separation or divorce, an Indian woman is entitled only to maintenance from her husband. She has no right to the assets, such as house or commercial property, bought in her husband’s name during the marriage.
- i. **Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act:** Women are still not equal guardians of their children. A father is considered the “natural guardian” of a child, although the custody of offspring under the age of 5 will ordinarily be awarded to the mother.

3. Political and legal reforms

Since its independence, India has made significant strides in addressing gender inequalities, especially in the areas of political participation, education, and legal rights. Policies and legal reforms to address gender inequalities have been pursued by the government of India. For instance, the Constitution of India contains a clause guaranteeing the right of equality and freedom from sexual discrimination.

India is also signatory to the Convention for the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, or CEDAW.

A listing of specific reforms is presented below:

1. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)
2. Prenatal Diagnostic Testing Ban
3. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013
4. Hindu Succession Act, 1956 (Amended in 2005; Gives equal inheritance rights to daughters and sons - applies to Hindus, Buddhists, Jains and Sikhs)
5. Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act of 1937,

4. Challenges for India according to UNDP

India ranks 130 out of 155 countries in the Gender Inequality Index (GII) for 2014, way behind Bangladesh and Pakistan that rank 111 and 121 respectively, according to data in the United National Development Programme’s latest Human Development Report (HDR) 2015.

Among South Asian countries, India fares better than only Afghanistan which is at 152.

The index captures inequalities in gender-specific indicators: reproductive health measured by maternal mortality ratio and adolescent birth rates, empowerment quantified by share of parliamentary seats and attainment in education, and economic activity measured by labour market participation rate. They list down some challenges that face by India to get to the gender equality.

- A. Persistent Inequality----** Persistent inequality is reflected in the low human development attainments of the country’s most marginalized groups including scheduled castes, tribal and rural populations, women, transgender, people living with HIV and migrants.

B. Gender Inequality despite Economic Growth---- Gender inequality in India persists despite high rates of economic growth, and is particularly apparent among marginalized groups.

C. Implementation Challenges of Rights-based Schemes----- The effectiveness of rights-based legislations such as the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, the Forest Rights Act and Panchayat Extension to Scheduled areas has been hampered by lack of implementation.

D. Feminization of the HIV epidemic--- An estimated 2.08 million people live with HIV in India, and are among the most visible of sexual minority groups, transgender remain largely invisible, isolated and subject to stereotypes.

5. Suggestions to remove gender inequality

The list of legislations as well as types of discriminations or inequalities may go on but the real change will only come when the mentality of men will change; when the male species of human beings would start treating women as equal and not subordinate or weaker to them.

In fact not only men but women also need to change their mindset as through cultural conditioning they have also become part of the same exploitative system of patriarchy and are playing a supportive role in furthering men's agenda of dominating women. The women needs to get themselves independent if they want really want to live their lives equally with the men. Some of the suggestions are dissed as follows

1. The women have been provided with the financial resources because when the women having the funds that means they are bring into economy and they are now no more dependent on the male counterpart.
2. The women have been provided the education so that the women is capable

of serving the society and earn some respect for themselves.

3. The women also need to change their mindset as through cultural conditioning they have also become part of the same exploitative system of patriarchy and are playing a supportive role in furthering men's agenda of dominating women.
4. The laws has needs to be made transparent and strict if anything goes unattainable against women then the person who find guilty has been given strong punishment to them .
5. **The parents needs to give their support not only to boy child they needs to give equal importance towards both child's.**
6. The schools also needs to teach value education to the children tis will remove gender inequality.

I personally feel that we should need to do this.

6. Summary

1. The Constitution of India ensures gender equality in its preamble as a fundamental right but also empowers the state to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favor of women by ways of legislation and policies. India has also ratified various international conventions and human rights forums to secure equal rights of women, such as ratification of Convention on elimination of all forms of discrimination against women in 1993.
2. The passing of Pre-natal Diagnostic Tech Act in 1994 also is a step in removing gender discrimination. This Act seeks to end sex-determination tests and female feticide and prohibits doctors from conducting such procedures for the specific purpose of determining the sex of the fetus.
3. The Government also announced the National policy for empowerment of women in 2001 to bring out advancement, development and empowerment of women

GENDER INEQUALITY IN INDIA

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4. As persistent gender inequalities continue we need to rethink concepts and strategies for promoting women's dignity and rights. *UN Secretary General Kofi Annan has stated, "Gender equality is more than a goal in itself. It is a precondition for meeting the challenge of reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and building good governance."* <http://indianexpress.com/article/india/india-news-india/more-gender-inequality-in-india-than-pak-bangla-un/>
5. There is a need for new kinds of institutions, incorporating new norms and rules that support equal and just relations between women and men. Today women are organizing themselves to meet the challenges that are hampering their development.
6. what is needed is the movement for Women's empowerment where women can become economically independent and self-reliant; where they can fight their own fears and go out in the world fearless; where they can snatch their rights from the clutches of men and they don't have to ask for them; where women have good education, good career, ownership of property and above all where they have freedom of choice and also the freedom to make their own decisions without the bondages of age old saying of Manu.

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IMPACT ON WAR ON CHILD: Analysis of psychological effects and need for Monitoring Mechanisms.

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Abstract:

It is very well said by Nelson Mandela, Former President of South Africa "There can be no keener revelation of a society's soul than the way in which it treats its children." But Eighteen million children are being raised in the chaos of war. In the past ten years, as a result of armed conflict, over 2 million children have been killed, 6 million have been disabled, 20 million are homeless, and more than 1 million have become separated from their caregivers. Some are recruited to become soldiers themselves and are placed directly in the firing line. When the heat of battle is over, landmines and unexploded ordinance can leave a deadly legacy for years.

Insurgent armies in India's restive Northeast region are exploiting the area's poverty to recruit and press-gang underage fighters and the problem has dramatically worsened in recent years. The Asian Centre for Human Rights says there are at least 500 child soldiers now in the Northeast. In Afghanistan children are "being used to perpetrate attacks and, in some cases, as human shields by the Taliban and other insurgents.

In 1996, Graça Machel, released a UN report entitled "The Impact of War on Children," bringing international attention to the subject among policy makers and academics. The 10 recommendations made in the report have become guiding principles to aid war-affected children. In this paper the author will be exploring the various reasons which result in non application of International protocols which prohibits injury to children and restricts recruitment under certain conditions, emphasis should be on psychosocial needs of war-affected children. Not only ongoing war but the paranoia or possibility of war can also severely affect the psychology of a generation of children.

Keywords: *press-gang underage fighters, human shields, aid war-affected children.*

During War, children and young people's rights are violated on a large scale; their rights to be protected from violence, abuse and neglect, to live in dignity and be supported to develop to their full potential. Eighteen million children are being raised in the chaos of war. In the past ten years, as a result of armed conflict, over 2 million children have been killed, 6 million have been disabled, 20

million are homeless, and more than 1 million have become separated from their caregivers.¹

¹ The Invisible Trauma War Affected Children, <https://www.psychologytoday.com/blog/talking-about-trauma/201304/the-invisible-trauma-war-affected-children>, accessed on 11th September, 2016.

The major psychological consequence of war .children and young generation lose their confidence .their trust in others and their trust in the future. This impact make them anxious, depressed, rebellious and aggressive. Consequences of War make lot of people refugees ,drag them away from their original place of residence ,make them homeless.it is not uncommon that children get separate from their parents because of various reasons like their father going to serve in the army, death of the parents in the War. Or evacuation from an area as a part of war time emergency. In England during the Second World War, children were often billeted to foster parents. The change in living standards whether for the better or worse was in many cases not welcome?

A child's life gets altered by the instance of war and its after effects on them at such tender age are often neglected. There is need for specific attention to such population comprising of children to be secured with proper medical facilities, rehabilitation from War trauma, re-joining an educational facility, accommodation etc. With support from International organization working in the field of funding such facilities appropriate to re-settle and rebuild such amenities to create such conducive environmental for healthy physical, social and mental development of war-affected children.

PHYSICAL HARM AND IMPERCEPTIBLE TRAUMA FACED BY WAR AFFECTED CHILDREN

1) PHYSICAL EFFECT ON CHILD:

Recent developments in warfare have significantly heightened the dangers for children. During the last decade, it is estimated (and these figures, while specific, are necessarily orders of magnitude) that child victims have included:

- 2 million killed;
- 4-5 million disabled;
- 12 million left homeless;

- More than 1 million orphaned or separated from their parents;
- Some 10 million psychologically traumatized.²
- These little life without any cause lost their life in the fight of two entities. Children without any reason have, always been caught up in warfare. They left with no choices but to face the horror of the warfare. And children have always been particularly exposed. In the situation of warfare it is quite common that food supply will run short, the child generation needs proper health care for their development and their growing bodies need steady supplies of essential nutrients. And the trauma of exposure to violence and brutal death has emotionally affected generations of teenage for the rest of their lives.
- Direct and indirect effect of War increase the child death in the warfare time period or make them gravely ill. After signing so many treaties or protocol on protection of child and women still at the time of conflict or war they are most effected groups, hospitals and health centres are destroyed, Children are most vulnerable to diseases like diarrhoea, malaria and cholera. Treatment is simple and cheap, but millions of children have died through lack of it.³These ongoing stresses have strong and lasting effects on children's socio-emotional well-being and their growing brains.
- Effect on children on Syria warfare: Research suggests that the physical consequences of conflict on a child's brain development can have adverse and these consequence are the potential for permanent changes to the brain's architecture. Without adequate intervention and the presence of protective and caring relationships, Syria's war could have a lasting impact on children's learning abilities, memory,

²<http://www.unicef.org/sowc96/1cinwar.htm> visited on 14th October 2016

³<https://www.warchild.org.uk/issues/effects-war-children> visited on 19th October 2016

social interactions, stress and fear responses, and the ability to control emotions. These war affected children from Syria warfare could lead to long-term mental health.⁴

- War results in numerous unsafe instances of kids who are gravely injured. Removal of appendages, loss of visual perception, or starvation and sickness over long stretches devastatingly affect the mind of the young generation, who survive this experience.
- There are not very many restrictive studies on the mental impacts of harm, however it has been noticed that a considerable measure of its impacts rely on upon the post war treatment. In nations such as Iraq and numerous African nations, the war harmed individuals keep on driving a crushed life. On the off chance that they are not completely impeded, numerous look upon their lives as a waste as they grow up and don't falter to join the terrorist bunches. They themselves neglect to show appreciation to lives of different people, and have no admiration for their own lives either, which makes them much more unsafe.⁵
- In zones such as **Japan (after the nuclear bomb pulverization)**, where adequate post war backing is given, in spite of the fact that the youngsters show side effects of PTSD for long, they step by step consolidate themselves with the standard. They take their debilitations if any into their step. However even among such youngsters, particularly on the off chance that they are more established,

self-destructive propensities have been noted.⁶

- **Spanish Civil War,1937**Mr.RICHARD W. B. ELLIS, O.B.E., M.D., F.R.C.P.(Professor of Child Life and Health, University of Edinburgh) had done a research on war impact on child health and marked that in Rotterdam and The Hague, where there was a period of acute under nutrition affecting the whole population for a relatively short and well-defined period in 1944-45, it was calculated that 50% of the female population became amenorrhoea, and that nine months later the birth rate was less than a third of the normal for the same cities (Smith, 1947). In Berlin the infant mortality rate in the British zone rose to well over 200 infant deaths per thousand live births between July and December, 1945, approximately four times the pre-war rate in Germany.⁷
- It is known that exposure to intense acute and chronic stressors during the developmental years has enduring neurobiological effects vis-a-vis the stress response and neurotransmitter systems with subsequent increased risk of anxiety and mood disorders, aggressive dyscontrol problems, hypimmune dysfunction, medical morbidity, structural changes in the CNS, and early death (DeBellis, Baum, et al., 1999; DeBellis, Keshavan, et al., 1999; Heim, Meinschmidt, & Nemeroff, 2003; McEwen, 1998).⁸ UNICEF (1996) noted that many more children die from starvation, sickness, and stress of flight than from the immediate effects of

⁴<http://www.wvi.org/experts/article/syria%E2%80%99s-children-%E2%80%93-how-conflict-can-harm-brain-development> , Syria's children – how conflict can harm brain development by Alison Schafer, Senior Programme Advisor, Mental Health & Psychosocial Support visited on 14th September 2016

⁵http://www.nasponline.org/resources/crisis_safety/children_war_general.aspx visited on 7th September 2016

⁶<http://www.newsguide.us/education/psychology/Children-War-and-Terrorism> visited on 7th September 2016

⁷Richard W. B. Ellis ,”Effects Of War On Child Health” The British Medical Journal, Vol. 1, No. 4544 (Feb. 7, 1948), pp. 239-245
Published by: BMJ

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⁸Psychological Effects of War and Terrorism on Children by AnirudhPurwar Arnab DhabalDiptarkaChakravarty

violence. In Africa it is reported that children die 20 times more frequently from lack of medical services and starvation than physical injuries from war.⁹

2) PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF WAR ON CHILDREN

- The frequency of occurrence of war or war like situations play a major role in shaping the psychological experiences for the children being affected by the war. Children who are being brought up in war-like situations are able to develop tough and aggressive mentality in order to accommodate with the ruthless environment. It is more difficult for children facing the gates of war for the first time to adapt to the change of events and the brutality coming with it.
- Displacement, death or injury to the parent contributes heavily to this experience, many children lose their parents during the war making them vulnerable to the ongoing war. Even if the children orphaned during the war are provided with residential capacity their childhood is inevitably changed leaving them with new guardians. The psychological impact is more deeper if the tragic death of the parent is witness by the child. Such events can leave an everlasting traumatic memory with is haunting reminiscence of the damage done during the war. The separation from either or both the parents can cause a huge emotional upheaval as the first and primary source of emotional attachment gets uprooted, leaving a void with is not easy to be filled.
- As modern day weaponry becomes more lethal and ground warfare is being heavily assisted through air support. Indiscriminate air attack leaves thousands of civilians injured with most effected being children. Despite many International Humanitarian Conventions

and Protocol binding nations to abide by such documents during the course of warfare there have been many instances where such humanitarian principals were being put at stake in order to attain swift victory or in order to accomplish surprise attack on the enemy state or organization.

- The lack of humanism witness by the child during the war and after it creates a social gap which makes them vulnerable to adopting such violent means in future. This non-attainment of pro-social maturity is due to mistreatment, disregard and constant exposure to violence. Constant War Zones around the world have witnessed more propensity of child soldier and potential future soldiers than regions with political stability. Many leaders prefer using children to adults, as they tend to be more submissive, less demanding, do not question orders and are easier to manipulate¹⁰.
- Middle East, Balkan, North Caucasus and Africa are the most prominent examples of such warzones as the local recruitment of children is very prevalent in order to instil the animosity for the warring enemy and to sustain the strength of soldier unit so as to maintain fresh blood . This exposure to violence on daily basis and persistent fear of a new attack leaves a psychologically devastating impact on the children. Despite no official count on the number of children involved in the 1991-1995 Balkan wars, Croatia's Association of Underage War Volunteers of the Homeland War estimates that some

⁹ <http://www.unicef.org/sowc96/1cinwar.htm> visited on 13th September 2016

¹⁰ Harvey Rachel, 'Recruitment and deployment of child soldiers – The beginning of the end?', *Child Right* [March 2000], Issue 164; <http://www.essex.ac.uk/armedcon/News%20Folder/Future/2000News/Comments/DraftOPCS.htm>, assessed on: 15/06/2007 ; accessed on 14th September, 2016.

3,000 boys fought in the conflict.¹¹ Not only ongoing war but the paranoia or possibility of war can also severely affect the psychology of a generation of children. Due to such atmosphere of warfare, the children are severely affected as they are deprived of a socially sound environment but instead have to cope with constant danger of life and injury, no proper infrastructure for education and healthcare

After the end of Second World with the defeat of Axis Powers, the fear receded and with the institution of United Nations, a new hope was conjured to prevent future warfare's like the two World Wars. This hope was not entirely dashed as there has been no Third World War but the polarization of world politics lead to the formation of two poles: Capitalist(USA) and Socialist (USSR). This gave birth to the era of Cold War and with it came the paranoia which affected an entire generation of children and majorly those of USA and USSR. The fear of a war took a prominent position in US educational system where school going children were being addressed to war propaganda. Films were being shown on nuclear explosion and how to what steps to be taken to be safe during such explosions and encouraged to "duck and cover" – hide under desks – to escape the effects.¹² In Soviet Union propaganda was being sold to the citizens with heavy censorship where media was state controlled. The Space and Destructive Weapon Race with USA was a source of pride. USA was portrayed as aggressor in order to generate the necessity of the motherland to be defended.

¹¹Child Soldiers Of The Balkans, January 23, 2016, http://www.rferl.org/content/Child_Soldiers_Of_The_Balkans/1349516.html, accessed on 12th Jan, 2016.

¹²Cold War paranoia: fear of the Reds and the Bomb, http://www.telegraph.co.uk/film/bridge-of-spies/cold_war_paranoia/, accessed on 21st September, 2016.

International Protocols prohibiting direct part in hostilities and recruitment of children

1) International Humanitarian Law

Additional Protocols to the four Geneva Conventions of 1949 (1977):

- The minimum age for recruitment laid down by the protocol is 15, it is applicable on the circumstances of armed conflict. This minimum standard is applicable on all parties in both international and internal armed conflict.

Article 77(2) of Additional Protocol I: relevant to international armed conflicts, states:

- The conflicting parties under this protocol are being bound to take such reasonable measures so as to ensure that the children below fifteen years of age don't get directly implicated and become part of the hostilities. The restriction on recruiting is relaxed in the 15-18 age group but the recruitment the parties to the conflict are persuaded by using the words "shall endeavour" to give priority to those who are the oldest.¹³

¹³ See: Protocol additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the protection of victims of international armed conflicts (Protocol I) (with annexes, Final Act of the Diplomatic Conference on the reaffirmation and development of international humanitarian law applicable in armed conflicts dated 10 June 1977 and resolutions adopted at the fourth session). Adopted at Geneva on 8 June 1977, "The Parties to the conflict shall take all feasible measures in order that children who have not attained the age of fifteen years do not take a direct part in hostilities and, in particular, they shall refrain from recruiting them into their armed forces. In recruiting among those persons who have attained the age of fifteen years but who have not attained the age of eighteen years the Parties to the

Article 4(3)(c) of the Additional Protocol II: relevant to non-international armed conflicts states:

- There shall be no recruitment in the armed forces or group of children who are below fifteen years of age and should be restricted to take direct part in hostilities

Despite sincerity from UN to curb the disastrous impact of war on children through the document the true tales of these unfortunate lands reveal a drastic contrast of what actually happens. Children have been massively deployed as troops and have been taking part in direct hostilities for years. The implementation and check on such violation is the major concern which often gets diluted in diplomatic compromises or in dealing with hostile states/ organization.

2) Customary International Humanitarian Law :

The law is formed out of rules that take its origin from the general practice accepted as law due to their customary nature as such practices were being used from over the years by different states. This customary law stands autonomous from treaty law. Thus the rules practiced in this law provides for, **“children must not be recruited into armed forces or armed groups” and that “children must not be allowed to take part in hostilities”**¹⁴, which is applicable to armed conflicts of both international and non-international nature.

conflict shall endeavour to give priority to those who are oldest.” ,
<https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%201125/volume-1125-I-17512-English.pdf>

¹⁴ See: Child Soldiers International,
http://www.child-soldiers.org/international_standards.php,
accessed on 18th September, 2016.

MONITORING AND REPORTING MECHANISM AND GUIDELINES MONITORING AND REPORTING MECHANISM (MRM) ON SEVERE VIOLATIONS AGAINST CHILDREN IN ARMED CONFLICT

The UN has been empowered by the resolutions made by the Security Council in order to efficiently take hold of the grave matters of violation against children during armed conflict. This resulted in formation of country-specific MRM (**Monitoring and Reporting Mechanisms**). These mechanisms are employed in listing of parties to the conflict according to the annual report on Children and Armed Conflict are responsible for recruitment and use of children, killing and maiming of children, sexual violence against children, and attacks on schools, hospitals and protected persons; the establishment of country-specific MRM¹⁵ Systematic and comprehensive monitoring, reporting and oversight, as requested by the United Nations Security Council resolutions 1539 and 1612, should cover all violations against children affected by armed conflict and could be performed by governments or non-State parties to the conflict.¹⁶

Through the task forces in conflict affected countries covered by the MRM, UNICEF and partners collect information on grave violations committed against children to share with the UN Security Council and to develop appropriate responses to respond to children's needs. As co-chair of each country-based MRM task force, UNICEF engages with government forces and rebel

¹⁵ Refer to the MRM Field Manual: **Monitoring and Reporting Mechanism on Grave Violations Against Children in Situations of Armed Conflict**. OSRSG-CAAC, UNICEF & DPKO, April 2010 (www.mrmtools.org)

¹⁶ Child Protection Information Sheet : **Protection Children During Armed Conflict** , http://www.unicef.org/chinese/protection/files/Armed_Conflict.pdf, accessed on 12th September, 2016.

groups perpetrating recruitment or use of children, killing, maiming, rape or other sexual violence to develop action plans to end and prevent these violations from taking place, noting that governments hold ultimate responsibility for protecting children and ending impunity for grave violations against children.¹⁷

The grave violations against children during armed conflict are being monitored through the creation of the Security Council Working Group on Children and Armed Conflict (SCWG-CAAC); and the requirement of dialogue with listed parties on the development of concrete and time-bound Action Plans to halt and prevent violations.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

Committed governments, international welfare organizations working with regional organization should work jointly to establish the mechanisms of monitoring and reporting. This should be done in order to bring the perpetrators of grave violence against children being done during an armed conflict to justice. Children are amongst the most vulnerable in any society and any conflict. Impunity for violations against children during armed conflict must end; our children deserve protection.¹⁹ There has been an increasing risk of the participation of under-18s in state armed forces in hostilities or otherwise being exposed to the risk associated with conflict as incidence of armed conflict or intensive armed violence is on the rise in some states in India. This risk is particularly manifest in areas affected by “Naxal violence”, where there have been past reports of children in the ranks of the

¹⁷ UNICEF, Child protection from violence, exploitation and abuse http://www.unicef.org/protection/57929_57997.html, accessed on 05th September, 2016.

¹⁸ Children and Armed Conflict; Working Paper No.1, The Six Grave Violations Against Children During Armed Conflict :The Legal Foundation October 2009 (Updated November 2013), accessed on 08th September, 2016.

¹⁹ Supra Note 19

Special Police Officers (SPOs), who have been known to be involved in counter-insurgency operations.

Child Soldiers International has serious concerns about the lack of effective age verification measures in place during recruitment in state armed forces, including paramilitaries and police forces in India. This is particularly problematic given the low rate of birth registration in the country.²⁰ It is difficult to pinpoint the recruitment pattern being employed to use children in an armed conflict. This is because there is no monitoring and reporting agency at work in India. Many NGOs have been working on this issue and provided various reports of such recruitment of children against armed opposition .

It is a failure on the part of the government to not establish systematic monitoring system to curb such recruitment and has instead relied on emergency and security legislation, including by detaining children suspected of association with armed opposition groups. There has been international concerns over underage recruitment in three areas: Jammu & Kashmir, areas affected by “Naxal violence” and Northeast India.²¹ It is necessary to make arrangement for monitoring and reporting mechanisms or to allow international agencies which can help in study the affected areas, reasons for its instability and how those children prone to means of violence can be detached from that hostile environment.

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SILENTLY ENJOYING THE PAIN

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Abstract:

A prostitute is a person, "who allows her body to be used for lewd purposes in return for payment". Prostitution is the sale of sexual services, such as oral sex or sexual intercourse, for money. Prostitution the word itself speaks about the plight of a women .It is not a problem which exists in India but exists throughout the world. Prostitution was a part of daily life in ancient Greece. In the more important cities, and particularly the many ports, it employed a significant proportion of the population and represented one of the top levels of economic activity. A prostitute or a *tawaif* or a *devadasi* as different times have called them in India are the facilitators of what some people say the "oldest profession of the world", Prostitution. In India prostitution is legal but the other related activities such as soliciting, pimping and brothels are illegal. There are more than 20 million prostitutes in India if a *Human Rights Watch* report is to be believed — and as many as 35% of them enter at an age less than 18. Prostitution was once upon a time a theme of Indian literature and arts for centuries. But the true face still lies hidden. This paper brings out the Problems faced by Prostitutes in Nagapattinam District of Tamilnadu, South India

Keywords: *Economy, Prostitution, Society Violence, Women*

India is one of the biggest markets for prostitution in Asia with Mumbai alone accommodating 200,000 prostitutes. [Trafficking](#), sex tourism and 'clandestine' nature of the industry is further imposing problems and spread of HIV/AIDS is on the rise at an alarming rate with woman being more prone to infection. Because of such nature and lack of regulatory body the real magnitude of severity of the actual situation cannot be comprehended. Every hour, four women and girls in India enter prostitution, three of them against their will. There are around 2.8 million prostitutes in the country and their number is increasing, as informed by Lok Sabha

A prostitute or a *tawaif* or a *devadasi* as different times have called them in India are the facilitators of what some people say the "oldest profession of the world",

Prostitution. But surely one must not be negative enough to think that this so called "oldest profession" is driven by need of physical pleasure only, but is rather driven by the economic and psychological distresses which contribute majorly to the entry of prostitutes in this profession.

In India [prostitution is legal](#) but the other related activities such as soliciting, pimping and brothels are illegal. There are more than 20 million prostitutes in India if a Human Rights Watch report is to be believed — and as many as 35% of them enter at an age less than 18. Prostitution was once upon a time a theme of Indian literature and arts for centuries. In Indian mythology there are many references of high-class prostitution in the form of celestial demigods acting as prostitutes. Poverty is one of the main causes which brings helpless woman to the doors of

prostitution. A woman distressed economically, often ill treated by parents or seduced by boyfriend who later turns out to be a pimp or procurer, and lastly uneducated or with a very low education level seldom finds any other avenues to feed herself other than prostitution. There are other social factors which are degrading the status of a woman. One such factor is the view of women being a commodity – which is pervasive in popular manifestations of culture in India.

Radical Feminism

Alison M. Jaggar and Paula S. Rothen Berg has listed out the traits of radical feminism in the following way:

1. Women were the first oppressed group in all the historical periods.
2. In every known society women's oppression is widely spread and virtually in existence;
3. Women's oppression is deep-rooted to the extent that it hard to eradicated and even other social changes like the abolition of class cannot remove this hardest form of oppression;
4. Women's oppression causes qualitative and quantitative sufferings to victims;
5. Women's sufferings due to oppression often go unrecognized mainly due to the sexist prejudices; and
6. Women's oppression provides a conceptual model to the understanding of the rest of the oppressions.

Radical feminists are on the conviction that all women are the natural allies while all men are the enemies of women because sex-class is the basic division in the whole world. Radical feminists view that this is a

fundamental political oppression. Hence Radical feminism aimed to organize all women politically so as to destroy the sex-based-class-system in every society.

Causes of prostitution:

- Ill treatment by parents.
- Bad company.
- Family prostitutes.
- Social customs.
- Inability to arrange marriage,
- Lack of sex education, media.
- Prior incest and rape.
- Early marriage and desertion.
- Lack of recreational facilities, ignorance, and acceptance of prostitution.
- Economic causes include poverty and economic distress.
- Psychological causes include desire for physical pleasure, greed, and dejection.

In modern India different kinds of prostitution is prevailing apart from prostitutes in brothel there are:

- Street prostitutes
- Bar dancers
- Call girls
- Religious prostitutes
- Escort girls
- Road side brothel
- Child prostitutes
- Fricatrice prostitutes
- Gimmick prostitutes
- Beat prostitutes

The prostitution leads to many health problems for the prostitutes like

- Cervical cancer
- Traumatic brain injury
- HIV
- STD

-
- Psychological disorders

OBJECTIVES:

1. To find out the Socio-Economic Status of Prostitutes.
2. To understand their real life situations for involving in Prostitution.
3. To study the Problem faced by women in prostitution.

SELECTION OF SAMPLING

There are nearly 1 lakh sex workers in Tamil Nadu and over 14,000 in Chennai alone. The researcher personally verified and found nearly 75 Prostitutes in Nagapattinam District, Tamilnadu. Therefore the member of respondents who were available during the time of data collection, were included in the study. The researcher has selected 75 transgender by adopting Snowball method. A well structured interview schedule was used to elicit data with regard to problem.

Result and Discussion

In Age wise, the majority 44% of them belongs to 20-30 years age category. In the Community Level, Out of the total, 46.67 per cent of them were belongs to SC. Regarding the educational level of the respondents, 49.34 per cent of them had their secondary education. More than half of the respondents 50.67 per cent were married.

Majority of the respondents 48 per cent states that poverty is the main reason for them to become a prostitute, 61.33 per cent of the respondents were doing prostitution in day time alone. To take care of their children, they will not be available at night time.

More than half of the prostitutes 57.33 per cent prefer lodge for doing prostitution. Two forth of the prostitutes 49.33 per cent were getting their customers by Pimp's. The People who are above the age of 50 (48%) were coming to prostitutes for prostitution.

In the sexual preference of the clients, 36 per cent of them were preferred Oral sex. 48 per cent of the respondents involves in prostitution for twice a week. In the Income level, 44 per cent of the prostitutes are getting above 4000 per week.

Opinion of Respondents about Prostitution

Regarding opinion of the respondents, it is understood that 46.66 per cent of them are considering it as part of life, 42.67 per cent of them are considering it as a source of income, 6.67 percent of them considering it as shameful, remaining 4 per cent of them are not considering it as wrong.

Opinion about Types of living

The above table explains about type of living which is liked by the respondents. Out of the total 46 per cent of them like to live with family. 29.33 per cent of them like to live individually. Finally only 24 per cent of them want to live with same group. They live by their own codes.

Distribution of respondents by Problems Faced

The above table explains that 57.33 percent of them are suffered from heavy body pain after having sex with their clients. 32 per cent of them were cheated by not giving of money after having sexual intercourse. 6.67 per cent of the respondents

were sometimes heavily beaten by clients due to heavy intake of alcohol. Finally 4 per cent of them were tortured and abuse in public places like toilets and mobile places. They are forced to have oral sex with local strangers.

Conclusion

A prostitute is said to be "one who commits common indiscriminate sexual activity for hire, in distinction from sexual activity confined exclusively to one person; therefore, a women who indulges in illicit sexual intercourse with only man has been said not to be a prostitute. On the other hand, it has been held, when a women is a common prostitute she does not depend alone upon the number of persons with whom she has illicit intercourse but rather may be judged from all the surrounding circumstances

Prostitution has been viewed in different forms. It has always aroused a wide range of emotions. Some are morally outraged by its presence, others merely curious. Some view it as a threat, others as a necessary evil. However, at least in recorded history, no society has completely accepted it as a valid and integral part of the community life. Prostitution is something to be abhorred or tolerated but never condoned. It is a nuisance, a problem, but above all, it is an embarrassment, for the religiously inclined, it reminds us that we are from the moral standards set for us by most scriptures. For the government, it is considered a sign of their mismanagement since prostitution is taken to symbolize a society in decline. Prostitution, besides having elements of venality and emotional indifference, enunciates the ingredient of exploitation.

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COMPULSORY PILOTAGE UNDER LAW OF SEA

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Abstract:

Compulsory pilotage refers to the norm under which it is compulsory for a vessel to be operated and controlled by a licensed pilot unless the vessel itself falls under the category of exempted ones. Almost all the states have created an exemption for boats that are licensed to the United States and operating in coastwise trade and for small vessels.

Pilotage is required beyond internal waters in the territorial sea of a coastal state including an international strait the LOSC imposes constraints on the coastal state regulation of foreign shipping within those waters. Those rights of the coastal state are not unilateral and must be understood in the context of not only the LOSC but also related mechanisms and frameworks, especially those dealing with ship safety and the regulation of navigation overseen by the International Maritime Organisation (IMO).

As per various statutes prescribed by various states, the owners of the ship are supposed to have a licensed pilot upon its entering a harbor. Collisions between vessels caused solely by the negligence of such "compulsory pilots" are governed by separate and distinct rules of liability under admiralty and the common law.

Personal liability is a prerequisite to the liability of a vessel. However this view has been considered as substantively non determinative because the courts have clearly abandoned the personification theory. This gave rise to a uniform application of the common law rule.

With the recent cases, it is certainly clear that the apex court is in itself stuck in this riddle. In fact the Supreme Court has long recognized the existence of an "abiding riddle" in imposing liability on the vessel but not its owner, but has failed to resolve it.

The researcher will look at these issues in the context of a compulsory pilotage regime that has been adopted by the international community and established through various case laws.

Keywords: *compulsory pilots, International Maritime Organization, liability under admiralty, personification theory.*

Pilotage has a long maritime history, and is closely connected with efforts to secure the safety of shipping and the safety of a port from wayward ships. Rose has defined a 'pilot' as "a person other than the master or one of the crew of a vessel who is taken on board especially for the purpose of conducting it through a river, road or channel, or from or into a port, particularly

with regard to his knowledge of local conditions."¹ Compulsory pilotage therefore arises when there is a legal or statutory obligation upon the master of a vessel to take on board a pilot while navigating through

¹ Francis Rose, *The Modern Law of Pilotage* (Sweet & Maxwell, London: 1984) 1.

certain waters.² This practice is longstanding, and has been identified as having occurred in the twelfth century. Compulsory pilotage refers to the norm under which it is compulsory for a vessel to be operated and controlled by a licensed pilot unless the vessel itself falls under the category of exempted ones. Almost all the states have created an exemption for boats that are licensed to the United States and operating in coastwise trade and for small vessels.³

It has been advocated, by Ivamy,⁴ that, if at any part of the voyage, a pilot is required, the vessel will be considered unseaworthy unless she obtains one. When the case law and the wording of the MIA 1906 are examined, it can be seen that the situation is not as straightforward as suggested by Ivamy. Whether the lack of a pilot renders the vessel unseaworthy will be examined by considering various possibilities.

If a vessel sails from a port where a pilot may be procured and the nature of the navigation requires one, she will probably be unseaworthy without one unless the master himself has competent knowledge of the navigation.⁵ Similarly, if a vessel sails from a port where pilot has been made compulsory by a statute,⁶ she will be considered unseaworthy without one. One might consider whether, sailing in violation of a statutory provision like this, would render

the voyage illegal and, thus, constitute a breach of the implied warranty of legality, instead of breach of seaworthiness. This can be extremely important as, unlike the breach of implied warranty of seaworthiness, the breach of implied warranty of legality cannot be waived by the insurer. The general rule established by the case law is that a breach of a safety regulation does not render the voyage illegal, but instead renders it unseaworthy.⁷

Expanded seaside State control of route in adjoining waters is turning out to be more basic as concern becomes both for the assurance and safeguarding of the marine environment and for the developing number of marine mischance prompting to genuine contamination of that environment. The most famous occurrence showing these patterns was the Exxon Valdez establishing in Alaskan waters in 1989. This prompted to the presentation by the United States of the Oil Pollution Act 1990 (OPA90), which built up a far reaching administration for managing ship-sourced marine contamination in the neighboring waters of the United States.

The Exxon Valdez episode was trailed by a few genuine contamination occurrences in European waters, including the tanker Braer destroyed off the southwest bank of Shetland in 1993, and the foundering of the tanker Erika off France in 1999 and of the tanker Prestige off Spain in 2002. These episodes have all served to increase the sensibility of coastal front States to the dangers of ship-sourced marine contamination in their adjoining waters, and have prompted to moves towards more prominent control of transportation in these waters. Human blunder was a key consider these episodes, especially those including the establishing of a ship.

² See Alex L. Parks and Edward V. Cattell Jr, *The Law of Tug, Tow and Pilotage* 3rd (Cornell Maritime Press, Centreville, Ma: 1994) 1018-1021 discussing the distinction between voluntary and compulsory pilotage.

³ <http://definitions.uslegal.com/c/compulsory-pilotage/> last visited on 31st January, 2016.

⁴ Ivamy, 1988, p 376

⁵ *Dixon v. Sadler* (1839) 5 M & W 405; and *The Framlington Court* 69 Fed Rep 300 (1934)

⁶ Article II of the Convention on the Regime of Maritime Port 1923 recognises the right of each state to organize and administer pilotage services as it thinks fit. In the UK, pilotage was originally the responsibility of independent individuals. Later, it was administered by the corporation of Trinity House, in certain districts, and by local authorities, elsewhere. Since the Pilotage Act (PA) 1987, it has been provided by competent harbor authorities.

⁷ *St John Shipping Corp v. Joseph Rank Ltd* [1957] 1 QB 267

Environmental Norms

The 1982 UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)¹ provides the framework for coastal State regulation of activities in adjacent waters. However, UNCLOS was formulated in a period when there was less concern for the health of the marine environment than there is at present and modern international environmental law was underdeveloped. Norms and principles for the preservation and protection of the marine environment have multiplied exponentially over the last two decades.

All State parties to UNCLOS have a general obligation to protect and preserve the marine environment,⁸ and UNCLOS Part XII sets out comprehensive rights and obligations for the preservation and protection of the marine environment. However, the navigational regimes in UNCLOS provide an example of the relatively lower level of concern for the marine environment that was current in the 1970s when UNCLOS was being negotiated. The regimes of straits⁹ transit passage and archipelagic sea lanes (ASL) passage apply to “all ships and aircraft”,⁹ and there is no clear right of the coastal or archipelagic State to prevent the passage of a vessel that might be perceived to be a serious threat to the marine environment.

Aldo Chircop had addressed the issue in the context of a ship in distress seeking a place of refuge in a strait used for international navigation concluding that:

While respecting the intention of the UNCLOS III negotiators to protect freedom of navigation through straits, one should be wary of applying too restrictive an interpretation that might not permit the coastal state to intervene to prevent a casualty from harming vital interests. It is possible to argue that international straits are not exempted from the right of protection of

the coastal state under general international law and the precautionary principle under international law apply.¹⁰

Many international conventions, as well as the desire of coastal States around the world to increase their controls over navigation in their adjacent waters, reflect the precautionary approach to preserving and protecting the marine environment. The second generation of environment conventions followed after UNCLOS. These reflect increased awareness of threats to the marine environment and incorporate concepts developed after UNCLOS, such as sustainable development and the conservation of biological diversity, as well as the precautionary principle.¹¹

The precautionary principle has its origins in the Rio Declaration,¹² one of the outcomes of the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) held in 1992 and now constituting a customary norm of international law.¹³ The precautionary approach reflects the notion that it is not necessary to await conclusive, scientific or technical evidence of the risks of damage to the marine environment before taking preventive action. ⁸ The precautionary approach post-dates UNCLOS by over a decade and its acceptance is a clear demonstration that the world has changed with regard to the balance between freedoms

⁸ UNCLOS, Article 192.

⁹ In accordance with UNCLOS Articles 38(1) and 53(2) respectively.

¹⁰ A. Chircop, “Law of the Sea and International Environmental Law Considerations for Places of Refuge for Ships in Need of Assistance,” in A. Chircop and O. Linden, eds., *Places of Refuge for Ships – Emerging Environmental Concerns of a Maritime Custom*, Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 2006, p. 246.

¹¹ R.R.Churchill and A.V. Lowe, *The law of the sea*, 3rd edition, Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1999, p. 336

¹² (1992) 31 *International Legal Materials* 818.

¹³ R. Rayfuse, “International Environmental Law”, Chapter 14 in S. Blay, R. Piotrowicz and M. Tsamenyi, eds, *Public International Law- An Australian Perspective*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997, pp. 360 – 1.

of navigation and marine environmental protection.¹⁴

Both Indonesia and Singapore backed Malaysia's insistence that Japanese plutonium shipments should not be routed through the Malacca Strait for fear of the environmental risks involved.¹⁵ The concern is also evident in the Revised Guidelines for the Identification and Designation of PSSAs adopted by the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) in 2005.¹⁶ These guidelines acknowledge that with the increase in global trade, shipping activities are also increasing with greater potential for adverse effects and damage to the marine environment. The guidelines are far more detailed and "liberal" in their approach than UNCLOS Article 211(6) reflecting the more sophisticated and comprehensive scientific understanding of the dangers posed by ships to the marine environment than was the case when UNCLOS was negotiated.¹⁷

Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas (PSSAs) are important measures that may be adopted by a coastal State as a means of regulating navigation in adjacent waters. PSSAs are designated by the IMO, which must be satisfied that the areas concerned require special protection because of their significance for recognised ecological, socio-economic and technical reasons and vulnerable to international maritime activities. The kinds of measure that might be taken by the coastal State include the designation of areas to be avoided, the

adoption of vessel traffic systems, speed restrictions and compulsory pilotage. Following the *Braer*, *Prestige* and *Erika* incidents, a proposal was tabled by several European States to have an extensive area of the north-eastern Atlantic declared a PSSA.¹⁸ The initial proposal was significantly watered down but restrictions on single-hull tankers and a mandatory ship reporting system have been implemented. However, differences still remain on the extent and effectiveness of PSSAs and the "PSSA discourse in the IMO is likely to remain contentious".¹⁹

Compulsory Pilotage: A Reexamination of Personification

As per various statutes prescribed by various states, the owners of the ship are supposed to have a licensed pilot upon its entering a harbor. Collisions between vessels caused solely by the negligence of such "compulsory pilots" are governed by separate and distinct rules of liability under admiralty and the common law.²⁰

The common law does not hold the ship owner personally liable. In fact it will be the damaging vessel which will be liable for damages in an in rem admiralty libel.²¹ However sometimes certain types of inadequacies and inconsistency determine the adequacy of the remedy provided to an injured party. For example, if the vessel

¹⁴ E. Gold, *Gard Handbook on Protection of the Marine Environment*, 3rd ed., Arendal: Gard AS, 2006, p. 62.

¹⁵ https://www.imo.int/mtg_docs/com_wg/ACLOS/ABL_OS_Con6/S1P1-P.pdf, last accessed on 22nd November, 2016.

¹⁶ *Revised Guidelines for the Identification and Designation of Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas*, adopted by IMO Assembly Resolution A.982(24), 1 December 2005 [hereinafter Revised Guidelines].

¹⁷ *West European Particularly Sensitive Sea Area (PSSA) – Comments made by the Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea of the United Nations (DOALAS) in connection with issues raised in document LEG 87/16/1*, IMO Doc. LEG 87/16/1, Annex 7 (23 October 2003).

¹⁸ J. Roberts, M. Tsamenyi, T. Workman and L. Johnson, "The Western European proposal: a "political sensitive sea area", *Marine Policy*, Vol., 29, 2005, pp. 431-440.

¹⁹ A. Chircop, "The Designation of Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas; A New Layer in the Regime for Marine Environmental Protection from International Shipping" in A. Chircop and T. McDorman, eds, *The Future of Ocean*

²⁰ Author(s): Dennis M. Robb, *The Compulsory Pilot Defense: A Reexamination of Personification and Agency*; Source: The University of Chicago Law Review, Published by: University of Chicago Law Review Stable; Vol. 42, No. 1 (Autumn, 1974), pp. 199-215 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1599132> Accessed: 12-02-2016 07:01 UTC

²¹ *Homer Ramsdell Transp. Co. v. La Compagnie Generale Transatlantique*, 182 U.S. 406 (1901).

steams out of the jurisdiction before it has been served in rem, it may escape service and liability altogether. The injured party's remedy would be more adequate if the common law permitted an in personam action against the ship-owner, who would presumably be easier to serve with process. The enigma of holding a vessel liable in the absence of an underlying personal liability of its owner results from an application of the personification theory of maritime liens.²²

Around four federal court of appeals have clearly denied the virtual paradox with reference to the context other than collisions caused by compulsory pilots. Personal liability is a prerequisite to the liability of a vessel.²³ However this view has been considered as substantively non determinative because the courts have clearly abandoned the personification theory. This gave rise to a uniform application of the common law rule.

With the recent cases, it is certainly clear that the apex court is in itself stuck in this riddle. In fact the Supreme Court has long recognized the existence of an "abiding riddle" in imposing liability on the vessel but not its owner, but has failed to resolve it.²⁴ It avoided it on both occasions by reversing the lower court's holding that no personal liability existed."

In *Calero-Toledo v. Pearson Yacht Leasing Co.*,²⁵ the court irrespective of the ship owner being innocent upheld the statutory

forfeiture of a ship. Though the majority affirmed the concept of independent liability of vessels in case of forfeiture, it certainly failed to answer the question of independent liability in other circumstances under a general theory of personification.²⁶

The undesirability of maintaining the personification fiction compels a reexamination of the bases of the rules of liability for collisions caused by the sole negligence of compulsory pilots. This comment first examines the cases that established those rules, both to expose the issues underlying the cases and to suggest the actual grounds of the decisions. It then considers the legal and policy issues to determine what the rule of liability should be, and concludes that the ship owner should be held liable whether the action is at law or in admiralty. Although this results in a rule like that currently existing in admiralty²⁷ rather than the contrary common law rule that courts generally have adopted as a natural consequence of rejecting the personification doctrine, it is supported by independent historical, legal and policy analysis instead of a conclusory application of the personification fiction.²⁸

Case laws:

The 19th century marked the genesis of the concept of compulsory pilot defense in the

²² See Toy, Introduction to the Law of Maritime Liens, 47 TUL. L. REV. 559, 563 (1973). The personification theory treats the ship as a juridical entity and has three distinct consequences: "(1) the maritime lien should attach irrespective of any personal obligation of the owner; (2) the limit of liability in an action in rem based on the existence of a maritime lien must be the value of the ship; and (3) the lien would remain indelible notwithstanding any change in ownership." Hebert, The Origin and Nature of Maritime Liens, 4 TUL. L. REV. 381, 383 (1930).

²³ See *United States v. Bissett-Berman Corp.*, 481 F.2d 764 (9th Cir. 1973).

²⁴ *Reed v. The Yaka*, 373 U.S. 410 (1963); *Guzman v. Pichirilo*, 369 U.S. 698 (1962).

²⁵ 416 U.S. 663 (1974).

²⁶ Justice Story's language in *The Palmyra*, 25 U.S. (12 Wheat.) 1, 14-15 (1827), and in *United States v. Brig Malek Adhel*, 43 U.S. (2 How.) 210, 233 (1844), is commonly quoted in conjunction with a citation to *United States v. The Little Charles*, 26 F. Cas. 979 (No. 15,612) (C.C.D. Va. 1818) (Marshall, Circuit Justice), to form "the usual trio of old forfeiture cases."

²⁷ A shipowner can limit his liability to the value of the vessel and the freight then pending by petitioning a federal district court, whether the action is originally brought in personam at admiralty or in a common law court.

²⁸ Author(s): Dennis M. Robb, *The Compulsory Pilot Defense: A Reexamination of Personification and Agency*; Source: The University of Chicago Law Review, Published by: University of Chicago Law Review Stable; Vol. 42, No. 1 (Autumn, 1974), pp. 199-215 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1599132> Accessed: 12-02-2016 07:01 UTC

court of law. Although the findings are no more a part of the legal language yet a short analysis of these cases is a must.

A. The Creole Case (1853)

In the year 1853, one of the first cases of pilotage defense came into being with *Smith v. The Creole*,²⁹ an admiralty case. If the vocabulary of the court is to be taken into consideration, earlier the ship owners were deliberately jeopardized irrespective of the pilot not being a voluntarily chosen servant. In their treatises, George Curtis and Joseph Story disapproved that view and accepted instead the prevailing British rule of non liability for the negligent acts of a compulsory pilot, finding it "only conformable to a principle of natural justice" to exempt the ship owner when his choice of a pilot was not free.³⁰

Justice Grier, while writing his opinion about the case; instead of confining his analysis to the specific legal situation before him, approached the question of liability in harbor collisions from the perspectives of common, civil, and maritime law as applicable to both voluntary and compulsory pilots. First, he recognized that if a colliding vessel guided by a licensed pilot were itself discharged, leaving only the pilot to respond in damages, the injured party would in most cases be denied a remedy.³¹

The Pennsylvania Supreme Court clearly stated that the pilotage statutes were not intended to obliterate the principle of law holding the owner of a vessel liable for the

conduct of the pilot. If Grier is to be believed then the whole concept of statutory compulsion which supposedly eliminates the relation of master and servant between pilot and owner is "more imaginary than real."³² Hence to conclude, third parties are entitled to treat the vessel as primarily liable for the acts of the owner, and in turn for the acts of his pilot, who would be considered the temporary master of the ship no matter how or why he was appointed.

*"It cannot be maintained that the circumstance of having a pilot on board, and acting in conformity with his directions, can operate as a discharge of the responsibility of the owners."*³³

B. The China (1858)

It took a collision between the steamship of China and the brig Kentucky to bring the concept of compulsory pilotage in the limelight and before the honorable supreme court. Here the major question of dispute was whether to follow the English rule or the rule of the American circuit and state courts.

While the Chinese relied upon various English precedents thereby pointing out the injustice of holding men responsible for the consequences of acts that the law compelled them to perform there only the libellant countered with policy arguments emphasizing that the British doctrine had never been adopted in the United States. A close reading of the opinion in *The China* reveals that the Supreme Court not only made a clear policy choice but also did so without turning to the old forfeiture cases as a way of personifying the offending vessel.³⁴

It was finally observed that the relation of master and servant does not change or gets

²⁹ 22 F. Cas. 497 (No. 13,033) (C.C.E.D. Pa. 1853).

³⁰ G. CURTIS, A TREATISE ON THE RIGHTS AND DUTIES OF MERCHANT SEAMEN 197 (1841); J. STORY, COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF AGENCY AS A BRANCH OF COMMERCIAL AND MARITIME JURISPRUDENCE ? 456a (3d ed. 1846).

³¹ Author(s): Dennis M. Robb , The Compulsory Pilot Defense: A Reexamination of Personification and Agency ; Source: The University of Chicago Law Review, Published by: University of Chicago Law Review Stable ; Vol. 42, No. 1 (Autumn, 1974), pp. 199-215 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1599132> Accessed: 12-02-2016 07:01 UTC

³² 22 F. Cas. at 506.

³³ Id. at 507-08, quoting *The Neptune the Second*, 165 Eng. Rep. 1380, 1381 (Adm. 1814). Story had cited *The Neptune's* countering the prevailing British rule that he incorporated into the main text of his treatise. J. STORY, supra note 20, at 595 n.1.

³⁴ Id. at 54-58 (summaries of the parties' arguments)

altered because a ship owner must employ a licensed pilot. If the common law is to be believed, the owners are responsible for the damages committed by their vessel and not the particular agent by whose negligence the injury was committed.³⁵

The court explained that the pilot temporarily took the master's place in guiding the ship and the principle of respondeat superior established the liability of the ship owner for damages negligently caused by either master or pilot. Thus, in its historical context, the rule of *The China* was grounded in the American common law and was applied by lower courts in suits at law and in admiralty.

C. Homer Ramsdell Co. v. Ia Compagnie GMrnale Trainsatlantique, 182 U. S. 406.

In this case the defendant's vessel, while under the command of a New York licensed pilot and wholly because of his fault collided with a pier owned by the plaintiff, the court held that the defendant was not liable in an action at common law, upon the ground that he was not personally at fault, as the employment of the pilot was compelled by the New York statute, the defendant could not be made responsible as principal.

This result in an action at law seems obviously correct. Yet the injured party may also have alternative remedies in admiralty, and since his rights are then governed by the principles of maritime law, it is by no means necessary that the same result should be reached. A libel in rem is based upon the distinct conception that the right to redress is against

the ship itself; in other words that the ship is the offending person regardless of the fact under whose control it was at the time of the collision. As culpability may thus be fixed upon the ship it has consequently been held

in the United States that a libel in rem will be sustained under such circumstances.³⁶

Conclusion:

The level and the amount of irregularity in the course while exempting a ship owner from the liability as well as the damages caused by the negligence of a compulsory pilot while holding the ship he owns liable should be eliminated, and the fiction that produces these inconsistencies should be obliterated where it serves no rational purpose. A close analysis of the original compulsory pilot cases reveals the use of the personification fiction in *Homer Ramsdell* in place of explicit consideration of a policy choice that underlay a rejection of the *China* rule. A preliminary consideration of the relevant policy issues indicates that a rule of ship-owner liability would be in consonance with the law of other maritime nations, with commercial needs and realities, and with modern principles of agency law. Reversal of the *Homer Ramsdell* rule, then, would establish a consistent rule of liability without resort to the doctrine of personification as a conclusory rationale.³⁷

³⁵ *Sherlock v. Alling* [93 U.S. 99 (1876)].

³⁶ *Compulsory Pilotage*; Source: *Harvard Law Review*, Vol. 15, No. 5 (Jan., 1902), pp. 405-406; Published by: Harvard Law Review Association; Stable URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1323542> ; Accessed: 12-02-2016 06:58 UTC